

Extraordinary Decisions®
Network-Derived Social Capital as a Survival Strategy on
Routes Through the Sahara Desert

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For Nhy

Per Veritatem Vis
Through Truth, Strength

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Questions Presented

- 1) How do migrants seek to develop and utilise network social capital
 - a) as a survival strategy on high-risk migration routes?
 - b) to facilitate integration into their host society?
- 2) How does analysing migrants' survival strategy on high-risk migration routes help us better understand states' moves toward increasingly securitised and extended enforcement regimes?

Abstract

This thesis examines how migrants have sought to develop and use network social capital as a survival strategy on high-risk migration routes and to facilitate integration into their host society. It focuses on the Sahara Desert context, which has been increasingly marked by intensified enforcement and risk to migrants amid the European Union's externalisation of migration control policies, acting with sending and transiting third countries in the African Union. The thesis draws on original field research involving interviews with 101 migrants who had the experience of travelling high-risk migration routes through the Sahara Desert. It also draws on interviews with 16 humanitarian organisation staff members working with migrants in these regions. Respondents identified several factors motivating efforts to derive network social capital that were central to their survival approaches. Leading factors included having limited resources, having no contacts at the intended destinations, lacking knowledge of migration routes, travelling alone and vulnerability to authorities, human smugglers and other actors. Each of these factors spurs them to derive network social capital in ways that include forming groups, humanitarian organisations, human smugglers, informal labour networks, social networking applications and the support of kinship connections. This thesis thus makes a significant contribution to the understanding of migrant agency, challenging some still-prevailing views of migrants as primarily threats or victims and instead presenting migrants as resilient survivors. It also situates their exercise of agency within the broader empirical and theoretical framework of increasing state securitisation of migration and their growing extraterritorial enforcement efforts. It works to advance understanding of the full implications of such policies while providing a fine-grained counter-narrative on them from migrants' contextually situated perspectives.

Statement of Originality

This work has not previously been submitted for a degree or diploma in any university.

To the best of my belief and knowledge, this thesis contains no material previously published or written by another person except where due reference is made in the thesis itself.

Daniel W. Szabo (he/him/his)

Keywords: extraterritorial, high-risk migration, international relations, migrant agency, political science, resilient survivor, securitisation.

**Human Research Ethics Committee
Ethical Clearance Certificate**

GRIFFITH UNIVERSITY HUMAN RESEARCH ETHICS REVIEW

Dear Dr Luis Cabrera

I write further to the additional information provided in relation to the provisional approval granted to your application for ethical clearance for your project "Extraordinary Decisions: The Determinants of Migrant Decision-Making on the Sahara Desert Crossing" (GU Ref No: 2019/317).

This is to confirm that this response has addressed the comments and concerns of the HREC.

The ethics reviewers resolved to grant your application a clearance status of "Fully Approved".

Consequently, you are authorised to immediately commence this research on this basis.

Regards

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Table of Contents

	Page
Acknowledgement of First Peoples	vii
Acknowledgements	viii
Dedication	xii
List of Acronyms	xiv
List of Figures and Tables	xx
Key to Icons	xxi
Preface	xxii
Chapter One: Framing the Questions	1
1.1 Introduction and Research Questions	3
1.2 Overview of Chapters	8
1.2.1 Chapter Two: Existing Research	8
1.2.2 Chapter Three: European Union Securitised Migration and Extraterritorial Enforcement in North and West Africa	9
1.2.3 Chapter Four: How Migrants Seek to Derive Network Social Capital On High-Risk Migration Routes	11
1.2.4 Chapter Five: Network-Derived Social Capital and Migrant Integration in the European Union	12
1.2.5 Chapter Six: A Discussion of Contribution and Significance	16
1.2.6 Chapter Seven: Conclusions	19
Chapter Two: Existing Research	21
2.1 Introduction	23
2.2 Background on High-Risk Migration	25
2.3 Migrant Agency	28
2.4 Foundations of Social Capital Theories	32
2.5 Migration and Network-Derived Social Capital	39
2.5.1 Network-Derived Social Capital and Decisions to Migrate	39
2.5.2 Network-Derived Social Capital and Migrant Integration	44
2.6 High-Risk Migration and Network-Derived Social Capital	46
2.7 Conclusion	50
Chapter Three: European Union Securitised Migration and Extraterritorial Enforcement in North and West Africa	53
3.1 Introduction	55
3.2 Conceptual Framework: Securitised Migration and Extraterritorial Enforcement	57
3.3 European Union Migration Control Mechanisms	62
3.3.1 Border Security	63
3.3.2 Technology-Based Initiatives	67
3.3.3 Voluntary Return and Reintegration— Regional Disembarkation Platforms	68

3.4 European Union Extraterritorial Enforcement Initiatives (Third Countries)	70
3.5 Enforcement: Central Mediterranean Route to Italy	74
3.5.1 Niger	75
3.5.2 Libya	79
3.5.3 Tunisia	82
3.6 Enforcement: Atlantic and West Africa Routes to Spain (Canary Islands)	84
3.6.1 Morocco	84
3.7 Enforcement: Western Mediterranean Route to Spain (Ceuta and Melilla)	86
3.7.1 Algeria	87
3.8 Conclusion	88
Chapter Four: How Migrants Seek to Develop Network Social Capital on High-Risk Migration Routes	93
4.1 Introduction	95
4.2 Data Collection Methods and Sites	97
4.3 Data Analysis Methods	106
4.4 Six Factors in Deriving Social Capital Through Networks During High-Risk Migration	108
4.4.1 Having Limited Resources	109
4.4.2 Having No Contacts at the Intended Destination	111
4.4.3 Lacking Knowledge of Migration Routes	114
4.4.4 Travelling Alone	116
4.4.5 Vulnerability to Authorities	118
4.4.6 Vulnerability to Human Smugglers and Other Actors	120
4.5 Six Ways Migrants Derive Social Capital Through Networks During High-Risk Migration	122
4.5.1 Forming Groups	123
4.5.2 Humanitarian Organisations	124
4.5.3 Human Smugglers	126
4.5.4 Informal Labour Networks	128
4.5.5 Social Networking Applications	129
4.5.6 Support of Kinship Connections	131
4.6 Conclusion	132
Chapter Five: Network Social Capital and Migrant Integration in the European Union	135
5.1 Introduction	137
5.2 Migrant Integration in the European Union	139
5.2.1 Common European Asylum System	143
5.2.2 Europeanisation of Migrant Integration	150
5.3 Member State Enforcement and Migrant Integration (Italy)	153
5.3.1 Asylum Procedures	154
5.3.2 Reception and Detention Systems	158
5.4 Anti-Migrant Rhetoric: A Barrier to Migrant Integration	163

5.5 Network-Derived Social Capital: An Integration Survival Strategy	176
5.6 Conclusion	182
Chapter Six: A Discussion of Contribution and Significance	186
6.1 Introduction	188
6.2 Advancing Understandings of High-Risk Sahara Routes	190
6.3 Advancing Understandings of Migrant Agency	192
6.4 Advancing Understandings of Migration and Social Capital	197
6.5 Securitisation and Neo-Colonial Power	200
6.5.1 Migration and Competing Regionalisms	200
6.5.2 Extraterritorial Enforcement and Neo-Colonial Power	202
6.5.3 Securitisation and Ethnicity: Internal Power	205
Chapter Seven: Conclusions	208
7.1 Summary Review	210
7.2 Directions for Future Scholarship	217
Afterword	221
Appendices	224
Appendix A: High-Risk Migration Participant Questions	225
Appendix B: Humanitarian Sector Participant Questions	227
Glossary	228
References	241

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Dedication

I dedicate this thesis to Peter Sutherland, UN Special Representative of the Secretary-General for International Migration, from 2006 to 2017. An advocate of equality and justice for migrants, including asylum seekers, refugees and other displacement populations, Peter believed in nations' shared responsibility to protect the vulnerable better.

In memory of
Rev. Thomas E. Chambers, C.S.C.
and
Randy Revell

List of Acronyms

ANCI	Italian Association of Local Authorities
ASGI	Association for Juridical Studies on Immigration
AU	African Union
BBC	British Broadcasting Company
CAS	Emergency Reception Centres (Italy) <i>(Centri di Accoglienza Straordinaria)</i>
CAT	Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment
CEPOL	European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Training
CIE	Centres for the Identification and Expulsion (Italy)
CJEU	Court of Justice of the European Union
COE	Council of Europe
COREPER	Committee of Permanent Representatives of the Governments of the Member States to the European Union (CotEU)
CotEU	Council of the European Union
COSI	Standing Committee on Operational Cooperation on Internal Security (CotEU)
CPR	Pre-removal Detention Centre (Italy) <i>(Previously CIE)</i>
CPSA	First Aid and Reception Centres (Italy) <i>(Centri di Primo Soccorso e Accoglienza)</i>
CRI	Italian Red Cross <i>(Croce Rossa Italiana)</i>
CRT	Tunisian Red Cross <i>(Croissant-Rouge Tunisien)</i>
CSDP	Common Security and Defence Policy (EU)
DCIM	Department for Combatting Illegal Immigration
DTM	Displacement Tracking Matrix

EASO	European Asylum Support Office
EC	European Commission
ECA	European Court of Auditors
ECB	European Central Bank
ECFR	European Council on Foreign Relations
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
ECOWAS	Economic Community of West African States
ECRE	European Council on Refugees and Exiles
ECtHR	European Court of Human Rights
EEA	European Economic Area
EIGE	European Union Institute for Gender Equality
EJN	Ethical Journalism Network
EMCDDA	European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction
EMHRN	Euro-Mediterranean Human Rights Network
EMN	European Migration Network
ENAR	European Network Against Racism
EP	European Parliament
EPRS	European Parliamentary Research Service
ERRN	European Return and Reintegration Network
ETAIS	European Travel Information and Authorisation System
EU	European Union
eu-LISA	European Agency for the Operational Management of Large-Scale IT Systems in the Area of Freedom, Security and Justice
EUAA	European Union Agency for Asylum
EUCAP	European Union Capacity Building
EUCO	European Council

EUI	European University Institute
EURODAC	European Asylum Dactyloscopy Database
EUROJUST	European Union Agency for Criminal Justice Cooperation
EUROPOL	European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation
EUROSTAT	Statistical Office of the European Union
EUROSUR	European Border Surveillance
EUTF for Africa	European Union Emergency Trust Fund for Africa
FIEP	International Association of Gendarmeries and Police Forces with Military Status
FTDES	Tunisian Forum for Economic and Social Rights (<i>Forum Tunisien des Droits Économiques et Sociaux</i>)
FME	Flow Monitoring Europe
FRONTEX	European Border and Coast Guard Agency
FRA	European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights
GBV	Gender-Based Violence
GAMM	Global Approach to Migration and Mobility
GCM	Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration
GDP	Global Detention Project
GRS	Global Reports Store
GTD	Global Terrorism Database
HDI	Human Development Index
HSRC	Homeland Security Research Council
HRW	Human Rights Watch
IARLJ	International Association of Refugee Law Judges
ICAI	Independent Commission for Aid Impact
ICC	International Criminal Court

ICMPD	International Centre for Migration Policy Development
ICPPED	International Convention for the Protection of All Persons from Enforced Disappearance
IGO	Inter-Governmental Organisation
IMISCOE	International Migration Research Network
INTERPOL	International Criminal Police Organization
IOM	International Organization for Migration
JHA	Justice and Home Affairs (EU)
JRC	Joint Research Centre (EC)
JVAP	Joint Valletta Action Plan
JMSR	Juma Map Services for Refugees
LAMP	Latin American Migration Project
LIBE	Committee on Civil Liberties, Justice and Home Affairs (EP)
LCGN	Government of National Accord Libyan Coast Guard and Navy
MAFE	Migrations between Africa and Europe Project
MEP	Member of the European Parliament
MexMP	Mexican Migration Project
MMP	Missing Migrants Project
MMC	Mixed Migration Centre
MOCADDEM	Operational coordination of the external dimension of migration (<i>Mécanisme Opérationnel de Coordination des Actions pour la Dimension Externe des Migrations</i>)
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organization
NCRA	National Commission for the Right to Asylum
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NUFFIC	The Dutch Organisation for Internationalism in Education

NWO	Dutch Research Council
OAU	Organization of African Unity
OCHA	United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs
ODI	Overseas Development Institute
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OHCHR	Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights
OSCE	Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe
PROMINSTAT	Promoting Comparative Quantitative Research in the Field of Migration and Integration in Europe
ReSOMA	Research Social Platform on Migration and Asylum
RMMS	Regional Mixed Migration Secretariat
SAI	System of Accommodation and Integration (Italy) <i>(Sistema Accoglienza Integrazione)</i>
SADR	Sahrawi Arab Democratic Republic
SIVE	Integrated Outdoor Surveillance System <i>(Sistema Integrado de Vigilancia Exterior)</i>
SNIA	National Strategy on Immigration and Asylum <i>(Stratégie Nationale d'Immigration et d'Asile)</i>
START	Study of Terrorism and Responses to Terrorism
SURENI	Sustainable Return from Niger <i>(Programme de Renforcement de las gestion et de la gouvernance des migrations et le retour durable au Niger)</i>
TCN	Third Country National
TCR	Tunisian Council for Refugee <i>(Conseil Tunisien Pour Les Refugies)</i>
TEU	Treaty on European Union
TFEU	Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union
TFPC	Treaty of Friendship, Partnership, and Cooperation

THBOR	Trafficking in Human Beings for the purpose of Organ Removal
TRC	Tunisian Red Crescent
UN	United Nations
UNCHR	United Nations Commission for Human Rights
UNCLOS	United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
UNDSS	United Nations Department of Safety and Security
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UNEGN	United Nations Group of Experts on Geographical Names
UNGM	United Nations Global Marketplace
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
UNISS	United Nations Integrated Strategy for the Sahel
UNODC	United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime
UNSMIL	United Nations Support Mission in Libya
UNSP	United Nations Sahel Support Plan
UNTOC	United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime
USDS	United States Department of State

List of Figures and Tables

Figures	Page
2.1 Elements in and Types of Social Capital	38
3.1 Conceptual Framework and Theoretical Emphasis	58
3.2 Mediterranean Rescue Operations 2015	65
4.1 Overview of High-Risk Migration Participants	98
4.2 Overview of Humanitarian Sector Participants	98
4.3 Data Collection Sites and High-Risk Migration Route Systems	100
4.4 Pilot Study 2017	101
4.5 Six Factors in and Six Ways Migrants Are Deriving Social Capital Through Networks During High-Risk Migration	122
5.1 Where Migration Fits in the EU Governance Structure	145
5.2 Overview of Asylum Procedures (Italy)	159
5.3 Anti-Migrant Rhetoric Cycle	166
5.4 Public Perception of Migrants (EU and Italy)	171
5.5 Ten Obstacles to Migrant Integration (EU and Italy)	171
7.1 High-Risk Migration Routes: Southeast Asia	218
 Tables	
5.1 Common European Asylum System Instruments	146
5.2 Hierarchy of Criteria for Determining the Member State Responsible (Dublin III)	149

Key to Icons

	Leadership		
	Missing		
	Public Information		
	Refugee		
	Resilience		

Preface

I take an inclusive approach and consider migrant to be an umbrella term. The label encompasses several distinctions primarily related to the cause (s) and purpose of migration. Therefore, migrant includes asylum seekers who seek international protection, refugees whose asylum claim is accepted and those in the process of migration for many reasons. Internally displaced persons, another category of migrant, is separate from my analysis. Distinctions among the different types of migrants are made throughout this thesis as warranted.

My thesis focuses on international migration. Migrant indicates international migration unless otherwise specified. I also note that some of the participants in this research shared their high-risk migration experience and no longer think of themselves as a migrant. They either have returned to their country of origin or integrated into a new life in a destination country.

I discuss select high-risk migration routes, the Atlantic, West Africa and Western Mediterranean Routes to Spain and the Central Mediterranean Route to Italy. When you read the 'route' label, it invariably denotes a series of routes instead of a singular route. Globally there are other high-risk migration routes, Central America and Mexico Routes to the United States—East and Horn of Africa—Middle East Routes from Iraq, Syria and Turkey—Eastern Mediterranean Route to Greece—Balkan Route through Eastern Europe—Southeast Asia Routes, including from or through countries like Bangladesh, Malaysia and Myanmar (Contant 2015). These additional high-risk migration routes require increased intervention by researchers. Additionally, country names follow the official UN list (United Nations Group of Experts on Geographical Names 2011).

I use the phrase survivor of gender-based violence and survivor of trafficking instead of victim of gender-based violence and victim of trafficking with purpose. It is no overstatement to assert the importance of this language in humanitarian response, psycho-social support strategies and within scholarship. The data is overwhelming. The quicker someone with the experience of abuse thinks of themselves as a survivor, the greater the potential for healing and recovery.

On extraterritorial enforcement, I examine the externalisation of migration control by the European Union to sending and transiting countries in North and West Africa. Other extraterritorial actions include carrier liability, the stoppage of vessels in international waters, visa control mechanisms, etc. These are not included in this thesis, though they are equally important areas for investigation. Additionally, at some points, I reference 2023 sources occurring after my Dec 2022 submission date. These additions took place during the minor revision phase.

Finally, I keep the focus on migrant agency and network-derived social capital. Therefore, the flow is in a direction other than approaches to migrant decision-making. At the same time, the title of this work is deliberate. It best encapsulates the entire emotional context of the experience. The accounting that follows is a record of resilience, struggle and Extraordinary Decisions (Szabo 2021) of individuals in their quest to survive along some of the most high-risk migration routes in the world.

‘Our fundamental obligation is to save and protect lives.’

- Peter Sutherland, 9 October 2015

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Chapter One

Framing the Questions

1.1 Introduction and Research Questions

1.2 Overview of Chapters

1.2.1 Chapter Two: Existing Research

1.2.2 Chapter Three: European Union Securitised Migration and Extraterritorial Enforcement in North and West Africa

1.2.3 Chapter Four: How Migrants Seek to Derive Network Social Capital On High-Risk Migration Routes

1.2.4 Chapter Five: Network-Derived Social Capital and Migrant Integration in the European Union

1.2.5 Chapter Six: A Discussion of Contribution and Significance

1.2.6 Chapter Seven: Conclusions

We spent a week in the desert. Some people, their water, it finished... I saw a woman and her baby. They were crying for water. Their water was finished.

- Male migrant, from Sierra Leone, interviewed in Niamey, Niger

1.1 Introduction and Research Questions

Since 2014, over 50,000 migrants have died on high-risk international migration routes, including over 25,000 presumed to have drowned in the Mediterranean Sea. Moreover, over 5,000 are missing and considered fatalities to the ravages and risk of traversing Sahara Desert routes (Missing Migrants Project 2022a; 2022b). These estimates are considered vast undercounts of the many years' worth of deaths occurring in both migration contexts. They highlight how migrants travelling high-risk migration routes from North and West Africa to Europe, the focus of this thesis, and elsewhere, face countless dangers.

High-risk migration is defined here as the movement of persons on routes where significant numbers of fatalities have occurred, and where travel conditions are such that those on the move face a heightened likelihood of exploitation and mistreatment, injury or death. They are understood in this thesis to typically emerge in contexts of securitised migration, where the movement of persons is framed by political and other elites in receiving states as a security threat, rather than a routine set of economic and social practices. Such securitisation generally leads to a hardening of borders, often an extraterritorial extension of receiving states' migration enforcement through agreements with transit or sending states, and overall, a lack of orderly, regular and safe migration pathways (International Organization for Migration 2019a; Danish Institute for

International Studies 2022). Increasing numbers of migrants have narrowing options than to travel on high-risk routes.

Journeys on such routes through the Sahara Desert, the Sonoran Desert of northern Mexico and the southwestern United States, among others, are long and arduous. Many succumb to thirst, hunger and exhaustion before reaching their destination. Sea and river crossings pose additional perils, with tens of thousands lost on crossings in recent decades. In addition to the physical toll of high-risk migration, migrants face the risk of exploitation by human smugglers and traffickers. These individuals often prey on migrants who are desperate to reach their destination, promising them safe passage in exchange for money or other valuables. All too often, these promises go unfulfilled, and migrants find themselves in even more danger, including being trafficked and trapped in ongoing exploitation. Those who do make it to the other side still risk being detained or deported by migration enforcement officials. Even if migrants avoid detention, they often arrive at their destination with little more than the clothes on their backs.

Thus, migrants are often framed effectively as passive victims, including by advocates of migrant rights. Alternately, they are framed as villains by migration restrictionists – as actors violating the law in complicity with smugglers (Mainwaring 2016). This thesis adopts a fundamentally different view, investigating migrants as *resilient survivors*: persons who exemplify a capacity to adapt - through an interaction of risk and protective factors - in the face of adversity and experience, amidst high-risk migration and migrant integration (Knight et al. 2022). Migrants are understood as active participants exercising creative agency and displaying resilience in highly challenging contexts, often as a means of bare survival. Through such a framing, this

thesis seeks to advance understandings of migrant agency in both practical and theoretical terms. In practical terms, it offers a detailed view of how migrants seek to exercise agency as a means of survival on high-risk routes. It draws on fieldwork in Africa and Europe which involved semi-structured, open-ended interviews with 101 migrants in Italy, The Gambia and Niger conducted in two phases during 2019 and 2020. Fieldwork also included 16 interviews with staff of humanitarian organisations providing aid to migrants in various displacement contexts in both regions.

Additionally, a 2017 pilot study for which I conducted 24 semi-structured, open-ended interviews with migrants at a transit centre in Niamey, Niger, informs this thesis.

The fieldwork illuminates a view of migrant agency and resilience on such routes as significantly focused on the development of networks, and on efforts to derive forms of social capital from them that are central to migrants' survival strategies. It also examines how migrants strive to draw on networks developed in transit when they arrive in Europe and how they seek to develop new networks there. Thus, this thesis offers extended engagement with theories of network-derived social capital (Lin 1999; Putman 2000; Aguilar and Massey 2003; McKenzie and Rapoport 2007; Kalter and Will 2016; Adedeji 2021). It contributes to understandings of the importance of such social capital for people in some of the most vulnerable migration contexts. Moreover, it advances understanding of the types of network social capital migrants seek to derive, and how. Finally, it highlights the role resilience can be understood to play in conceptions of migrant agency, in particular on high-risk routes.

In broader theoretical terms, the thesis contributes an understanding of the implications of the securitisation of migration and the extraterritorial enforcement of the same by destination states. It details how political elites in Europe and elsewhere have

worked to securitise migration, framing it again as primarily a threat to their people rather than a set of economic and social practices (Buzan et al., 1998; Huysmans 2000; Aslan 2022). They use such a security framing to justify hardening borders and more comprehensive enforcement and surveillance within destination states. Such a framing also plays an integral role in efforts by states in Europe and the European Union (EU) to extend extraterritorial enforcement through cooperation agreements with African states (Minnucci 2016; Mainwaring 2019; Crisp 2019). These agreements provide some development aid and extensive funding to increase African states' powers to block or deter migration. As a result, they have intensified the risks migrants face on Sahara Desert land routes and the Atlantic (Canary Islands) and Mediterranean Sea crossings.

This thesis thus examines migrants' exercise of agency on high-risk routes through the development of social networks, or use of existing ones, in the context of securitised migration and extraterritorial enforcement. Migrants' views of their own experiences and hardships offer a window into the practical implications of the securitised-extraterritorial dynamic. Moreover, they direct the thesis toward some more profound theoretical implications. These include an understanding of competing regional migration regimes. The EU and the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) formally affirm free movement within their borders. EU pressure, however, has meant that, in practice, movement is increasingly restricted in the ECOWAS region. Thus, 'fortress Europe' can be said to have increasingly extended to a 'fortress Africa,' where European interests dominate. That, in turn, raises some essential questions about regional hegemony or domination of post-colonial states. That domination, it is argued, is reinforced in the treatment of migrants from Africa within European destination states.

Overall, then, this thesis explores two primary Research Questions:

- 1) How do migrants seek to develop and utilise network social capital
 - a) as a survival strategy on high-risk migration routes?
 - b) to facilitate integration into their host society?
- 2) How does analysing migrants' survival strategy on high-risk migration routes help us better understand states' moves toward increasingly securitised and extended enforcement regimes?

Below I offer a summary of the investigation by chapter. I want to close this section with a brief note on author positionality. I follow Denzin here in understanding that 'The qualitative researcher is not an objective, politically neutral observer who stands outside and above the study of the social world' (Denzin 1989, p. 3). Instead, the researcher is an agent shaped by contexts and experiences. In this case, those include Western academic frames of reference (Australia and Canada) and experiences as a staff member of International Organization for Migration (IOM), designated as an UN-related organisation in the UN system (United Nations Global Marketplace 2021). The backgrounds and personal profiles of those I interviewed were typically quite distinct from mine. I have strived to understand their experiences and present them from their point of view, focusing as they do on agency, the importance of relying on others and resilience.

1.2 Overview of Chapters

1.2.1 Chapter Two: Existing Research

Chapter Two situates the thesis in the salient literature on migrant agency and social capital. It also highlights some underdevelopment in the literature on how migrants seek to develop networks in transit and derive social capital from them, especially on high-risk routes. It thus provides a theoretical foundation for understanding the exercise of migrant agency and highlighting the thesis's practical and theoretical contributions.

The existing research at the intersection of high-risk migration, migrant agency and network-derived social capital provides essential insights into how migrants navigate hostile environments. It has highlighted the innovative strategies employed by people on the move to secure resources, find safe havens and survive perilous journeys. The chapter will survey the existing literature on this subject to explore how social capital is developed through networks to aid migrants' in navigating their precarious circumstances while in transit. It will draw on that scholarship to shed light on the existing space in understanding regarding how and why these strategies have emerged over time. Doing so will provide a comprehensive overview of current knowledge about this interwoven nexus between high-risk migration, migrant agency and social capital.

In addition to the existing literature on the subject, the chapter will also consider areas where the existing literature is underdeveloped. For example, while researchers have provided important insights into the role that networks of family, friends and colleagues play in migration processes, there remains a lack of information about the social mechanisms through which such networks develop when migrants are in transit, on high-risk routes.

In Chapter Two, I begin by offering some background on the various high-risk migration routes discussed in this thesis, providing data on fatalities disaggregated by the route and some of the conditions migrants are likely to face. I then highlight the literature on migrant agency, the victim and villain framings and where treatments of migrant agency coalesce with migrant experiences on some of these routes in question. I discuss the foundations of social capital theories, including the elements and the types of social capital. I then unpack network-derived social capital and review the development of bonding, bridging and linking categories. The discussion then moves to places in the literature where migration and network-derived social capital link up. Specifically, I look at how network-derived social capital influences migration decisions and its importance in migrant integration. I explore the studies of others in several different migration contexts, with emphasis on the work of Schapendonk (2011; 2015), who has similarly studied migration patterns and survival strategies on high-risk Sahara routes. I highlight the contributions he has made, and areas his work leaves unexplored, in particular why and how migrants seek to develop networks and derive forms of social capital from them *in transit* on high-risk routes. A second novel contribution discussed is the way this thesis focuses on how migrants who have formed such networks often continue to draw on them in various ways once they reach destination countries.

1.2.2 Chapter Three: European Union Securitised Migration and Extraterritorial Enforcement in North and West Africa

The conceptual framework of this thesis centres around two elements of migration governance: securitised migration and extraterritorial enforcement. Since the mid-1990s, the EU has pursued a policy stance that frames migration primarily as a security

issue – as a threat rather than a set of economic and social processes – an approach described as securitisation. Framing migration in this way typically provides a rationale for hardening border enforcement to tackle clandestine migration flows.

Chapter Three provides background for understanding how securitised migration informs policies of extraterritorial regulation and enforcement - i.e., extending the reach of EU law beyond its territorial boundaries - with particular attention paid to the conceptual and legal aspects of migration governance. It is argued that the success of such policies has been limited, both in terms of their effectiveness in tackling clandestine migration flows and their political implications for developing countries in Africa. Ultimately, the chapter provides a way to understand EU approaches to securitised migration better and comprehend its impacts of extraterritorial enforcement on today's global human mobility landscape.

In the chapter, I start by discussing the two pillars of my conceptual framework. First, I look at the development of security framings of migration from fear-based concerns of the spread of illness and terrorism threats in the EU. Second, I discuss the genesis of extraterritorial enforcement and the importance of this aspect of EU migration governance. I note several EU migration control mechanisms, from border security to technology-based initiatives, Voluntary Return and Reintegration programmes and proposals such as regional disembarkation platforms. I then delve into some of the specific arrangements, frameworks and relationships the EU and its Member States have in place. I spend the remainder of the chapter outlining the specific enforcement measures implemented along three central high-risk migration route systems and five countries in Africa engaging with the EU to restrict onward mobility. I start with the Central Mediterranean Route to Italy and arrangements with Niger, Libya

and Tunisia. I then move to enforcement of the West Africa and Atlantic Routes to Spain (Canary Islands), with Morocco as the leading African player. Finally, I look at the enforcement of the Western Mediterranean Route to Spain (Ceuta and Melilla) and specifically the relationship with Algeria, which migrants travel through on their way to Morocco and Spain.

1.2.3 Chapter Four: How Migrants Seek to Derive Network Social Capital on High-Risk Migration Routes

This chapter presents fieldwork undertaken in Africa and Europe to highlight how social capital plays a pivotal role in migrants' navigation of high-risk routes. Specifically, migrants attempt to develop networks to access information and resources to travel more safely, for transportation, and to find forms of labour in transit. In the context of high-risk migration routes through the Sahara Desert, the research presented in this chapter will show that migrants rely heavily on the forming of groups and gathering information from others met along the journey and on smugglers to assist in onward movement. These networks that migrants develop become an invaluable source of knowledge about potential dangers and how best to navigate them. Many migrants seek out these networks at various stages throughout the journey.

The chapter begins with details on data collection sites and methods involved in my fieldwork, which included interviews with 101 migrants from 11 countries of origin in Niger, Italy and The Gambia and 16 civil servants in seven specialised fields from humanitarian organisations spread across seven countries. Next, I describe the two phases of the data collection process regarding locations and surrounding environments and how interviews took place. These interviews took various forms, from face-to-face

interventions by me in Niger and Italy, to remote linkups coordinated with the help of a research assistant on the ground in The Gambia. I then describe the data analysis methods implemented for this project. The primary methods included open and axial coding, with triangulation of other sources to strengthen reliability. I then describe in detail the two main arteries of this chapter resulting from these interviews. The first involve six primary risk factors which motivate migrants to seek to form social networks in transit on high-risk routes. These six factors that migrants describe are: (1) having limited resources, (2) having no contacts at the intended destination, (3) lacking knowledge of migration routes, (4) travelling alone, (5) vulnerability to authorities and (6) vulnerability to human smugglers and other actors. These six factors motivate migrants to develop networks or try to derive valuable forms of social capital from existing networks. The field research found six specific ways migrants seek to derive network social capital during high-risk migration. These include (1) forming groups in transit, (2) connecting with humanitarian organisations, (3) connecting with human smugglers, (4) integrating into informal labour networks, (5) using social networking applications and (6) seeking support from kinship networks.

1.2.4 Chapter Five: Network-Derived Social Capital and Migrant Integration in the European Union

Networks, while providing a valuable source of support during the high-risk migration experience, also extend beyond it. Chapter Five discusses how the network-derived social capital acquired in transit on high-risk routes can also be essential for migrants as they navigate their new environment and attempt to gain security and stability within it. Through these networks, migrants can gain information on employment prospects,

housing options, access to healthcare services, education and much more. In addition, this network-derived social capital further facilitates the integration of migrants into their destination country and host community. As a result, network-derived social capital is essential in aiding successful migrant integration and survival.

Chapter Five also highlights how the migrant integration process is complex and differs between those who apply for asylum, those ineligible for an asylum claim and those awaiting a decision or appeal. Those applying for asylum are subject to an EU-wide system that determines their eligibility according to specific criteria. Depending on the outcome, they may be granted refugee status or subsidiary protection or denied and deported for the return migration home. Refugees and individuals with subsidiary protection have certain rights, such as access to services and support from public authorities. However, those who are denied asylum may remain in Europe in some circumstances with limited access to services and state protection. Finally, there is another category of migrants who are not part of the asylum system at all. This group is arguably in the most precarious position as they do not enjoy any legal residence or any access to services except what is available through humanitarian assistance and other forms of non-governmental support.

This chapter identifies the barriers to migrant integration and the network-derived social capital used to attempt to overcome these barriers. Through a combination of formal and informal networks, these resources may help provide access to more opportunities, protection and support. It is through such resources that migrants create resilient identities to allow them to function within their host society. This resiliency also reflects in their strategies of self-advocacy, which involve challenging

existing anti-migrant rhetoric and stereotypes when engaging with formal institutions, seeking employment or building connections with the community.

In the chapter, I begin by discussing the Common European Asylum System which is a set of directives and policies which govern migrant access to asylum in the EU. These policies aim to manage claim of those fleeing persecution and further control migration across EU. As part of this system, countries have implemented measures such as border controls, visa requirements and asylum-seeker processing centres. I help to orientate the reader to where migration fits in the larger EU governance structure and include which agencies, courts, institutions and ministries have migration woven into their portfolios. I provide the main instruments of the CEAS and include a hierarchy of criteria used for determining the Member State responsible for a migrant's asylum claim better known as the Dublin III Regulation. Dublin III establishes rules on how Member States must cooperate in determining responsibility and mechanisms for appeals and returns.

I then discuss the Europeanisation of migrant integration. Proponents of migrant integration policies at the supranational level have long argued that migrant populations need to be better integrated into European societies to ensure migrant safety, reduce bureaucratic limbo and prevent deaths at sea. Such an approach requires a shift from the current state-level control of migrant access and policy towards one of Europeanisation, whereby migrant policies are harmonised across Member States by Brussels as the epicentre of EU power.

However, there is growing resistance in many Member States to migrant integration and multicultural policies directed at the supranational level due to fears about losing national sovereignty. This resistance has led to increasing tensions between

those advocating for more robust migrant integration policies on a supranational level and those who oppose such policies nationally. In the next section, I use Italy as a case study and show how Member States heavily securitise migrant integration. Upon arrival in the country, migrants must undergo various security checks and obtain legal documents that allow them to continue their journey or seek protection. Those who are deemed ineligible for asylum may be detained and deported. These measures have significantly impacted migrant populations within Italy, creating an atmosphere of fear and insecurity which may substantially impede migrant integration in the cities and countryside. In addition, this section reviews both the asylum procedures at the country level and the reception and detention systems that many migrants experience. There are also often substantial restrictions on migrant access to social services such as employment and housing. This further reinforces the idea of securitisation among migrant populations, as those seeking to integrate into Italian society are cut off from accessing the necessary resources required for successful integration.

In the next section I discuss how the securitisation of migration has been an increasingly influential factor in migrant integration policies within the EU. It is commonly accepted that migrant integration frameworks have come to be defined by this security-centred approach, which places far greater emphasis on migrant control than on migrant rights or welfare. This context is marked by a rise in anti-migrant rhetoric both within and outside the EU. This type of discourse seeks to legitimise an environment of fear, portraying migrant communities as potential threats instead of potential contributors to the host society. As such, anti-migrant rhetoric can pose a significant barrier to migrant integration and can be a significant risk factor driving migrant social network formation.

I conclude the chapter by discussing how network-derived social is used as an integration survival strategy. I note how, besides the general risks posed within a securitised integration context, migrants face risk factors including the lack of contacts at their destination, limited resources and vulnerability to authorities. Such risks help to drive efforts to gain access to network-derived social capital, including by continuing to rely on ties made during transit, or forming new groups to derive bonding and bridging forms of social capital. By doing so, migrants can gain access to helpful resources that aid the transition into their new environment while also helping them develop meaningful relationships with individuals who understand their circumstances.

1.2.5 Chapter Six: A Discussion of Contribution and Significance

Chapter Six details the broader contributions made by the thesis and ties its strands of analysis together. Discrete contributions highlighted include both practical and theoretical ones: (1) an improved comprehension of Sahara Routes, (2) a greater understanding of migrant agency and migrants as resilient survivors, (3) how migration and social capital are related and (4) securitisation and neo-colonial power. The last is divided into three subsections: (4a) migration and competing regionalisms, (4b) extraterritorial enforcement and neo-colonial power and (4c) securitisation and ethnicity: internal power.

In the chapter, then, I first discuss how the thesis has sought to advance understandings of the surroundings and threats faced by migrants on high-risk journeys through the Sahara Desert. In particular, it highlights how international political agreements shape migratory routes and influence the decisions of those who embark on them. Additionally, the fieldwork conducted for this study helps us to gain insight into

migrants' perspectives, providing a valuable source of understanding regarding one of the most perilous migration contexts in the world.

In the next section, I discuss how, by exploring these migrants' lived experiences, this thesis provides an alternate framing of migrants as active agents rather than solely as passive victims or perpetrators. I will show that migrants exercise agency as part of a resilient survivor strategy during their high-risk migration experience and migrant integration in destination countries. Ultimately, it is hoped that the findings presented here will contribute to developing more effective ways to support our understanding of those undertaking high-risk migratory journeys. Furthermore, the fieldwork provides evidence of how migrants exercise agency on routes characterised by extreme danger and vulnerability. Finally, how migrants seek out sources of support and information from communities along their journey are testament to their resilience and resourcefulness – despite facing multiple adversities both before and during their travels.

This thesis makes a specific contribution to social capital theories in understanding how social capital derives through networks and its role on high-risk routes. Social capital theories broadly premise that people may benefit from their position in a network through the relationships they maintain with other actors. Consequently, social capital is significant concerning high-risk routes, such as those taken by migrants. I reinforce that networks, and hence social capital, help shape individuals' experiences regarding migration and provide resources to help them mitigate risks along their journeys. This research's findings will help inform theoretical and practical approaches to understanding the dynamics of high-risk migration movements.

The next section focuses on the contribution to the idea of securitisation and neo-colonial power. It is divided into three subsections: migration and competing regionalisms, extraterritorial enforcement and neo-colonial power, and securitisation and ethnicity in migrant integration. In the first subsection I discuss the competing regionalisms of the EU and ECOWAS, embodied in their freedom of movement regimes, are increasingly in conflict with one another due to the extraterritorial enforcement of migration by the former. Such activities raise essential questions regarding how population mobility is affected by different territorial, organizational and conceptual borders and the implications thereof. In effect, while the EU embraces the principles of free movement for its own regional integration project, its increasing emphasis on extraterritorial migration enforcement serves to hamper the development of the emerging free movement regimes in ECOWAS and the African Union. Such tensions remain only lightly explored in the literature, and the thesis serves to highlight them as implications of the overarching securitisation of migration in and by the EU.

The second sub-section focuses on related neo-colonial power dynamics, and how the extraterritorial enforcement of EU migration may reinscribe colonial-era domination of African states and populations by European ones. First, it provides historical perspectives that lay the foundation for present-day partnerships between African countries and the EU to deter onward mobility. It explores how these collaborations have shaped current policies regarding migrant rights and ensured their protection, and it considers specific case studies from Algeria, Libya, Morocco, Niger and Tunisia to provide an accurate understanding of how neo-colonial power dynamics affect policymaking decisions. Highlighted are ways in which extraterritorial

agreements have been shown to be less a partnership among state equals than a re-inscription of state hierarchies of control resonating from the colonial era.

In the last subsection of this chapter, I extend the neo-colonial analysis to focus on how migrant integration is increasingly racialised and anti-migrant rhetoric serves to frame many African migrants as security threats, and also as subordinate to white Europeans. I reinforce how the anti-migrant rhetoric cycle can perpetuate an environment of xenophobia. Host countries and their political leaders exploit citizens' fears through inflammatory language about migrants 'stealing' jobs or engaging in criminal activities, while ethnicity and race are implicit or often explicit in their threat framings. Media coverage often reinforces these stereotypes and amplifies negative stories about migrants, including asylum seekers and refugees. These elements contribute to heightened racism and hostility towards migrants to justify ever stricter measures against them.

1.2.6 Chapter Seven: Conclusions

In this chapter I provide a concise summary overview of the ground covered in this thesis. I include a review of the main arguments and a reinforcement of the findings. I also discuss some possible avenues for extending participation in future research. The first is to continue working and developing the inquiries in the Sahara-Sahel region, delving more deeply into migrant survival strategies and into ways in which African regional free movement development is challenged by EU extraterritorial enforcement on the ground. The second is to expand these levels of inquiry into migrant agency and network-derived social capital to other high-risk migration routes, such as those through Southeast Asia. There is significant room for comparative work involving those and

other routes. The third is to explore different theories, such as prospect theory, to see how it interacts with high-risk migration and the decisions on the risk that migrants are making. Finally, this thesis concludes with the aspiration that the aims established at the beginning are successful the conclusion to inform readers and an appropriate gateway to furthering their understanding of migrant agency, network-derived social capital and high-risk migration.

Chapter Two

Existing Research

2.1 Introduction

2.2 Background on High-Risk Migration

2.3 Migrant Agency

2.4 Foundations of Social Capital Theories

2.5 Migration and Network-Derived Social Capital

2.5.1 Network-Derived Social Capital and Decisions to Migrate

2.5.2 Network-Derived Social Capital and Migrant Integration

2.6 High-Risk Migration and Network-Derived Social Capital

2.7 Conclusion

2.1 Introduction

Migration scholars have extensively documented the importance of migrant agency and social capital theories, including network-derived social capital (Van Liempt and Doomernik 2006; Massey and Espinosa 1997; Cummings et al. 2015; Mainwaring 2016; Triandafyllidou 2017; 2018a; Díaz de León 2018; see also forthcoming). These investigations have provided extensive insight on how network-derived social capital can influence migrant decisions on when and where to migrate, on how migrants strive to integrate into host communities, and a range of other issues. There has far less attention given, however, to the roles played by network social capital on high-risk routes, and especially to how migrants seek to develop networks in transit to generate social capital as part of their survival strategies on such routes.

This chapter works to weave together three significant facets of migration scholarship and processes: high-risk migration, migrant agency and social capital. It offers a critical overview of the salient literature, with two primary aims. The first is to detail the evolution, significance and increasing nuance of research on migrant agency and social capital relevant to migration. The second is to highlight the relative underdevelopment of the literature in relation to how migrants seek to develop networks to derive social capital valuable to their survival strategies on high-risk migration routes.

The chapter is structured as follows. First, I provide further details on high-risk migration routes. I then discuss recent literature on the types of agency migrants exercise and examine how the exercise of that agency can be relevant to group formation, with specific emphasis on networks throughout the Sahara Desert crossing and subsequent integration attempts in Italy. The next section discusses the evolution of

social capital theories, and their subsequent applications to migration contexts. I begin with the origins of these social capital theories, emphasising how Bordieu, Coleman and Loury establish the foundations of this theory in social science. Next, I consider the contributions made to developing a network-derived approach to social capital, meaning constructing solid and weak networks are consequential in pursuing an individual's objectives. I then look at bonding, bridging and linking social capital, precursor elements of network-derived social capital (Putnam 2000; Granovetter 1983; Lin 2000). In the following sections, I look at how network-derived social capital has figured in migration studies. I first discuss decisions to migrate. I focus on the works of those who highlight the complexities of decision-making by migrants and ways in which their decisions are driven by more than rational individual decisions made in the face of economic pushes or pulls, and also involve important social network variables (Espinosa and Massey 1997; Haug 2008; Massey and Aysa-Lastra 2011). I then examine the much less developed literature on the generation of network social capital by migrants in transit. I highlight the work of Schapendonk as providing some important signals in this area, and I discuss how the thesis goes beyond his analysis in focusing on ways in which migrants exercise creative and often sophisticated agency in the development of networks to derive social capital for protection on high-risk routes. The next chapter extends the analysis by highlighting how such dynamics are both spurred by and may provide important counter-narratives to the increasing securitisation of migration in contexts such as the EU and the extension of migration enforcement to Africa.

2.2 Background on High-Risk Migration

I will begin with some context on high-risk migration routes. As noted in the introduction, more than 50,000 migrants are estimated to have died on international high-risk routes since 2014, including more than 37,000 on African and Mediterranean routes (Missing Migrants Project 2022a). High-risk migration routes include the ones along the Atlantic, West African and Western Mediterranean Routes to Spain and the Central Mediterranean route to Italy. They also include routes through Central America and Mexico to the United States.

In context of the Sahara routes, specifically, since 2014 IOM's Missing Migrants Project (MMP) has recorded 5,226 deaths. As Black (2020) notes, that is almost certainly a conservative estimate, in part because Sahara fatalities are more challenging to track. The remote and desert conditions, with temperatures scorching during the day and freezing at night, make the terrain and journey particularly intense (International Organization for Migration 2014; Newman 2022). When deaths occur, whether by abandonment by smugglers, the elements, lack of water, medical care and the like, witnesses are few, and with many lacking identification documents means the missing disappear without a trace (Singleton et al. 2017; McMahon and Sigona 2021).

Those who survive the desert journey then must typically face a high-risk water crossing to Europe. IOM's Global Migration Data Analysis Centre (GMDAC) reports that between 1 January and 11 November 2022, 135,889 migrants arrived at sea in the EU (International Organization for Migration 2022a). More than 2,800 died at sea during the same period in the region (Missing Migrants Project 2022a). The data covers arrivals to Cyprus and Greece via the Eastern Mediterranean Route, Italy and Malta via the Central Mediterranean Route and Spain via the Western Mediterranean Route. Since

2014, IOM has recorded an estimated 1,117,793 migrant arrivals by sea, and Missing Migrants Project (2022a) has recorded 25,720 deaths in the Mediterranean and 2,406 on the West Africa and Atlantic Routes to the Canary Islands. Other sources report higher numbers of fatalities on the Canaries route (Godenau and Buraschi 2018; Black 2021; Zapata Hernández 2021).

Numerous Mediterranean incidents have involved a considerable loss of life. For example, on 18 April 2015, tragically, a fishing boat departing from Tripoli overloaded with hundreds of migrants aboard suffered a catastrophic crash into the hull of an aiding cargo vessel. The incident resulted in the sinking of both ships and the loss of life. A UN investigation concluded that more than 800 people drowned, with 27 survivors. A collective effort of cooperation could identify only 40 of the deceased through various forensic methods (Miglierini 2016; Cattaneo et al. 2020).

The mass fatalities have occurred against a backdrop of increasingly strong border enforcement by the coordinated European Border and Coast Guard Agency (FRONTEX). Operations such as Indigo and Minerva espouse their efforts to support anti-smuggling efforts alongside Spanish national police forces, including during summer when rescue missions can take place at sea alongside military vessels carrying out coastal patrol duties (European Border and Coast Guard Agency 2021). They also have occurred amid multiple flows of migration. The Migrations Between Africa and Europe Project, which started in 2005, highlights that migration in the region is more than South-North and involves migration flows in both directions from Africa to Europe. South-South, return, and transnational migration are substantial. (Migrations Between Africa and Europe Project 2005; see also Schapendonk 2013; International Organization for Migration 2020c).

Increasingly stringent enforcement has also been a significant factor in increasing risks on migration routes in the Americas. As Friebel et al. (2018, p.8) observe: ‘With rising border controls and immigration enforcement activities, economic returns to the smuggling business has been growing over the last decades and South-North migration routes have increased in length, difficulty and riskiness in different parts of the world.’

Higher risks on migration routes into and in the United States can be traced to the Clinton administrations’ launch of Operation Gatekeeper in 1994. The operation sought to deter irregular migration by hardening traditional crossing sites near urban areas and using harsh desert terrain as effectively a barrier against crossing (Operation Gatekeeper 1994; Cabrera 2010; Collyer 2007; see also Andersson 2016).

Missing Migrants Project records 3,651 migrant deaths from 2014 to 8 February 2021 between Central America and the U.S.-Mexico Border. A record 853 border deaths were recorded by US authorities in the fiscal year ending October 2022. Representatives interviewed at GMDAC and Missing Migrants Project (2022a) headquarters in Berlin, Germany, believe the number of fatalities actually is much higher in recent years.

The above gives a further sense of the high-risk routes that are the focus of this thesis, and the general intensity of risks to migrants. Chapter Four goes into significantly greater detail about the specific risks. The aim here has been to provide context for the examination of the existing literature on migrant agency and efforts by migrants to develop networks and derive social capital from them to facilitate their journeys, toward highlighting the underdevelopment of literature on in-transit network social capital on such high-risk routes.

2.3 Migrant Agency

Researchers have increasingly investigated aspects of migrant agency, seeking to move beyond media and political rhetoric of migrants as either passive victims or as complicit actors ‘villains’ engaged in unlawful activities (Mainwaring 2016). This rhetoric has highlighted how migrants participate in various forms of negotiation with or navigation through border control regimes (Triandafyllidou 2017). They have also investigated how migrants strive for security in complex contexts (Innes 2016)—engaging in resistance that both challenges and contributes to reframing aspects of sovereignty, membership, and civil disobedience (Cabrera 2010; Benli 2018; Mégret 2018; Cabrera 2021). These treatments in the literature expose where there is room for a unique conceptual framing to highlight a migrant’s entirety of experience while transiting on these high-risk routes.

As noted, researchers are increasingly active in looking at ways in which migrants exercise agency. For example, Mainwaring (2016, p. 292) points out that ‘even on the edges of states and societies, faced with challenging levels of marginalisation, people continue to resist, find room for negotiation.’ Negotiation with whom? Authorities, other travellers, and human smugglers. Migrants find ways to support their onward mobility. Ignoring migrant agency makes state security of borders and its effectiveness in controlling migration more abstract as the primary security constructs. And Triandafyllidou (2017) views agency as migrants overcoming hurdles to their mobility as set by deterrence policies. These are considered impediments to navigate through. Differently, Benli (2018) looks at migrant agency as an act of civil disobedience and challenging subjugation to dire circumstances. The primary discourse on migration comes from states’ points of view (Jonsson 2020), focusing more on the

administrative state's securitised and extraterritorial migration enforcement strategies. Scholars such as Nail (2015) argue that there is value in shifting our context and viewing high-risk migration through the eyes of the migrant.

Researchers in the migrant agency sphere have spent time considering the potential significance of agency exercised by migrants. And there is room in the scholarship to look at migrant agency more explicitly from the group and network formation angle, most certainly in the context of the Sahara Desert crossing. Achilli and Abu Samra (2021) look at how migrants originally from Palestine¹ utilise their national ties and use of informal networks during clandestine migration through militarised checkpoints from Syria while at the same time challenging the binaries of legal or illegal.

In comparison, Díaz de León (forthcoming) evolves the migrant experience from Central America and their use of social capital relationships while crossing through Mexico. Díaz de León investigates how groups that begin the journey change while in transit. Also explored are the negative aspects of networks through experiences of abuse (see also Díaz de León 2018). Part of my thesis is that migrants adopt a survivor strategy while in transit during high-risk migration, an experience grounded in resilience. I will show migrants' use of agency through their development of social capital, with particular emphasis on network social capital.

While migrants may not control their circumstances, they may exercise more motivated agency in responding to them, proving especially true in high-risk situations such as crossing the Sahara Desert. One of the contributions of this thesis is to extend the literature on migrant agency in two distinct ways. The first is by highlighting how

¹ Palestine was recognised by the United Nations (2012) as a 'non-Member Observer State' by a vote of 138 in favour to 9 against, with 41 abstentions.

migrants on high-risk routes exercise significant and meaningful agency in seeking to form networks and derive forms of social capital from them that are valuable to a survival strategy. The second offers an elevated framing of migrants who use high-risk migration routes and, during integration, as resilient survivors. The *resilient survivor* concept contradicts depictions of migrants as victims by elites across some academic, humanitarian, media and political discourse or villains by others in these fields.

Looking at the treatment of resilience in the literature, Bourbeau (2013) highlights how the vibrant discussion of resilience, this idea of rising above circumstances, is taking place at the forefront of other disciplines, such as psychology and areas in political science like political geography. In contrast, resilience has comparably reduced visibility in international relations. Bourbeau looks at resilience, particularly in securitisation, through the lens of either maintenance, marginality, or renewal. All are ways that states respond to migration flows to keep in place, marginally adjust or intensify securitisation processes. In (2015a), he offers an interesting triangulation between migration, resilience and securitisation. Bourbeau surmises how media and others typically frame international migration as a problem. States then employ resilience as a mechanism and tool to strengthen migration securitisation efforts (see also 2015b; 2015c)—Joseph (2013) simultaneously frames resilience as a neoliberal government principle that fosters individual agency and a valuable tool the state uses to further their security objectives.

Where this thesis takes resilience, a good beginning reflection point is Maslow's *A Theory for Human Motivation* (1943). In it, Maslow notes that the person's circumstance and surroundings are important indicators, though not a sole representation of the reasons for responding to that environment. A need for safety in

situations of risk or crises is the motivator of an individual to access or, in the cases of this research, create necessary means. Schwazer and Warner (2013) frame resilience as a person's adaptation to stress and upheaval. That resilience stems from adversity and traumatic situations (see also Rutter 1987; Bonanno et al. 2010). The literature also comprehensively documents the effects of trauma on a person's mental health during and post-migration with multiple diagnoses, including post-traumatic stress disorder and depression amongst migrant populations (Mghir et al. 1995; Khamis 2005; Ellis et al. 2008; Li 2016).

Bringing resilience then into the focus of a migrant's high-risk migration experience and directly pertinent to this research is a study by Cigrand et al. (2022). In it, interviews with migrants reveal the role of resilience during the migration experience. Migrants discuss their journeys as requiring a specific mindset to access resilience as an adaptation mechanism (see also Jamieson 2018; Carroll et al. 2020; Lusk et al. 2021; Schapendonk et al. 2021). Another salient study by Verbena et al. (2022) focuses on the connection between resilience and the integration experience. In this one, the authors look at the importance of resilience to migrant youth integrating in Italy. How a person views themselves as a resilient individual plays in helping them grow in the face of challenges and overcome obstacles (see also Brodsky et al. 2011; Brodsky and Cattaneo 2013; Brodsky et al. 2022). The study also highlights how more than resilience is needed to guarantee a successful integration experience. Structural support from communities is integral to an encompassing and welcoming integration.

2.4 Foundations of Social Capital Theories

In this section, I introduce the foundations of relevant social capital theories. I start with treatments by Bordieu, Loury and Coleman. I then look at network-derived social capital by scholars Putman, Granovetter and Lin. Finally, I intend to show through this development of social capital how migration studies begin to intersect.

Social capital theory promotes the idea that it is the relationship between people which yields potentially the most valuable results for an individual. The strength or weakness of such relationships is a resource an individual must draw on to best support one's aims and objectives. They represent a departure from other social sciences approaches focusing on the individual as a solitary decision-maker. It is a turning away from the more homo economicus² view of rational decision-making that is influential in social sciences.

Social capital theory traces to the work of Bordieu. According to Bourdieu's theory of capital, there are three types, economic, cultural and social (Bourdieu 1986). Bordieu's influential conceptualisation presents social capital as 'the aggregate of the actual or potential resources which are linked to possession of a durable network of more or less institutionalised relationships of mutual acquaintance and recognition – or in other words, to membership in a group – which provides each of its members with the backing of the collectively-owned capital, a "credential" which entitles them to credit, in the various senses of the word' (Bourdieu 1986, p. 248). An obvious example is a connection to an institution, where membership enhances one's position in life and therefore has value—an employee of a United Nations organisation or part of a university. The argument is that being a member of these examples supports upward

² Economic man, or the rational agent depicted in economic models (Grampp 1948).

mobility. Both are forms of social capital symbolic of obligation, responsibility and service. A relationship grounded in reciprocity between the institution and the individual (Bourdieu 1990; see also Häuberer 2011).

Another source in the origin story of social capital theory is Loury (1987). He defines social capital as an opportunity to use one's social connections to maximise one's influence on the playing field and access equal opportunity benefits in a society based on skill. Loury thinks that minority family units, being less well-off due to racial discrimination, may be better suited to utilise social capital to acquire wealth and better standing. In this context, Loury's use of social capital intends to differentiate it from human capital. An example of human capital is how a company invests and utilises its employees. Instead, Loury seeks to motivate the individual to pursue excellence using all skills and assets available (Loury 1976; 1981).

Others further strengthen the foundations of social capital theories. For example, Coleman (1988) looks at social capital's relationship interdependence and defines its function. People with common interests may be in positions of authority concerning one or more other people. Relationships form, and exchanges ensue whereby an individual gains access to the very thing under the control of another that will support mobility. Coleman states...

It is a variety of different entities having two characteristics in common: They all consist of some aspect of a social structure, and they facilitate certain actions of individuals who are within the structure (Coleman 1990, p. 302).

An example of this social capital relationship growth is a notion that is valid for all. In general, people want to help. People tend to help those they know; think they know or feel closest to. As one's relationship develops and grows, it becomes more

productive. This productivity creates possibilities to achieve certain ends that are more difficult to attain in its absence. Social capital is about relationships. Relationships create opportunities to develop assets that are more difficult to reach in their absence. Thus, social capital is the relationships' strengths and weaknesses (Coleman 1988; Häuberer 2011; see also Woolcock & Narayan 2000; Bhandari and Yasunobu 2009). More specifically, network-derived social capital comprises the connections an individual develops that provide value in pursuing one's objectives. In the migration context, various forms of social capital are necessary for integration into host societies (Adedeji 2021) and migration decisions. Therefore, fieldwork for the present investigation focused on how migrants pursue network-derived social capital as a specific form of agency and part of a resilient survivor strategy on high-risk migration routes.

A network-derived approach to social capital is critical in furthering an understanding of social capital theory. Putman (2000) follows Coleman and begins to discuss network-derived social capital. The networks an individual develops are framed as having value in pursuing one's objectives. In contrast to values produced by cultural, economic and human capital, relationships best help an individual create results. 'The relations between individuals form social networks, norms of reciprocity and trustworthiness' (Putman 2000, p. 19). Relationships are influential and potentially more effective in supporting the individual's aspirations than operating alone (Putman 1995).

Some scholars focus on how weak social connections that make up one's networks are as consequential for individuals. For example, Granovetter (1973) highlights that while a family member may be a healthy, strong relationship and a

valuable resource, there are relationships considered weak social ties that may be strong regarding social capital. For example, when a person arrives in a new country and has little connection to anyone, a stranger or acquaintance, or a weak social link, it could be critical and the most effective at providing support, for example, in providing information about the locations of migrant resource centres. The value derived from a well-established relationship and the lack of value derived from a less-established relationship seem instinctive. On the other hand, the value derived from a less-developed relationship is less intuitive and exciting to consider. Granovetter's view is that the strength derived from weak ties may be just as important at a critical moment in supporting an individual's objectives (Granovetter 1973; 1983; see also Portes 1998; Portes and Landolt 2000).

Four significant characteristics of network-derived social capital have been highlighted as supporting actors' objectives. First, according to Lin (1999), network connections (1) facilitate the flow of information (2) exert influence on agents because some networks are location specific and, therefore, more valuable (3) an individual's knowledge and access to these resources enhance one's credentials (4) connections reinforce identity and recognition. (Lin 1999; 2000).

Three specific types of network-derived social capital have been highlighted in the literature: bonding, bridging and linking (see figure 2.1). Bonding social capital, best thought of as horizontal ties, refers to the connections and relationships between people within a community or group with similar attitudes, beliefs and demographic characteristics. This element of social capital derives from networks ties between individuals rather than from formal institutions or organisations. Bonding social capital has been identified as key to providing access to important information and assets that

align with a person's aspirations and goals. Bonding social capital is framed as less constrained by formal rules or hierarchy. Instead, it is more fluid and informal, based on individual personal relationships (Putnam 2000; Claridge 2018). An example of bonding social capital would be where migrants with few connections and limited resources who are integrating into a new community and are looking for support for their children's education will rely on support from members of their new community (Portes 2000). From a different perspective, a study by Adler and Kwon (2002) found that some network contacts have bonding social capital characteristics and will share their resources and their hold on different assets, and that hold may be uneven. The unevenness of this hold may cause one group to have an advantage over another (see also Granovetter 2005; Pelling and High 2005).

Bridging social capital, best thought of as horizontal ties, describes the development of relationships between people who share similar interests and come from diverse backgrounds. Bridging social capital is often created through associations, which function as a 'bridge' between groups. This characteristic of social capital promotes cooperation and understanding between different social groups. Bridging social capital is associated with several positive outcomes, including improved collaboration and communication among other groups, increased trust and reciprocity, and enhanced problem-solving skills. Bridging social capital is vital to promoting social cohesion and helping overcome social divisions. Pelling and High (2005) view bridging social ties as a way for people with different interests or goals to come together and work towards common aims. These associations are an exchange where each party offers something they have, resources that the other wants and does not already possess,

to establish relationships based on these exchanges (see also Granovetter 1985; Villalonga-Olives et al. 2016).

Linking social capital, associated more typically with vertical relationships, is an element of social capital that describes networks of individuals and groups with disparate social statuses and power dynamics. Linking social capital is formed when people reach out to others in different situations, such as those outside the community who foster networks and ties with humanitarian organisations, for example, states, other agencies, or human smugglers, as in my research. Linking social capital is framed as significant because it has the potential to facilitate the transfer of resources between distinct groups (Claridge 2018; see also Woolcock 2001; Claridge 2004).

Cofré-Bravo et al. (2019) provide a crisp analysis in one of their contributions. They use Chilean fruit farmers as their case study and show how they develop distinct types of networks in which they utilise all three types of social capital: bonding, bridging and linking in different combinations. Reading their piece echoes similarities to how these three types of social capital interplay with the six ways migrants in my research develop their networks. The presentation in Chapter Four shows that all three types of social capital, bonding, bridging and linking, are present and in different combinations during these high-risk migration and integration contexts.

The following discussion focuses primarily on forms of bonding social capital present in migration contexts, though arguably asymmetrical relations between migrants and human smuggling rings could be framed as linking social capital.

Figure 2.1 Elements in and Types of Social Capital

Social Capital is About Relationships
 Elements Include Civic Engagement, Generalised Trust, Networks, and Norms of Reciprocity

Sources: Granovetter 1985; Woolcock 2001; Claridge 2004; 2018; Pelling and High 2005; Bhandari and Yasunobu 2009.

2.5 Migration and Network-Derived Social Capital

Migration involves more than a one-dimensional view involving decisions based only on economic factors. Kalter and Will (2016) look at the social processes involved in migration and networks' vital role in these dynamics. They discuss the strength and weaknesses of networks:

We find that weak ties are especially relevant in the first step-considering migration at all-while strong ties are more important in the second step-transforming such considerations into actual migration (Kalter & Will 2016, p. 61).

2.5.1 Network-Derived Social Capital and Decisions to Migrate

Since at least the 1960s, researchers have explored ways in which network-derived social capital can influence migrant decision-making, in particular on choice of destination and 'chain migration' involving members of specific networks choosing to follow one another to a destination city. As Aguilier and Massey observed some 20 years ago: 'It is now well established in migration literature that networks are a source of social capital and that migrants draw upon them to migrate' (Aguilier and Massey 2003, p. 672; see also Massey and Espinosa 1997, de Haas 2010; Flores-Yeffal and Aysa-Lastra 2011; Cummings et al. 2015).

Such network social capital can lower costs and mitigate many risks associated with migration. It supports employment opportunities in transit countries and integration into destination countries. For example, a critical factor in determining where someone will move after they leave their home country is how much money family members have available to support them and whether job opportunities await at the destination, all strongly influenced by community input:

Examples of community-level variables likely to influence the migration decision include local employment opportunities, wage levels, land tenure arrangements, inheritance systems, transportation and communication linkages, access to community facilities, economic and political power structures, climatic factors, governmental policies, and kinship networks (Massey & Capoferro 2004, p. 1087).

Network-derived social capital develops over time. McKenzie and Rapoport (2007, p.6) discuss some of the effects of these networks as lowering the costs of future migration, which balances the unevenness of remote dispatching communities in Mexico. These networks also benefit the household through remittances, ‘These households will become richer due to remittances. When migration costs are high to begin with, the first network effects then will increase migration opportunities more for the middle and upper-middle classes.’

Some of the most influential studies of social capital and decisions to migrate have been published by Massey and colleagues, via the Mexican Migration Project (MexMP). That project has involved annual random surveys of tens of thousands of households across Mexico, and surveys of households in the United States. Findings since the 1980s have emphasised the role that network-derived social capital plays in migrants’ decisions to leave, their choice of destinations in the United States, and the influence these connections have in integration such as seeking employment (Mexican Migration Project 1982; Massey 1986; 1987; Massey et al. 1990; 1993; 1994; Massey and Espinosa 1997; Massey and Philips 1999; Massey and Riosema 2010; Massey and Aysa-Lastra 2011). As Massey observes, ‘Migration between Mexico and the United States is supported by social networks that link sending communities with specific work sites in the United States’ (Massey 1986, p. 103). Further, network-derived social

capital was found to be strongly linked to a rapid increase in the migration of nationals from Mexico to the United States during the 1970s (Massey and García-España 1987).

Massey and Espinosa (1997) look at network-derived social capital and ties to parents, siblings or someone known in the local community who has migrated to the United States, increasing the likelihood that another will follow. They use data from households in the United States where members legalised under the Immigration Reform and Control Act of 1986. ‘This massive program created a new and potentially important source of social capital for people in Mexico because those receiving amnesty were better able to sponsor the migration of friends and relatives at home’ Massey and Espinosa (1997, p. 952). Along those lines, Palloni et al. find that ‘Having an older sibling who has been to the United States triples the likelihood of migrating to the United States’ (2001, p. 1295). Finally, in one published study, Massey and Phillips (1999) found out that 81% per cent of respondents in Mexico knew someone who had already moved to or worked in the United States previously, leading them to be more likely candidates for migration themselves.

Asad and Garip (2019) use large-scale data from MexMP and show that economic, political and social factors all play a role in migration decisions. They find, however, that social factors are the most influential. In other contexts, such as Germany, researchers have similarly highlighted the importance of networks in determining destination decisions and overall planning. Bilecen et al. note that, ‘migratory processes do not occur in a vacuum; rather they are embedded in social networks’ (Bilecen et al. 2018, p. 1; see also Massey et al. 1993).

Numerous researchers have focused on ways in which network-derived social capital can reduce the cost and risk of migration. Clark and Lisowski (2019) confirm

that social capital and one's access to networks play a role in decisions to move or stay (see also Kan 2007; Massey and Riosmena 2010). Akanle and Orobome (2019) points to the role that family ties help individuals achieve opportunities for migration. While Garip (2008) believes that network-derived social capital is about understanding where one's information sources are, individuals access these sources through their relationships as part of their migration experience. Liu (2013, p. 1243) states that:

Migrants' networks contribute to continued migration flows and the changing characteristics of these flows. Migrant networks lower migration costs and increase the number of people migrating, resulting in broader migrant networks, and further reduced migration costs.

It should be noted that, while accessing available network resources has the potential to reduce the expense, uncertainty, and sometimes volatile nature of migration for individuals, such support is often unreliable. For example, research indicates that network-derived social capital among migrants from Iran now living in Turkey lowers the initial migration costs. At the same time, such networks cannot necessarily be relied upon for support over time (Akcapar 2009; see also Clark and Lisowski 2017, Kan 2007). Silver et al. (2018) highlight the effects of family separation in the context of network social capital. An individual may attach feelings of stress to the thought of providing for family back home (see also Chávez et al. 2016; Chávez and Altman, 2017). Thus, network ties may have less than positive implications for individual migrants.

Work conducted under the auspices of the Latin America Migration Project (LAMP) (1998) has highlighted how even decisions to migrate that may be spurred by violence can be strongly influenced by network ties. Project researchers have studied how violence and civil unrest in countries such as Colombia affect emigration. The

project started with a set of surveys conducted in Puerto Rico and expanded to include fieldwork throughout most major regions within that continent, including Colombia, Costa Rica, Dominican Republic, Ecuador, El Haiti, Nicaragua, Paraguay and Peru, which began implementation in Spring 2012. There are many factors why someone would want to leave their home country, including police deployed around them at night, at the same time, ‘The importance of social capital was amply confirmed by our analysis, which not only revealed that international migration was strongly and significantly predicted by ties to a current or former international migrant and showed that network ties to a specific region powerfully predict migration to that location’ (Silva and Massey 2014, p. 176).

Finally, human smugglers represent a form of network-derived social capital. As noted above, they possibly could be viewed in a linking social frame, given that they often stand in hierarchical relationships with migrants. Jandl (2007) notes two relevant points: first, high-risk routes are primarily sites of transit migration rather than migration to destinations along the path—and most migrants travelling these routes use smugglers. Smugglers have knowledge of the routes and how to evade authorities. Most respondents in another study refer to their use of smugglers to facilitate migration. There is a general lack of trust in these groups, and many migrants fear being robbed or killed (Garip 2016). Chapter Four examines the role of smugglers and gives more detail on migrants’ engagement of them and how they can be viewed within a network-derived social capital framework on high-risk routes.

2.5.2 Network-Derived Social Capital and Migrant Integration

Researchers also have extensively studied the roles played by network-derived social capital in migrants' efforts to integrate into host societies. Haug (2008), for example, highlights findings that, 'Social networks provide a foundation for the dissemination of information as well as for patronage or assistance' (p. 588). Kindler et al. (2015) assessed the quality and variety of social ties and networks in determining social capital usefulness in such contexts. Looking at the literature on migrant integration across the various Member States, they conclude that networks are significant in the first settlement in a destination country. As each migrant strengthens their networks in a destination country, newer arriving migrants benefit from these established communities.

Migrants often seek out those of the same nationality in host countries. For example, newly arrived Mexican migrants in the United States benefit from connecting with other migrants from Mexico for support:

In moving to strange, and often hostile land, migrants naturally draw upon these familiar bonds [kinship, friendship and *paisanje*]³ which are reinforced through regular interactions (Massey et al. 1990, p. 140; see also Granberry 2014).

Madhavan and Landau (2011) look at migrants' connections in three cities: Johannesburg in South Africa, Maputo in Mozambique and Nairobi in Kenya. They aim to understand better the role of network-derived social capital plays in migrant integration in urban Africa. Studies in developing nations suggest substantial network-derived social capital has critical psychological implications:

³ A thought of belonging to a shared community of origin.

Social contacts at destinations not only reduce the psychological costs of migration by providing a supportive relationship during the migrant's adjustment period, also reduce monetary costs by providing information on employment opportunities as well as material assistance during the job search (Banerjee 1983, p. 185).

Nannestad et al. (2008) and others look at network-derived social capital related to integrating non-Western migrants in the European Union. Data from Denmark's Social Capital Project (SoCap) involves the largest five national migrant groups, including refugees residing in Denmark from Pakistan, Palestine, Somalia and Turkey. Their findings highlight that migrants seek out individuals from the same nationality for some types of support and seek out others outside nationality groups for other types of support. Kalter and Will (2016) draw on data from the Polish Migration Project (PMP) and the likelihood of Polish migration to Germany. They also analyse data from the MexMP which they think, 'clearly demonstrates that the social processes are a crucial element of many facets of past and contemporary Mexican-U.S. migration' (Kalter and Will 2016, p.47).

As the above discussion demonstrates, network-derived social capital in migration literature is well-established and covers a broad umbrella of categories. Scholars look at the impact networks have on decisions made before migration, including destination decisions and the role family, friends and acquaintances play. Strong and weak connections each influence potentially reducing costs and risks of migration to support integration and employment opportunities in host countries. At the same time, this covers only part of the migration story. The next section examines existing accounts that touch on or explore aspects of social capital network formation on high-risk routes, and it highlights the considerable space remaining in the literature for furthering understandings of the processes involved and their potential significance.

2.6 High-Risk Migration and Network-Derived Social Capital

Some researchers have examined social capital formation by migrants in ‘transit’ countries. These are typically understood as countries which are not migrants’ ultimate destinations. Instead, they pass through these countries to reach their destinations or ones where they may spend some time before attempting their journey’s final leg.

Wissink and Mazzucato (2018), for example, examine migration through transit countries such as Greece and Turkey. Suter (2012) looks at how Nigerian migrants in Istanbul work to establish networks and derive social capital from them in transit countries. Suter points out that studies on network-derived social capital show that migrants draw on support assets provided by close relationships, mostly friends, family and neighbours.

Others have given some attention to social capital networks on the high-risk routes that are the focus of this thesis. Collyer (2005), for example, notes that migrants in high-risk migration contexts form networks differently, developing weaker bonds than those with more substantial familial networks (see also Akcapar 2009). Relatedly, Sue et al. (2019) shows how financially vulnerable migrants who have weaker existing networks had to rely on bonds formed in transit. ‘Lacking migration experience and perceived viable ties in the U.S.,’ Sue et al. (2019, p. 2474) note, ‘these migrants leaned on in-transit connections to find employment, regardless of destination.’ Their focus, however, is on the factors that influence migrants’ choice of ultimate destination, rather than the roles network-derived social capital play in survival strategies on high-risk routes.

Press (2017) interviewed 60 African migrants, primarily at a migrant resource centre in Perugia, Italy. His analysis is wide ranging, seeking to fill gaps in knowledge on the Sahara migrations and migrants' experiences of it. He touches on the role of social networks in transit, noting that even some migrants who have relatively strong network ties may be forced to try to develop in-transit ones. 'While some migrants from Africa had a relative in Europe or a friend in Libya, they were obliged to form new networks on the journey, adjusting to circumstances' (Press 2017, p. 10). He does not go into specific detail on the roles played by such networks, the specific factors driving migrants to develop them, or how they seek to do so. Singer and Massey (1998, p. 561) diverge from the Sahara-oriented research on networks in transit, noting how migrants on the increasingly high-risk US Mexico routes progressively relied less on smugglers to help guide them. 'As people gain experience in border crossing, they rely less on the assistance of others and more on abilities honed on earlier trips.' As will be discussed in Chapter Four, on Sahara routes, migrants continue to rely on smugglers over time.

Liu et al. (2018) also touch on some aspects of network formation or use in transit. They focus on sibling ties on high-risk routes from Mexico to the United States, and also from Senegal, West Africa, to Europe. Migrants with older siblings were more likely to have survived the journey and had more social capital than older siblings. Family migrant networks are relevant, and here because of the association between sibling position and migration, it could be an artefact of the network structure (Liu et al. 2018). Migrants who saw their older brothers as role models were more likely to have higher levels of social capital than those who did not. Their study provides insights into the gendered nature of social capital in high-risk migration and the potential importance of very strong ties to survival (see also Liu 2013; Kindler et al. 2015; McMahon and

Sigona 2018; Poeze 2013). In that context, I also note the study by O’Leary (2012, p. 133). It examines the border crossing experience of women to show that migrants leaving south and central Mexico have less opportunity and time to foster relationships and accumulate ‘migration-related social capital.’

Such studies give some important, if relatively limited, insights into the roles played by various forms of network-derived social capital on high-risk migration routes. The work of Schapendonk (2011; see also Schapendonk 2012; 2013; Schapendonk and Steel 2014) has provided more extensive insights and deserves a closer look.

Schapendonk has conducted numerous qualitative field studies involving African migrants bound for Europe. Schapendonk conducted a qualitative research study from 2007-2011 on the journeys of 108 migrants from sub-Saharan Africa to the EU. Schapendonk had two aims, firstly, to look at what factors affect migrants’ mobility and what their motivations were for moving from sub-Saharan Africa to the EU. Secondly, he was looking for migrant aspirations and how their networking practices ultimately influenced their trajectory from sub-Saharan Africa en route to Europe. His field research included interviews in Morocco, Senegal and Spain with migrants heading to or moving through the EU. He went to the transit countries of Morocco and Turkey, interviewing 57 migrants on their experiences. He connected with 13 migrants remotely using the telephone and internet to stay engaged with their journey. He then met a few respondents and engaged with 36 more migrants once they arrived at their destination, the Netherlands.

Work from this extended field research has focused, for example, on providing details on individual migrants’ journeys and experiences with EU Member States’ asylum systems (2012). Schapendonk and Steel (2014) have also examined migrant

networks, including ones on high-risk Sahara routes, with an initial emphasis on ways in which such networks are highly changeable and malleable rather than static.

Specifically, and again by presenting the migration experiences of specific persons, he focuses on how new relationships form, and old relationships are let go—the changing character of relationships, the changing power dynamics. He also focuses on the effort required to create and maintain relationships and accumulate social capital from them, though he also offers a general conception of social capital in the context.

Overall, Schapendonk’s work helps us better understand migration trends and how migration routes evolve in specific directions (Schapendonk 2010; see also Schapendonk 2011; 2012; 2013; 2015; 2018; 2020; Schapendonk and Steel 2014; Schapendonk et al. 2015). This thesis is informed by Schapendonk’s work. It also seeks to provide a more systematic analysis of why and how migrants seek to develop networks while in transit on high-risk routes, how they use existing networks, and how both can extend into their efforts to integrate into destination cities in Europe. More narrowly, this thesis highlights six specific factors driving migrants on the high-risk Sahara routes to seek to form networks or use existing ones. It similarly details six ways in which migrants seek to derive social capital as part of their survival strategies on such routes, either from networks formed in transit or existing networks. It highlights an important distinction from other high-risk routes, e.g., in the Americas, in that Sahara migrants typically do not have contacts in their intended destination cities before setting out. The thesis also provides new information about the roles social networking applications for mobile phones are increasingly playing on high-risk routes and in the context of network formation and use, and on the maintenance of networks formed in-transit during integration efforts in Europe. The thesis thus offers some significant

advances on the existing literature.

2.7 Conclusion

This chapter has reviewed key aspects of migration scholarship and processes: high-risk migration, migrant agency and social capital with two objectives. The first was to share the contribution and growth of the research on migrant agency and social capital. The second was to highlight the less developed scholarship on how migrants seek to develop networks and derive social capital from those networks on high-risk migration routes.

In section 2.2, the chapter provided background on high-risk migration routes, including data on arrivals, fatalities and conditions. Then, in section 2.3, I discussed migrant agency and how many scholars challenge legal or illegal binary framings. Finally, I highlighted the need for further growth in the migrant agency sphere by looking more closely at group and network formation dynamics. In section 2.4, I reviewed the existing research which covered the foundations of social capital theories, including Bordieu, Loury and Coleman's treatments. It then spent time on how scholars in migration studies are developing network-derived social capital to show that migration is a social process driven by economic indicators. Next was a discussion of Putman, Granovetter and Lin. This section then covered the contributions of Espinosa, Haug, Massey and others who highlight the complexities of decision-making by migrants. Moreover, ways in which their decisions are driven by more than economic indicators. Finally, I looked at three elements of network-derived social capital (1) bonding social capital, which is horizontal ties and refers to the relationships and connections between people within a group or community with similar demographic

characteristics and attitudes, (2) bridging social capital, which has horizontal ties and a type of social capital that describes the development of relationships between people who share similar interests and come from different backgrounds and (3) linking social capital which is also vertical ties and is a type of social capital that describes networks and ties among individuals and groups who occupy very different social positions and power.

In section 2.5, I discussed how network-derived social capital is a way of looking at the multiple factors involved in high-risk migration. Scholars in this field examine how individuals make decisions based on more than economic indicators. During migration, it is helpful to consider networks as having these three different elements discussed (1) the bonding between people who know each other well enough, share their migration experiences and care for one another, (2) the bridging of social ties formed through participation within familiar associations, in this instance, humanitarian organisations and other civil society outreach and (3) the linking of social capital creates through interactions with strangers such as smugglers who have assets critical for survival.

In section 2.6, I presented the treatments in the literature on migrants using network-derived social capital as a survival strategy in high-risk migration. Examining the literature on high-risk migration routes includes along the Atlantic, West Africa and the Western Mediterranean Routes to Spain, Central America and Mexico Routes to the United States and the Central Mediterranean Route to Italy. This review of existing research pays particular attention to the research of Schapendonk. He has done the most recent work in the area with much the same population as this thesis.

There remains considerable space in the literature in a few areas, including further development of the high-risk migration experiences of the Sahara routes in addition to the role of network-derived social capital on these routes and how migrants are exercising agency in unique ways as part of their survival strategy. In Chapter Three, I will examine European Union's securitised migration and its extraterritorial enforcement efforts in North and West Africa. Chapter Three is an essential next step as it advances one of my arguments that migrants on these high-risk migration journeys face an increasing landscape of security and enforcement.

Chapter Three

European Union Securitised Migration and Extraterritorial Enforcement in North and West Africa

3.1 Introduction

3.2 Conceptual Framework: Securitised Migration and Extraterritorial Enforcement

3.3 European Union Migration Control Mechanisms

3.3.1 Border Security

3.3.2 Technology-Based Initiatives

3.3.3 Voluntary Return and Reintegration—Regional Disembarkation Platforms

3.4 European Union Extraterritorial Enforcement Initiatives (Third Countries)

3.5 Enforcement: Central Mediterranean Route to Italy

3.5.1 Niger

3.5.2 Libya

3.5.3 Tunisia

3.6 Enforcement: Atlantic and West Africa Routes to Spain (Canary Islands)

3.6.1 Morocco

3.7 Enforcement: Western Mediterranean Route to Spain (Ceuta and Melilla)

3.7.1 Algeria

3.8 Conclusion

3.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the conceptual framework of the thesis, highlighting two closely related elements of migration governance at the supranational and state levels: securitised migration and extraterritorial enforcement. The securitisation of migration by the EU – framing and treating migration as a security threat rather than a set of economic and social processes – provides the conceptual context for understanding EU moves to both harden enforcement and extend it into Africa. Further, the chapter provides background for understanding how the extension, or extraterritorial enforcement of the EU migration regime has contributed to intensifying the risks on the Sahara and Mediterranean migration routes. This action has compelled migrants to attempt to derive network social capital as part of their survival strategy.

The primary aim here is thus to highlight the securitisation of migration and extraterritorial enforcement policies that flow from it, and the implications of both for the security of migrants themselves. The EU, and various countries cooperating with it in North and West Africa have increasingly identified clandestine migration as a security problem. Accordingly, they have responded to migration through the Sahara Desert and the Mediterranean Sea to Europe by tightening enforcement, and by similarly strengthening regional migration architecture and support. As states enact stricter enforcement policies, limit legal migration pathways, and tighten visa regimes, migrants seek more risky journeys. Routes have become more dangerous for migrants, while making them a more profitable environment for human smugglers. Relatedly, migrants engaging in formal migration systems often face challenges in accessing critical services of the citizenry and refugees (Mainwaring and Brigden 2016).

By its end, this chapter will have provided a clearer picture of the enforcement forces migrants face travelling these high-risk migration routes from North and West Africa to Europe. It will thus provide the context in which migrants seek to exercise various forms of creative agency, in particular by seeking to form networks on the routes and derive social capital from them for self-protection and ultimately as central parts of a resilient survivor strategy.

The chapter is structured as follows. First, definitional details are given on the two elements of the conceptual framework: securitised migration and ways in which it has informed movement toward extraterritorial enforcement. Then background is given on EU-region migration governance policies, strategies and technologies. The next sections examine EU moves toward extraterritorial enforcement, with emphasis on specific deterrent mechanisms implemented in countries on high-risk migration route systems relevant to this thesis. These include Niger, Libya and Tunisia along the Central Mediterranean Route to Italy—Morocco along the Atlantic and West Africa Routes to Spain and the autonomous community of the Canary Islands—Algeria on the Western Mediterranean Route to both the mainland of Spain and the Spanish enclaves of Ceuta and Melilla. Finally, the chapter highlights the linkages between the securitised migration, the extraterritorial enforcement of migration and intensification of risks to migrants, and the resulting efforts by migrants to exercise sophisticated forms of agency in seeking to derive network social capital. Also highlighted are the importance and role of the State in which the migrant is travelling -- in either hindering or supporting migrant mobility (Schapendonk 2010). The chapter closes with observations on tensions around statements of solidarity with migrants increasingly made in international resolutions, for example, the New York Declaration for Refugees and Migrants (United

Nations 2016), and attempted reforms of the Common European Asylum System through EU initiatives such as A New Pact on Migration and Asylum (European Commission 2020a), and the Renewed Action Plan Against Migrant Smuggling (European Commission 2021a). While such efforts are underway, increasing numbers of receiving and transit states are hardening borders and cooperating on extended enforcement.

3.2 Conceptual Framework: Securitised Migration and Extraterritorial

Enforcement

This section presents the two pillars of the conceptual framework of this thesis: securitised migration and ways it informs policies of extraterritorial enforcement (see figure 3.1). Increasingly scholars use securitisation theory to explain how policymakers and the public understand migration issues. The concept of securitisation is linked to the Copenhagen School of security studies, and with associated scholars including Wæver (1993) among others. They have highlighted ways in which certain issue areas such as migration are constructed as security threats to justify aggressive responses or enforcement measures. Numerous other scholars have highlighted ways in which, in Huysmans' (2000, p. 752) words, 'migration has been increasingly presented as a danger to public order, cultural identity and domestic and labour market stability; it has been securitised.'

Figure 3.1 Conceptual Framework and Theoretical Emphasis

Securitisation thus involves framing migration as a security issue, a threat to the nation. The terms 'flood' or 'invasion' of migrants often accompany and reinforce this framing, and it can be prominent in justifications for measures such as increased border controls and detention. Securitisation scholars highlight how such negative portrayals of migrants and related enforcement measures can threaten migrant rights (Buzan et al. 1998; see also Huysmans 2000; 2006; Bourbeau 2011).

In more general terms, the migration rhetoric of many political elites has increasingly been marked by two diverging characterisations of migrants, especially those travelling high-risk migration routes to Europe. First, associated primarily with the left or progressive side of the political spectrum, is that migrants are victims who lack agency, such as of abuse or trafficking. Second, associated with more conservative and those on the right-leaning elites, is that migrants are, at the very least, complicit actors engaged in supporting clandestine behaviour to reach the EU. At worst, they

represent multi-threats to the local citizenry and national security. Migrants are described as disease carriers, queue jumpers, straining public resources, and with a host of other labels (Tsoukala 2005; Mainwaring 2016; Plambech 2014). Private sector elites, including various firms lobbying governments, reinforce securitisation narratives, framing migrants as a threat requiring costly mitigation (Akkerman 2021).

Those adopting a security framing of migration often highlight concerns such as the risk of importing of radical extremism and terrorism as well as the potential for increased crime in cities and the spreading of disease (Huysmans 2000; Aslan 2022). In terms of the spreading of disease, I note the rhetoric around (1) the Ebola crisis of 2014, (2) outbreaks of Polio and measles in Syria starting in 2013, (3) other outbreaks among the Syrian refugee populations in camps across Iraq with cholera, (4) tuberculosis in Lebanon and Jordan and (4) cutaneous leishmaniasis in Turkey. The rhetoric emphasised that sooner or later, migrants will try to get to Europe carrying these pathogens and infect the populace (Poletto et al. 2014; Ozaras et al. 2016; Khan et al. 2016; Kassem 2020). During the COVID-19 pandemic, some of the most dramatic state actions were linked to such fears, as numerous states restricted people's movements (Displacement Tracking Matrix 2020; Kassem 2020; Benton et al. 2022). The pandemic included both restrictions of movement across national boundaries and some restrictions connected to internal boundaries in countries such as Australia (Australian Human Rights Commission 2021).

In the context of terror threats, a range of researchers has highlighted how political and other elites have sought to link migration to terror threats in Europe and the United States, especially since the September 11, 2001, attacks on the United States. As observed by Messina (2014, p. 535), 'Although opinions diverge somewhat about the

specific motives inspiring such discourse, the conventional wisdom is that numerous mainstream politicians and extreme right political actors have rhetorically exploited September 11 and other terrorist-related events in a deliberate and calculated manner.⁷ He notes, however, that there is variation among cases and accounts of securitisation.

Extraterritorial enforcement of migration can be seen as closely related to the securitised migration by political elites. *Extraterritorial* denotes the processes of delegating or transferring tasks related to migration control to third countries. It is also referred to in the literature as the externalisation of migration governance or policies. The externalisation of migration control to third countries is at multi- and bi-lateral levels. Extraterritorial initiatives also include measures such as interdiction at sea and other *non-entrée*⁴ (*no entry*) policies like carrier liability and visa requirements (Hathaway 1992; Hathaway 2005; Fischer-Ilescano et al. 2009; den Heijer 2012; Hathaway and Gammeltoft-Hansen 2014; Hirsch and Bell 2017; Crisp 2022; International Migration Research Hub 2022; see also Moreno-Lax 2017; Ambrosini and Hajer 2023).

Most international law has yet to be crafted and remains in constant evolution (Suter 2004; Slagter 2022). However, some national and supranational legislation are clear examples of *non-entrée* policies. Legislation such as the United Kingdom's Immigration (Carrier's Liability) Act (1987) and Amendment Regulations (2023) penalises airlines and ships having passengers aboard without proper documentation or vehicles having clandestine entrants. Or the European Union's Carrier Sanctions Directive (2001a) requires the same scrutiny of passengers' documents before they board the carriers, with both passenger and transporter liable for penalties and

⁴ A term first credited to Hathaway (1992).

repatriation costs (see also Ruff 1989; Nicholson 1997; Rodenhäuser 2014; Cesarz 2019). These types of legislation are in direct conflict with international law that is established, namely the Convention on the Status of Refugees article 31, in which states 'shall not impose penalties on account of their illegal entry or presence' (United Nations 1951; see also Hathaway and Gammeltoft-Hansen 2014).

Setting aside the legal debate on extraterritorial jurisdiction that may be attached to extraterritorial enforcement, the EU has adopted several measures to deter and disrupt clandestine migration before migrants reach European territory. These external initiatives fall into three broad categories. The first includes unilateral actions by the EU and Member States that impact the third country and occur without consultation or coordination with it. Examples would be the issuance of visas for stays not exceeding three months, consular activity or the rules for passing through external frontiers (Rijpma and Cremona 2007). The second category focuses on coordination with third countries. This could include partnering with neighbouring states to strengthen security at their external borders and providing incentives for them to halt or otherwise disturb and slow these flows. The third category is comprised of those migrants from countries deemed to be 'safe', and the procedures for denying even the opportunity to apply for asylum,

Where a third country can be regarded as a safe country of origin, Member States should be able to designate it as safe and presume its safety for a particular applicant, unless he/she presents serious counter-indications (Council of the European Union 2005, p. 14; see also Cassarino 2007; Adepoju et al. 2009).

For the third category to be effective in practice, there needs to be certain buy-ins from a third country to accept the return of its own citizens under international convention and law on repatriation (United Nations 1966). Sometimes such cooperation

is less than forthcoming by states, such as when Senegal cancelled its repatriation deal with Spain, as reported by *NBC* (1 June 2006). In some cases, Member States have found resistance also comes from the courts, as when the Court of Justice of the European Union ruled against the Czech Republic, Hungary and Poland for refusing to take in asylum seekers fleeing conflicts in Iraq and Syria in violation of European law (Rankin 2020; Court of Justice of the European Union 2020; Progin-Theuerkauf 2021; European Commission 2021d).

Section 3.3 gives background details on efforts by Member States to coordinate migration enforcement at their shared regional borders. Section 3.4 then discusses the extraterritorial enforcement of migration by the EU through coordination with third countries, including those on some of the key Sahara routes.

3.3 European Union Migration Control Mechanisms

The increasing securitisation of migration has presaged more stringent and systematic enforcement measures, best captured under the European Agenda for Migration of 2015. Central to the agenda were ‘reducing the incentives for irregular migration,’ and border management – ‘saving lives and securing external borders’ (European Commission 2015a). This section discusses four enforcement areas: coordinated border security, search and rescue at Sea, technology-based initiatives and Voluntary Return and Reintegration programmes. EU proposals for regional disembarkation platforms are also briefly examined as an example of non-cooperation from countries of origin and as a lead into the next section. Section 3.4 then focuses on extraterritorial extensions of EU border enforcement efforts.

3.3.1 Border Security

EU border security operations have grown increasingly sophisticated and wide-ranging. In 2013, the European Border Surveillance System (EUROSUR) was created as a cooperative structure for data sharing and other activities to deter clandestine migration, crime, and the protection of migrants. Each Member State has established a National Coordination Centre (NCC). The NCC assists with information sharing between all official entities involved in external border security and provides a national situational analysis (Jeandesboz 2011; European Commission 2018b). Further, under the 2015 European Agenda for Migration, patrols by FRONTEX were intensified in the Mediterranean Sea. More recently, FRONTEX has established agreements with an estimated value of US\$ 51 million with various aerospace and defence companies, including Airbus, Israel Aerospace Industries and Elbit. Particularly salient here, one of these contracts' deliverables was for drones to conduct surveillance services along the blue sea borders in the Mediterranean Sea (Akkerman 2021). Overall, the EU's border security market has seen annual growth rates of around 15 per cent (Homeland Security Research 2017; see also Akkerman 2021; 2021a; Market Research Future 2021).

A notable joint border patrol and interception initiatives include Operation Hera, coordinated by Spain and FRONTEX and launched in 2006 in response to increased entries to the Canary Islands from western Sahara routes. Hera has had several phases or operational periods, involving interviews and identification of arriving migrants, and also intensified patrols to intercept boats carrying migrants or divert them from Canary landings back to Africa (Léonard and Kaunert 2022). Numerous other operations have similarly involved interceptions and rescues at sea (European Border and Coast Guard Agency 2021; European Parliament 2021b). For example, the joint sea

operations of 2015, such as Operation Indalo in the Western Mediterranean and Operation Triton in the Central and Eastern Mediterranean, rescued large numbers of migrants rescued at sea. According to IOM, over 100,000 rescues of migrants took place (Missing Migrants Project 2015). Rescued migrants were then brought to Italy for processing (Scammell and Bonomolo 2015). These large-scale operations were highly sophisticated and involved collaboration between 10 national coast guards and navies, various civilian craft and independent vessels from NGOs like Médecins San Frontières (MSF) and Migrant Offshore Aid Station (MOAS). A primary stated goal of these collaborative efforts was to save lives. Therefore, in some ways this period marked a significant turning point for migrant rescue operations in the Mediterranean Sea, signified by coordination toward a common humanitarian goal. A map published by Missing Migrants Project (2015) shows the extent of the EU flotilla and the operations involved (see figure 3.2).

Figure 3.2 Mediterranean Rescue Operations 2015

Source: Missing Migrants Project 2015.

However, anti-migrant rhetoric, spurred in part by the ongoing flows of asylum seekers from the civil war in Syria, became more prevalent (Fakhoury 2016). In 2015, a dramatic increase in migrants fleeing Syria was welcomed, at least initially, by EU Member States such as Germany, which accepted an estimated 1.5 million persons fleeing the conflict. Since then, however, the ‘migrant crisis’ has become one of the triggering events mobilising populist parties in Europe on both sides of the political spectrum against migrants (Jeandesboz and Pallister-Wilkins 2014; Palm 2018; Casiraghi and Bordignon 2022). By 2019, there was a marked increase in migrants intercepted at sea in Libya’s territorial waters by the Government of National Accord Libyan Coast Guard and Navy (LCGN) and returned to Libya (Cusumano and Villa 2020; International Organization for Migration 2020a; 2020b). Patrol and rescue operations by FRONTEX in the Mediterranean Sea have intensified due to the uptick of migrants arriving at Lampedusa, especially during summer. The island has a limited capacity for asylum seekers and currently holds close to 1,000 asylum seekers - far above its original capacity of 192 people. In one incident, a vessel carrying an estimated 400 migrants arrived at the island, further exacerbating overcrowding issues. Many migrants manage to leave the facilities to make their continued attempts to reach other areas of the EU or Italian cities like Milan and Rome (Ghezelbash et al. 2018; D’Ignoti 2020; Williams 2022).

Finally, FRONTEX sea surveillance activity, especially in the Atlantic, Central and Western Mediterranean, has become more contentious, around the issue of non-refoulement, or not returning persons to a country where they could face persecution (Mungianu 2016). In 2019, Italy passed a law imposing fines on private boat owners who perform rescues at sea and authorised the seizure of the boats for repeat violators

(Squires 2019). Policies by individual states implementing these types of enforcement actions seem to align with increasingly contentious anti-migrant rhetoric.

3.3.2 Technology-Based Initiatives

Efforts made by the EU to combat human smuggling and trafficking include shifting towards more technology. This shift has emphasised biometrics and the development of sophisticated apprehension and surveillance techniques such as databases like the European Asylum Dactyloscopy Database (EURIDAC). The EURODAC system is the EU's fingerprint database that helps manage asylum applications (European Parliament 2013a; European Commission 2020c). There is also an emphasis on technologies at land and sea borders themselves. For example, heat-seeking or thermal imaging, laser, radar, cameras, edge interruption and databases are operating increasingly globally (Carrera 2007; Global Reports Store 2019) and in Europe. Spain, for example, has developed an extensive system for surveillance, Sistema Integrado de Vigilancia Exterior (SIVE), operated by the Guardia Civil. It employs a sophisticated combination of technologies to identify clandestine vessels and alert command structures for interception (Carling and Hernández-Carretero 2011).

The EU's Smart Border program, in development through 2022, marks another important development in EU border management technology. Its two main components are an Entry/Exit System (EES) and the European Travel Information and Authorisation System (ETIAS). The ESS is a centralised system designed to record the time and place at which a non-EU person or third-country national entered or exited the borders of any

Schengen area country.⁵ Allowing authorities to keep track of entry and exit points is intended to help them identify suspicious activity and potential terrorist threats, as well as reduce clandestine migration. In the context of this chapter, such programs can be seen as means of establishing increasingly more comprehensive surveillance of those crossing borders or seeking entry in an increasingly securitised regional migration context (European Agency for the Operational Management of Large-Scale IT Systems in the Area of Freedom, Security and Justice 2015a; 2015b).

3.3.3 Voluntary Return and Reintegration—Regional Disembarkation Platforms

The Voluntary Return and Reintegration strategy is a significant part of EU migration governance. Accordingly, the EU has established a legal framework and a functioning apparatus for returning migrants from Member States to their countries of origin (European Commission 2018a; Apostolache 2021). The financial investment in this apparatus includes the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund, which aims to support Member States' efforts in countering clandestine migration by strengthening the return process to alternative countries outside the EU (European Union 2021b). International organisations involved in the process, such as IOM and UNHCR, refer to these programmes as Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR). International Organization for Migration began implementing AVRR programmes as far back as 1979 (International Organization for Migration 2018).

⁵ The Schengen Area is a visa and passport-controlled free zone that encompasses 26 European countries, including most EU Member States, excluding Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Ireland and Romania. However, Bulgaria, Croatia and Romania are currently in the process of joining the Schengen Area and applying the Schengen acquis to a large extent. Additionally, also the non-EU States Iceland, Norway, Switzerland and Liechtenstein have joined the Schengen Area (European Commission 2018c).

Domestic politics looms large in these matters in both countries of origin and transit. Bilateral cooperation is key to the effectiveness of any return mechanism. Many times, such cooperation from countries is only sometimes forthcoming. In Senegal, for example, there are conflicts with international lobbying efforts by the EU for a smooth return agreement for that country's citizens. From the perspective of Senegal, as Adam et al. (2020) point out, the domestic political climate is such that if the government consented to EU demands, the political opposition would most surely use it against them. At the same time, politics has not kept Brussels from making a sizeable contribution through the Emergency Trust Fund for Africa (EUTF) in Senegal, with ten national and eight regional programs amounting to US\$ 203 million (Ly and Grégoire 2020; Vieweg 2020). The other issue with this mechanism occurs when the return of migrants is less than voluntary and most often linked to a period of detention. Another contentious issue is when migrants are returned instead to a transit country such as Libya, which raises concerns about refoulement (Le Coz 2021). Finally, this mechanism often puts migrants at risk of human trafficking and other abuses when not considered voluntary. Further dialogue on these scenarios ensues below.

Algeria, Morocco and Tunisia resist returns as much as they support strengthening borders with EU partners and their neighbours. Such is the case between Morocco and Spain—Tunisia and Libya—both Morocco and Tunisia in the case of Algeria (Abderrahim 2019). Similar responses are evident in countries such as The Gambia and Niger, with just enough engagement to keep the developing funding spigot open while at the same time not alarming the public to increase return acceptance rates (Zanker et al. 2019).

Another demonstration of how countries of origin and transit often push back and are less than fully cooperative with EU proposals is the example of regional disembarkation platforms. The idea here is that cooperating countries in North Africa would hold migrants rescued at sea at their ports, thereby embarring them from entry into EU waters and circumventing European responsibility for asylum application claims on its territory (Archick & Margesson 2021). For example, Algeria, Morocco and Tunisia largely dismiss EU calls for regional disembarkation points as problematic. These countries are part of the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) 's Mediterranean Dialogue. These countries are part of the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO)'s Mediterranean Dialogue.⁶ Setup by NATO in an exercise deemed an extension of its regular military purview, the Mediterranean Dialogue is a gathering of nations to establish security and help stabilise common security challenges of which migration is considered one (Abderrahim 2019; Cherkaoui 2021; Security Arrangements and Migration Crises 2022).

3.4 European Union Extraterritorial Enforcement Initiatives (Third Countries)

The remainder of the chapter examines the European Union's recent moves to intensify and continue to extend its enforcement regime beyond its own borders. That intensification was significantly influenced by the Arab Spring in 2011, when control by various authoritarian governments in North Africa over their own populations and territories became more uneven or was weakened. That raised concerns within the EU about increased migration flows from that region and helped shape the development of the European Commission's Global Approach to Migration and Mobility (GAAM). It

⁶ There are seven members of the Mediterranean Dialogue, Algeria, Egypt, Israel, Jordan, Mauritania, Morocco and Tunisia (North Atlantic Treaty Organization 2022).

features provisions for strengthening partnerships with other nations to address migration (European Commission 2011; Minnucci 2016). Specifically, the GAAM represents a significant part of the EU's efforts to take migration deterrence and enforcement activities and externalise them beyond its borders. It provides a policy framework to formalise such externalisation. The framework emphasises 'migration routes management,' where sending and transit countries are enlisted as partners in enforcement and related activities while also receiving aid intended to address drivers of migration (Mainwaring 2019; European Commission 2011; 2011a; European Parliament 2020).

Related to the framework, the European Commission has developed several major dialogue and coordination initiatives. Notable here is the European Agenda on Migration, a 2015 initiative meant to provide an immediate response to large number of refugees and migrants then entering EU states, while also establishing a longer-term, comprehensive approach to managing migration in the region (European Commission 2015a). A second initiative is the Joint Valletta Action Plan (JVAP), a set of political and operational measures to enhance cooperation between countries in Africa and Europe. The purpose of JVAP is to establish systems for equitable migration management of impacted countries of the Mediterranean Sea (European Commission 2015b). The primary funding mechanism developed to support these high-level communications is the European Union Emergency Trust Fund for Africa (EUTF for Africa), a fund for a host of projects along a broad spectrum devoted to addressing various root causes of migration and regional displacement (European Union 2021; 2022).

A third key regional migration governance initiative is the New Pact on Migration and Asylum, recognising that there needs to be shared responsibility and that Member States should more equally share in migration governance initiatives and measures (European Commission 2020a). Part of implementing all of these initiatives include the EU's relationship with third countries. These partnerships include ways to combat human smuggling, develop more robust migration governance that manages clandestine migration, and better support the forced displacement of people.

I will offer details on some related exemplar programs here and then discuss more narrowly how extraterritorial enforcement of the EU border regime has developed within specific African countries. One exemplar initiative is the Seahorse Project, an initiative of Spain and its Coast Guard, Guardia Civil, supported by EU funding. It included the States of Gambia, Guinea-Bissau, Cape Verde, Mauritania, Morocco, Senegal and West Africa. Cooperation took the form of training, equipment and shared border patrols (Casas-Cortes et al. 2016; Monroy 2018; Casas-Cortes and Cobarrubias 2019; see also Carrera 2007; European Commission 2005; 2010). Separately, Italy has delivered equipment such as boats and vehicles to Tunisia to stem the flow of clandestine migration (Gerli 2016). Similarly in Libya since Gaddafi's overthrow, an association that existed before the 2011 Arab Spring has been re-envisioned, focused primarily on strengthening Libya's borders through funding and technological enhancements and increasing the effectiveness of Libyan Coastguard activity in the Central Mediterranean (European Union Emergency Trust Fund for Africa 2017).

Extraterritorial EU enforcement also has been prominent beyond North Africa, extending to countries such as Niger, Mauritania, Senegal and The Gambia. As an example, the EU has spent approximately US\$ 347 million on training border forces in

Niger, based on 2019 data. This is in addition to 1 billion worth of EU development cooperation assistance from 2014-2020 (European Commission 2017b). I may note also here that, according to a 2016 study, human smuggling operations and transit migration through the country have contributed over US\$ 103 million to the local economy (European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation 2016). Such revenue is significant in Niger, which ranks last out of 189 countries on the UN Human Development Index (HDI). The HDI is an index that measures education, income per capita and life expectancy (United Nations Development Programme 2020).

Particularly notable here, under pressure from European governments, Niger 2015 passed a law banning human smuggling. With EU funding, the Niger government cracked down on such activities, resulting in smugglers seeking more isolated routes through the desert and, in some cases, abandoning large numbers of migrants in remote terrain (Penney 2018). Such political and enforcement dynamics have served to compound and make more persistent threats of violence, sexual assault and kidnapping from smugglers, gangs, authorities and others on the routes (Black 2020). They are discussed further in Chapters Four and Six.

Overall, the EU has undertaken myriad measures to reduce migration flows along high-risk migration routes through the Sahara Desert, deter covert entry to its Member States, and disrupt human smuggling syndicates. There have been millions of Euros spent on training border forces in Niger and joint task forces within the African Union since 2014 (European Parliament 2015b; FitzGerald 2020; Topak and Vives 2020; European Union 2021). Incentivising countries to act to deter migration flows heading to the EU is thus a core component of this overall strategy in the region. The European Union makes assurances of more attractive trade terms, a more liberal visa

partnership, investments in equipment and training. It also may threaten the withholding of development aid for non-support (Akkerman 2021). In addition, the EU is one of the largest funders of humanitarian activities in North Africa (European Union 2021).

Finally, extraterritorial coordination of enforcement has emerged outside of border agencies, via organisations such as the International Association of Gendarmeries and Police Forces with Military Status, which includes European and African states among its now 19 members. Since the mid-1990s, the association has sought to provide opportunities for police forces to share data, methods and tradecraft (Mountz and Hiemstra 2012), and in recent years it has facilitated more robust cooperation on migration, including enhanced surveillance and joint training (Acosta Sánchez 2021).

3.5 Enforcement: Central Mediterranean Route to Italy

This section focuses on the deterrence efforts of Niger, Libya and Tunisia and discusses Algeria in conjunction with the Western Mediterranean Route. The Central Mediterranean Route to Italy includes routes typically starting in Niger and include Algeria, Libya and Tunisia. These migration routes traverse the Sahara Desert. From there, migrants attempt to cross to Italy's mainland, Lampedusa, or Malta. I will note that, while this research focuses on high-risk migration to Europe, much of the migration through Africa is South-South and considered mixed migration within the continent. It is the case, however, that the risks associated with more stringent enforcement, including that resulting from EU extraterritorial enforcement of its border regime, affect Sahara migrants regardless of their ultimate intended destinations.

3.5.1 Niger

For migrants travelling the Central Mediterranean Route, Niger is the first major transit hub. As mentioned, Niger is perhaps the poorest country in the world by Human Development Index indicators. Salient here, it also has visa-free travel for nationals of the 14 other Member States of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS).⁷ ECOWAS citizens are affirmed such free movement across regional borders under the Treaty of the Economic Community of West African States, Chapter I, Article 2, Sub-section (d) and Chapter IV, Article 27 (Economic Community of West African States 1975). Such rights are reinforced under Article 3, Section 2, Sub-section d) iii) of the Revised Treaty (Economic Community of West African States 1993). This means that in principle, travelling from Niger to the border of Libya on the Central Mediterranean Route through the Sahara should be safeguarded for nationals of these countries.

The African Union, which includes 55 African states,⁸ also has taken steps toward a free movement regime in recent years – following on from its 1963-99 predecessor the Organization for African Unity (OAU) The African Union in 2016 began introducing a common regional passport, and in 2018 enshrined principles of full free movement in the Protocol to the Treaty Establishing the African Economic Community Relating to Free Movement of Persons, Right of Residence and Right of Establishment (African Union 2018). More than 30 Member States had signed the

⁷ ECOWAS Member States include Benin, Burkina Faso, Cabo Verde, Côte d'Ivoire, The Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Togo.

⁸ The UN recognises 54 nations in Africa instead of the 55 identified by the African Union (AU). The difference in numbers lies with the politically disputed territory of Western Sahara. Morocco considers Western Sahara to be part of its sovereign territory. However, the Polisario Front independence movement considers Western Sahara independent of Morocco and part of the Sahrawi Arab Democratic Republic (SADR). The SADR is a full member of the AU and recognised by the UN as a non-self-governing territory (United Nations 2022; Kyris 2022).

Protocol through 2022, though only four relatively small states had ratified it, leaving it well short of implementation (see also Organization for African Unity 1991).

This backstory is essential to understanding the region, as inherent tension has developed between the movement by African regional institutions toward freeing the movement of persons and the chief European institution toward limiting it. Niger holds a strategic place in the latter's extraterritorial enforcement migration governance strategy. It is the primary beneficiary of EU development funding, such as the EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa (EUTF). That places the EU in a strategic negotiating advantage to push for greater migration deterrence by Niger, with significant implications for migrants travelling the Central Mediterranean Route. Specifically, around 2013, roughly half of all migrants from West Africa travelled that route through the city of Agadez in northern central Niger. As the Niger government increasingly coordinated with EU authorities, it suppressed the movement of large numbers of trucks transporting migrants to Libya. This led smugglers, who control most aspects of border movement and trade, to establish alternative routes, at significantly higher prices to migrants and increased risks (Gallagher and David 2014; Deliversky 2017; McMahon and Sigona 2018).

At the Member State level, there are initiatives with Niger by countries including Germany and the Netherlands. One such initiative is part of the European Union Capacity Building (EUCAP) mission in Sahel Niger. The countries invested US\$10.2 million in Niger to instruct, outfit and recruit, border combat clandestine migration and trafficking in narcotics and weaponry (Global Detention Project 2019). Similarly, the Support for Justice and Border Management in Niger (AJUSEN) project includes contributions of more than US\$ 50 million from Italy, \$30 million from the

European Union and \$10 million from France. The funding has underwritten the creation of eight regional command posts for security forces, eight new border police posts, construction of posts for domestic security forces on the border, technology to aid in combating migrant smuggling, and support for courts (Alliance Sahel 2020). It also includes resources for migrants and increased investment for the EUFT's Sustainable Return from Niger (Akkerman 2018). The purpose of listing these arrangements is to highlight the enormous influence of the EU and relevant Member States by financing an African country in significant need, which gives the EU considerable leverage in advancing its extraterritorial enforcement of migration aspirations.

In the Niger context also, the domestic legal framework poses inherent obstacles to migrants, in relation to laws concerning entry, residence, stay and exit for foreigners. These include Ordinance No. 81-40, Article four, allowing for the expulsion of those travelling without documentation (Niger 1981). Article eleven provides for the criminalisation of those who do not leave the country after being ordered (Niger 1987). This juridical structure strengthens as the years go by to include Ordonnance No. 2010-86, which deals with combating human trafficking and sets penalties and survivor protections (Niger 1987; 2010). Notably here, Niger's Law Against Illicit Smuggling of Migrants (Niger 2015), made it the first country in the Sahel region to enact legislation to combat migrant smuggling (United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime 2000). The legislation aims to penalise those involved in human smuggling and significantly disrupt operations to reduce these ventures. The loosely organised smuggling syndicates generate profits in the hundreds of millions yearly (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime 2011).

Further in relation to legal and governance frameworks salient to the high-risk journeys through Niger, I note that the United Nations at the country level primarily intervenes with its Integrated Strategy for the Sahel (UNISS). Through UNISS and agencies such as United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC), the UN helps strengthen the scope of government to better protect migrants against human smugglers and foster enhanced levels of support between States involved through protocols such as the Protocol Against Smuggling of Migrants Land, Sea and Air (United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime 2000). However, these differing points of law create the space for the detention of migrants' subjects without authorities needing to specify the terms of custody (Niger 2015; Yuen 2020).

Data is hard to obtain when it comes to the imprisonment of migrants. NGOs like Amnesty International and the Global Detention Project are making efforts to document the conditions of detention centres. An Amnesty International report (2018) identified certain police stations holding arrested migrants. At the same time, data is scarce, and there is little research into the conditions of migrants after arrest. The legal framework also lacks safeguards for those in detention, such as legal representation. Adding to this are pushbacks of migrants by Algerian authorities, both nationals from other countries and those of Niger itself, back onto Nigerien territory. The legal systems in the country are ill-equipped to assist migrants fully in these vulnerable conditions.

Adding to this are threats to migrants from other actors, such as transnational criminal syndicates and terrorist organisations (Raineri 2018; see Frowd 2020; Hahonou and Olsen 2021; see also figure 4.3). In short, nothing presented here about the Niger context denotes a hospitable environment for migrants travelling to reach Europe. These themes repeat throughout the region as States in general ignore the rights of migrants

and create even more hostile environments. The above thus should begin to give some narrower sense of the ways in which the securitisation of migration in the European Union (Buzan et al. 1998; Sanchez 2020; Van Dessel 2021), and extraterritorial enforcement of migration has multiplied and, in many ways, compounded risks for migrants already traveling on high-risk routes.

3.5.2 Libya

Migrants in Libya, especially the newly arrived, are more vulnerable in a structurally strained country that lacks a fully functioning, unified government and access to health and other public services (Displacement Tracking Matrix 2021a; 2021b). Conditions are dire in this environment where the fractured militia runs the country. These are situations in which migrants are subject to frequent and arbitrary detention (Displacement Tracking Matrix 2021c). There are numerous reports by humanitarian IGOs and NGOs, including testimony in this research, of beatings, extortion, forced labour, gender-based violence (GBV), and other freedoms and rights violations (United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs 2021). Brussels negotiates with these militias at the EU level to curb migration flows. There is a significant investment of millions of Euros to strengthen detention capabilities and personnel training. Libya's Department for Combatting Illegal Immigration (DCIM) is the bureaucracy responsible for the detention system in the country. There has also been significant investment in the equipping and training of Libya Search and Rescue personnel to support patrols at sea (Global Detention Project 2020a). Overall, in 2021, 32,425 migrants were returned to Libya after rescue in the Central Mediterranean Sea, according to the International Organization for Migration Libya (2022b).

What was once an EU-led effort to rescue migrants at sea involving coast guards and many EU Member States' navies was effectively handed over to Libya in 2018. The responsibility for interceptions and rescues lies with the Libyan Coast Guard. The intention is to have as many migrants return to Libya rather than Italy. However, the lines are often blurred between Libyan authorities involved in detention operations and closely aligned with militias engaged in human smuggling and trafficking (United States Department of State 2022).

Regarding the EU Member State level and Libya, some Italian political elites have long framed clandestine migration from the Mediterranean Sea as an invasion. Successive Italian governments have sought partnerships with Libya to curb arrivals. Italian authorities also make efforts to prevent vessels that have rescued migrants aboard from disembarking in Italian ports -- in contravention of the Convention on the Law of the Sea (Paoletti 2010; United Nations 1982; Global Detention Project 2020a). In 2017, Italy entered with Libya and agreed to a 'Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) on cooperation in the fields of development, the fight against illegal immigration, human trafficking and fuel smuggling and on reinforcing the security of borders between the State of Libya and the Italian Republic' (Italy 2017). The MOU, which was renewed in 2020, builds on previous agreements made between the two nations, namely the Treaty of Friendship, Partnership and Cooperation (2008) and the Tripoli Declaration (2012), which spells out implementation strategies to find 'urgent solutions' to clandestine migrants (see also Libya 2009; Italy 2017).

The text of the MOU provides a straightforward exemplar of principles of extraterritorial enforcement being put into practice by EU-level institutions and an EU Member State. It outlines some support for migrants at reception centres and is heavily

tilted to enforcement and aid for Libya (European Union Emergency Trust Fund for Africa 2017; Italy 2017; Palm 2017, 2018; Reviglio 2020). An analysis by Anja Palm of the Istituto Affari Internazionale in Rome, observes that in the MOU:

...immediate actions clearly focus on reducing entries to Italy at any cost. Not only is the goal of the memorandum repeatedly stated to be the stemming of flows of transiting migrants through Libya to Europe,[and] the more detailed actions outlined in the MoU (as well as in subsequent deals and meetings) primarily focus on securitising Libya's borders and preventing departures. Indeed, if the memorandum were to be implemented according to its wording, migrants would be blocked and – most probably – pushed-back at the Libyan southern border, or would be intercepted by the Libyan coast guard upon departure to Europe by sea and transferred back to local reception camps pending repatriation or voluntary return to their countries of origin (Palm 2017).

Some of the significant issues that arise from such extraterritorial enforcement arrangements again are the potential violation and disregard of the *non-refoulement* principle, prohibiting the return of anyone to a country where “torture, cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment is a distinct possibility.” Courts have highlighted violations of international law in some such cases. For example, the European Court of Human Rights in 2012 issued a judgment in a case where a group of Eritrean and Somali migrants embarked from Libya, intending to reach Italy. However, the Italian Revenue Police and the Coastguard vessels intercepted the group of migrants in Malta waters and returned them to Libya. As a result, the Court found that Italy had violated the Articles of Convention (United Nations 1982) and put the applicants at risk (European Court of Human Rights 2012).

Another significant regional actor in the Libyan context is the United Kingdom, which has made significant aid transfers to Libya aimed in part at upgrading detention centres and strengthening naval operations. A report by the UK Independent

Commission for Aid Impact raised concerns that such coordination could increase the risk for migrants and violate their rights: “While reducing the number of deaths at sea is vital, we are concerned that the program delivers migrants back to a system that leads to indiscriminate and indefinite detention and denies refugees their right to asylum (Independent Commission for Aid Impact 2017). Further, the Commission reported concerns that local and State actors, often in official capacities, are deeply linked to human smuggling and trafficking, and have been involved in extorting migrants in detention (Gallagher and Pearson 2010; Tini 2017).

At the country level then, investment by the EU and particular Member States to deter migration and prohibit landings means that migrants’ vulnerabilities can be intensified, with the real prospects of prolonged detention after interception crossing the border from the Sahara Desert or at Sea. Moreover, according to reports, detainees, estimated in the tens of thousands, encounter regular abuse (Global Detention Project 2020a; see also Mountz and Loyd 2013; Flynn 2017).

3.6.3 Tunisia

Tunisia, located on the southern Mediterranean between Libya and Algeria, plays a vital role in migration flows in the region, despite its relatively small size. Estimates are that 20 per cent of arrivals to the EU depart from Tunisia, most of them nationals from sub-Saharan Africa (International Organization for Migration 2022a). Moreover, as the country increases its securitised migration along its land and sea borders, it has entered partnerships with EU institutions and certain Member States. One such example is the 2014 EU-Tunisia Mobility Partnership (European Commission 2021b) with 10 EU

members.⁹ Among other elements, the partnership arrangement provides a gateway to migrants' readmission to Tunisia. The country also has agreements with Italy on the readmission of nationals from third countries back to Tunisia, including funding for the creation and maintenance of detention centres (Global Detention Project 2020b). And, it has negotiated new agreements with the UK since that country's exit from the European Union.

Domestically, the Tunisian legal framework is such that while there are built-in protections to oversee and guarantee the opportunity to seek asylum, the actual asylum infrastructure has significant challenges. Moreover, some laws criminalise clandestine migration, creating a sphere of vulnerability for migrants, which includes abuse, arrest, detention, forced expulsions and other punitive measures (Tunisia 1968a; 1968b; 1975; 2004; Global Detention Project 2020b; see also Badalič 2019).

Enshrined in the Tunisian Republic Constitution (2014) is Article 29. Under this Article, how long someone is in detention must be 'defined by law,' and detainees have the right to legal representation. Yet, the Article in practice seems irrelevant to apprehended migrants and their subsequent treatment. For example, a 2016 study based on migrant testimony found that authorities denied nationals from Senegal the right to apply for asylum—instead, they experienced arbitrary expulsion. Arrivals from other States, such as Cote d'Ivoire, Ghana, were also refused by security forces. The criminalization of clandestine migration contributes to prolonged detention, the barring of migrants from ever reaching UNHCR to make an asylum claim and forced expulsion regardless of legal statute (Planes-Boissac et al. 2010; Office of the High Commissioner

⁹ The EU-Tunisia Mobility Partnership 2014 agreement is between Tunisia and Belgium, Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, Poland, Portugal, Spain, Sweden and the UK.

for Human Rights 2013; Badalič 2019; Tunisian Forum for Economic and Social Rights 2019; United Nations 2000a; 2000b; Global Detention Project 2020b).

3.6 Enforcement: Atlantic and West Africa Routes to Spain (Canary Islands)

The West Africa and Atlantic Routes to Spain pass through the Sahara Desert and open to numerous embarkation points along the Atlantic Coast. From these points migrants make their way by sea to the Canary Islands. The routes, which have seen an ebb and flow of migrant numbers since the early 2000s, saw increasing movements in 2021, with related increases in risk, death and disappearance amid shipwrecks along the Atlantic coasts. 2021 saw a modest decrease in migration to the Canary Islands, with 22,316 reaching its shores from West Africa by boat. This figure is 707 persons lower than 2020's 23,023 total (Displacement Tracking Matrix 2022b).

3.6.1 Morocco

For migrants on these routes, Morocco is a key transit country, both by sea to the Canary Islands and by land to Ceuta and Melilla – Spanish colonial-era holdings on bordering Morocco. They represent the only land border between Africa and Europe. With Spain's strengthening of the land border with Morocco from the enclaves of Ceuta and Melilla, the West Africa and Atlantic routes became attractive to migrants in 2005, went more dormant in subsequent years and has seen a resumption of activity in 2020 and 2021 (Vives and Williams 2021; International Organization for Migration 2020c). As such, Morocco is essential to the EU's extraterritorial enforcement strategies. Migrants travelling through Morocco face a host of deterrent forces at every level, including the EU, Member States and the State of Morocco itself (Vives 2017a).

As an example, in December 2019, an announcement in an EC communique stated that the EU was enhancing its partnership with Morocco with programmes amounting to US\$ 402 million, including via the EUTF for Africa to support Morocco with improved strategies to deter clandestine migration, including human trafficking (European Commission 2019). One result is that the EU's second-largest cooperation portfolio on migration in the region is with Morocco, with a total of US\$ 357 million, out of which around US\$ 246 million is drawn from the EUTF for Africa, with the balance from other EU financial instruments (European Union 2021). In addition, the Euro-Mediterranean agreement between Morocco and 15 Member States provides a framework for partnership development on progress made by Morocco towards their common purpose of security in the Euro-Mediterranean zone (European Union 2000b).

Boni and Lacomba (2011) frame the relationship as one of co-development between security and trade at the EU level. However, tensions exist between two policy objectives: EU security and its commitment to curbing clandestine migration, and free commerce between Member States and Morocco. At the Member State level, France, Germany, Portugal and Spain have signed readmission agreements with Morocco. In addition, arrangements with Portugal and Spain exist to tackle clandestine migration between their countries, resulting in the return of migrants rescued at sea to ports in Morocco (Vives 2017b). Further evidence of the complex nature of returns is how the judiciary weighs outcomes. The case mentioned above against Italy resulted in a judgement from the European Court of Human Rights favouring the applicants. In another case brought before the Court, two nationals from Mali were disputing their expulsion back to Morocco after having reached Spain by clandestine means. The Court ruled in favour of Spain. The judicial ruling upheld the right to return migrants

attempting a clandestine national border crossing, affirming their responsibility for maintaining control over it (European Court of Human Rights 2020). The Court highlighted that the removal was a consequence of the migrant petitioners' own conduct. The ruling was striking in seeming to set aside explicit criteria for *non-refoulement* and instead setting a possibly ambiguous 'own conduct' standard (United Nations 1951; European Parliament 2013b).

Migrants also confront laws governing migration detention and the criminalization of clandestine entry at the Morocco country level. Embedded in these laws are the framework necessary for prosecuting migration infractions, financial penalties of between US\$ 194 to US\$ 1,949 and prison terms of up to six months (Global Detention Project 2021). Furthermore, those who evade expulsion orders or re-offend by returning under similar means or methods may be given additional prison terms of six months to two years (Morocco 2003). At the same time, Title II: Fundamental Freedoms and Rights of Morocco's Constitution (Article 23), provides that anyone held in detention should be informed of the reason they are being held, 'And of his rights, including that of remaining silent. He must benefit, as well, from juridical assistance and of the possibility of communication with his relations, in accordance with the law' (Morocco 2011). In practice, migrants typically lack legal protections and often face racist rhetoric and targeting violence (Sow et al. 2016; Bachlet 2018).

3.7 Enforcement: Western Mediterranean Route to Spain (Ceuta and Melilla)

The Western Mediterranean Route runs from countries in Central Africa, such as Cameroon, Gabon and Nigeria, through to Niger and Mali. It traverses the Sahara

Desert and Algeria, then runs through Morocco to the southern Mediterranean coastline, often to the Spanish enclaves of Ceuta and Melilla or to boats seeking to make the crossing to Spain.

3.8.1 Algeria

Algeria is thus a key transit destination country for migrants travelling the Western Mediterranean Routes, and a focus for the EU as part of extraterritorial enforcement efforts. In practice, Algeria has largely remained more independent of EU-level agreements than Libya and Morocco. Instead, it has preferred bilateral agreements with specific EU and African Union members, such as close cooperation with Spain and Morocco on active border surveillance, a hardening of the frontier and a strong collaboration with Niger on migration-related issues (Triandafyllidou 2018b). The security situation for migrants is certainly as precarious as the states mentioned previously in this chapter. Algeria appears, based on reporting, to have adopted a rigid stance on migrants in the country. Arbitrary detention, raids and expulsions are common. According to migrant testimony, including this research, authorities regularly force detainees back into the desert on either Niger or Mali borders. Human Rights Watch (2021) reported that authorities expelled an estimated 17,000 migrants from sub-Saharan countries between January and October 2020 without consideration for status or the right to appeal.

In terms of the domestic legal context in Algeria, Law N° 08-11 (Algeria 2008) encompasses how foreigners may enter, stay and exit the country. It also specifies criminal penalties for infractions, with prison terms of up to two years, plus fines from US\$ 64 to US\$ 194. The law also sets out certain conditions for authorities to expel

foreign nationals, including proper notification with a Ministry of Interior order and the right to appeal any such ruling in front of an administrative tribunal and allows the appellant the right to representation. Notwithstanding these assurances, migrants face a lack of access to these mechanisms, including lodging a complaint, insufficient information about procedures, lack of access to appropriate representation, and fear of immediate expulsion if they raise concerns (Refugee Studies Centre 2019).

I note in this context that the Constitution of the People's Democratic Republic of Algeria (1989) and the revision of 1996 enshrines certain protections for foreigners. Article 67, for example, states that 'Any foreigner being legally on the national territory enjoys the protection of his person and his properties by the law', while Article 69 states that 'In no case, a political refugee having legally the right of asylum can be delivered or extradited' (Algeria 1989). These passages highlight again the tensions between formal protections and the treatment of migrants in practice.

3.8 Conclusion

This chapter provided essential insight into the conceptual framework underpinning this thesis. That framework focuses on two aspects of migration governance: the securitisation of migration and extraterritorial enforcement by the EU and its Member States. In practical terms, it has highlighted the increasingly stringent enforcement faced by migrants on various high-risk routes and how, when states tighten enforcement and enact policies that limit safe and legal migration pathways as forms of deterrence, migrants/smugglers typically seek even riskier alternative routes and journeys. Overall, a picture emerges of a securitized migration context, marked by increasingly

comprehensive surveillance and border security regimes around the EU and within neighbouring states that place constant downward pressure on migrants.

The first section provided definitional details on securitization and the extraterritorial extension of the EU enforcement regime. Securitisation, it was shown, is a process typically driven by political elites and involving the framing of issues such as migration as security threats, rather than as more routine economic or social processes. Such framings are typically used as justifications for more stringent border enforcement and more recently for extensions of immigration enforcement and control.

The next section examined the intensification of migration enforcement measures in and around the EU. It focused on specific areas of control, including (1) border security and interceptions/rescues at sea, (2) technology-based initiatives and (3) voluntary return and reintegration. In terms of the first element, it was shown that the border security apparatus of the EU is massive and intricate. It involves cooperation between government, law enforcement and private industry levels to create systems to respond more quickly and tackle clandestine migration through FRONTEX on land and sea. Second, it was shown how technological advances at borders themselves, such as thermal imaging and advanced alerts, strengthen responses to intercept smugglers and attempts at entry. Finally, the EU's Voluntary Return and Reintegration mechanism was discussed as a significant part of the migration governance strategy, its aim being to support Member States in returning migrants to third countries. It was discussed how those states have faced challenges at times enlisting the cooperation of origin countries in North and West Africa, and how some return initiatives have been highlighted as in severe tension with principles of *non-refoulement* to transit countries where they could face persecution. The EU proposals for regional disembarkation platform were also

highlighted as being soundly rejected by countries for fear of being stuck with the burden of managing asylum claims and supporting migrants' long-term.

The next section focused on the extension, or extraterritorial enforcement of EU border measures beyond its own land and sea borders, to Africa. It was discussed how such efforts intensified following the Arab Spring events around 2011, when some authoritarian governments in northern Africa faced popular challenges or revolt, raising concern for the EU that instability would lead to large-scale increases in migration. When regimes fell in Libya and Tunisia, the EU sought to establish relationships within those states to ensure the restriction of mobility towards its borders. These efforts culminated in policy actions such as the European Commission's Global Approach to Migration and Mobility, cooperation networks such as Seahorse, programming like the West Sahel, and other projects aiming to strengthen EU relationships with critical North and West African States. Details were provided on the large-scale investments by the EU in such extraterritorial enforcement and control initiatives.

Then there was a presentation of the enforcement picture for migrants along the Central Mediterranean Route to Italy, looking at three essential countries Niger, Libya and Tunisia. Three levels of intervention were discussed for each country: the EU, Member State and country-specific level initiatives. It was discussed how the free movement of people is a core principle for the Economic Community of West African States, and increasingly for the African Union. However, such principles are in significant tension with EU and Member State extraterritorial enforcement efforts.

The context for and pressures on migrants were discussed for the specific countries. Countries like Niger are moving towards greater enforcement towards migrants making their way through their territory, making them increasingly subject to

arrest, arbitrary detention and forms of abuse. Further, it was discussed how in the Central Mediterranean Sea interceptions that once were framed and primarily executed as rescue operations led by the EU are now the responsibility of Libya. Migrants are increasingly returned to that country and face uncertain futures, with prolonged detention in many cases. Finally, it was highlighted how migrants traveling through States such as Tunisia face a system whose legal framework specifies their protection, and whose enforcement regime often violates protections in practice.

The next section similarly presented the context for migrants travelling the Atlantic and West Africa Route to Spain (Canary Islands). It discussed how in states such as Morocco migrants face a host of deterrent forces evolving from three levels of intervention: the EU, Member State and the country-specific initiatives. In this example, the relationship between trade, development and security is acute, with EU investments translating into arrangements to return to Morocco migrants intercepted at sea.

The final section presented the enforcement picture for migrants along the Western Mediterranean Route to Spain (Ceuta and Melilla), looking at Algeria and showing three levels of intervention: the EU, the Member State and the country-specific initiatives. It was discussed how, for the most part, Algeria has remained independent of the EU, opting for bilateral arrangements with specific EU and AU Member States for border surveillance and other migration issues.

Overall, this chapter has provided context for understanding the increasingly high-risk context in which migrants attempt to reach Europe via the Sahara routes. It has highlighted how the increasing securitization of migration by political elites within European Union Member States has provided justifications for a hardening of EU borders and efforts to essentially extend the EU enforcement regime to Africa through

cooperative agreements and coordination with African states, which then similarly have hardened their borders and internal enforcement. Chapter Four examines the agency migrants have sought to exercise in such an increasingly high-risk migration context, with emphasis on their efforts to develop networks in transit and derive from them social capital to aid in their own survival.

Chapter Four

How Migrants Seek to Derive Network Social Capital on High-Risk Migration Routes

4.1 Introduction

4.2 Data Collection Sites and Methods

4.3 Data Analysis Methods

4.4 Six Factors in Deriving Social Capital Through Networks During High-Risk Migration

4.4.1 Having Limited Resources

4.4.2 Having No Contacts at the Intended Destination

4.4.3 Lacking Knowledge of Migration Routes

4.4.4 Travelling Alone

4.4.5 Vulnerability to Authorities

4.4.6 Vulnerability to Human Smugglers and Other Actors

4.5 Six Ways Migrants Derive Social Capital Through Networks During High-Risk Migration

4.5.1 Forming Groups

4.5.2 Humanitarian Organisations

4.5.3 Human Smugglers

4.5.4 Informal Labour Networks

4.5.5 Social Networking Applications

4.5.6 Support of Kinship Connections

4.6 Conclusion

4.1 Introduction

This chapter details how migrants strive to construct specific network-derived social capital as a core part of their survival strategy on high-risk migration routes through the Sahara Desert. My investigation is again informed by an understanding of migration as a complex *social* process, and thus accounts of how individuals seek to develop various forms of social capital (Bourdieu 1986; Putnam 2000; Erel 2010). My focus is on the construction of social capital in the high-risk migration context, in particular where it is central to individuals' strategies on the high-risk migration routes (Garip 2008; Haug 2008; Massey et al. 1990; Massey et al. 1993; Flores-Yeffal and Aysa-Lastra 2011; Cummings et al. 2015). Migrants strive to maintain and build a sense of community and connection to increase safety for themselves. During social capital construction, when faced with an absence of strong ties, there is an imperative to develop and strengthen weak ties as part of an individual's survival strategy (Collyer 2005; see also Engbersen 1995; 2000; Ryan 2011; Gleeson et al. 2020; Ryan 2022; Ryan et al. 2022).

The chapter is structured as follows. First, I discuss the various data collection methods used and sites. Second, I detail the data analysis methods used. Third, I describe the factors that motivate migrants to develop network social capital. Fourth, I present the six types of network-derived social capital that are most prominent in migrants' strategies. To elaborate, the data collection methods and sites section explains the fieldwork and includes the demographic data and critical responses from the 101 high-risk migration participants interviewed. Data collection took place in Niger, Italy and The Gambia over two phases. The first phase of interviews took place in Niger and Italy. The second phase of interviews in The Gambia occurred remotely. The section also discusses the interviews conducted with 16 participants from the humanitarian

sector. Their insight matches to some degree with the experiences of the high-risk migration participants interviewed in the context of their high-risk migration experience, while providing additional context.

The data analysis methods section provides detail on the process used for coding the data, and it discusses how the project was designed to ensure the confirmability and credibility of the analysis through triangulation with other accounts and secondary sources. The following section provides insight into six high-risk migration factors or variables contributing to migrants' vulnerability on high-risk routes. These high-risk migration factors are the impetus to migrants striving to use network-derived social capital and help to shape protection strategies throughout their journey. These factors include (1) having no contacts at intended destination, (2) lacking knowledge of migration routes, (3) limited resources, (4) travelling alone, (5) vulnerability to authorities and (6) vulnerability to human smugglers and other actors (see figure 4.5). The section also highlights the distinctions between what Massey and others found on the Central America and Mexico routes to the United States and the discoveries of this research on the routes through the Sahara (Massey and España 1987; Massey and Sana 2004; Massey and Aysa-Lastra 2011; Mainwaring and Brigden 2016; Garip 2016; Olayo-Méndez et al. 2014; Balaguera and Gonzales 2018; Wurtz 2020).

The final section then delves into the participants' strategies to derive network social capital while in transit. These include:

- (1) forming groups, which in this context is both bonding and bridging capital,
- (2) engaging humanitarian organisations, which is a form of linking capital,
- (3) engaging human smugglers, which is linking capital,
- (4) using informal labour networks, which also is linking capital,

(5) using social networking applications, which is a form of bridging capital and
(6) enlisting the support of kinship connections, which is bonding capital (see figure 4.5). As noted in Chapter Two, each of these types of efforts to develop networks or use existing ones while in transit are responses by migrants to the increasingly stringent and extraterritorial enforcement practices, where Member States work with governments in transit countries to restrict onward mobility and extend their practical enforcement capacities (Geddes 2011; Palm 2020; Kamminga 2020). Migrants work instead to build and develop weak ties of network-derived social capital and in response.

4.2 Data Collection Methods and Sites

This fieldwork involved open-ended, semi-structured interviews with 101 persons who were or had been migrants on high-risk migration routes through the Sahara Desert. Participants were nationals of eleven countries, including Benin (2), Cameroon (4), Gabon (2), Ghana (5), Guinea (2), Ivory Coast (3), Liberia (11), Mali (8), Senegal (22), Sierra Leone (14) and The Gambia (28) (see figure 4.1). In addition, interviews were conducted with 16 staff members of humanitarian organizations with prominent expertise in migration. These interviews were conducted remotely with participants in London, United Kingdom (1)—Juba, South Sudan (1)—Istanbul, Turkey (1)—Vienna, Austria (1)—Berlin, Germany (2)—Rome, Italy (3)—Geneva, Switzerland (7) (see figure 4.2).

Figure 4.1 Overview of High-Risk Migration Participants

Figure 4.2 Overview of Humanitarian Sector Participants

Data collection took place in two phases and at four locations, Niamey, Niger—Rome and Milan, Italy—and The Gambia (see figure 4.3). The recruitment of participants involved multiple-entry, non-random purposive sampling (Etikan et al. 2015; Etikan and Balla 2017). The intention was to identify and engage those who had direct, extensive experience of high-risk migration routes and could speak about their journeys and understandings. Interviews were conducted at sites in Niamey, Milan and Rome. This geographic distribution helped ensure that the dataset provided for a robust comparison of participants’ knowledge base. Of particular interest was how these

individuals utilised their network-derived social capital assets while in transit and at their destination. This exercise helped support a more complete description of the processes of those who face similar circumstances in arrival and transit.

Figure 4.3 Data Collection Sites and High-Risk Migration Route Systems

Source: Base map is adapted from the Mediterranean Transit Migration (MTM) map on mixed migration routes in the MTM region (i-map) (International Centre for Migration Policy Development 2014).

Notes: This map is for illustrative purposes. High-risk migration routes are ever-changing, making migration cartography problematic. As a result, maps are often outdated before many are published (Bacon et al. 2016).

8/12/2022

In phase one, the first location was Niamey, Niger, where fieldwork was conducted in June 2019. Niamey is a major transit hub for migrants travelling from West Africa to Europe and returning after attempting the desert route. Numerous humanitarian organisations provide services there to migrants, including those rescued after being stranded in the desert and returning after abandoning the journey. The prospects were high to have the best opportunity in the time provided to engage potential participants. Further, virtually the entire country was, and still is, under a red-

Figure 4.4 Pilot Study 2017

Source: Szabo 2017.

level high-risk 'do not travel' advisory, highlighting an extremely shaky security situation. Several terrorist groups operate in the country with significant risks to Western travellers. Niamey is the only sector with a yellow 'reconsider travel' advisory. It was as close as I could get to the desert (Smartraveller 2022; United Nations Department of Safety and Security 2022). The pilot study (Szabo 2017) referred to in Chapter One also took place in Niamey. It involved the conduct of background

interviews at a migrant transit to better understand the context and issues at stake for migrants on the high-risk African routes (see figure 4.4).

In 2019, interviews were conducted in public spaces outside the airport and along streets. These are unpaved main streets where a significant amount of people congregates, and they are bustling with the activity of pop-up stalls displaying all sorts of commerce. In total, 18 migrants were interviewed, all males in their early to mid-twenties. Participants in this location were from Cameroon, Liberia, Senegal and Sierra Leone. All had attempted to reach Europe through the Sahara Desert through Algeria to Spain, or Libya to Italy. There were few females in these groups. Given the cultural sensitivities, approaching any female would have been difficult.

After Niamey, interviews were conducted with 38 migrants in Rome. The next location was Milan, Italy, where interviews were conducted with another 17 migrants. In Italy, Rome and Milan are central hubs for those who have made the Central Mediterranean Route crossings of the Sahara Desert and the Mediterranean Sea (Costa 2020; Cremashi et al. 2020; Crawley and Jones 2020). Both cities have for years hosted a large underground economy whose existence is one of the ways migrants survive (Reyneri 1998; Schuster 2005; Rosina 2022). In Rome, recruitment took place near the central Termini railway station and other public spaces nearby. Interviews took place around the Milano Centrale train station and the Piazza del Duomo, Cathedral, the principal city square in Milan. Most discussions took place while migrants were selling tourist trinkets at the two sites.

Unlike in Niamey, where interviewees and visitors to the country were less secure (United Nations Department of Safety and Security 2022; see also Morganbesser and Weis 2018), in Rome and Milan, I contacted migrants in busy tourist areas and on

well-populated streets, in locations where migrants are informal vendors of small goods and congregate. Interviews here were brief for a different reason. Given the migration status of most, and the fact that they lacked permits to sell their items, participants were wary and watchful for the police.

To help ensure a more robust data set, plans were developed to undertake a phase two of field research, involving a return to West Africa and Europe in the first half of 2020. With the arrival of COVID-19, however, countries shut their borders one after another, restricting mobility as the world felt the shock of a global pandemic on a scale not experienced since 1918 (International Organization for Migration 2021). On 20 March 2020, Australia closed its international borders. Therefore, it became necessary to develop a new strategy. Like other field researchers globally, adopting flexibility in approaches became crucial for research success (Krause et al. 2021).

Researchers increasingly use technological advances, such as mobile applications with messaging capabilities, to support data collection processes and communicate with interview participants (Staudacher and Kaiser-Grolimund 2016; see also O'hara et al. 2014; Kaufmann and Peil 2020). The new strategy for phase two involved the use of social networking applications such as Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter to recruit a local research associate who could help conduct interviews. A participant from the pilot study 2017 research initiative who I first met in Niamey, Niger, from The Gambia, reached out on Twitter, wanting to help. From September to November 2020. The country was a logical choice for phase two, since it is one of the many departure countries and a starting point for countless individuals who begin the dangerous and long trek to Europe (Suso 2019; Filho et al. 2022; Marino et al. 2022).

My research assistant sourced and we interviewed the remaining 28 migrant

participants in The Gambia, primarily through WhatsApp. Participants were all males between the ages of 20 and 30 who had attempted to reach Europe through the Sahara Desert, mainly using Atlantic, West Africa and Western Mediterranean Routes to Spain. All participants in this cohort had returned to The Gambia after being unsuccessful in their objective of reaching Europe.

Phase one interviews were in English. In some instances where I encountered a language barrier, particularly in Niamey, someone in the group would act as a translator. Phase two interviews in The Gambia were in English, and a similar translation from English to the lingua franca of Mandinka and Fulla by my research assistant. For all participants, interview questions were designed to answer the main research questions of this thesis: (1) How do migrants seek to develop and utilise network social capital a) as a survival strategy on high-risk migration routes? b) to facilitate integration into their host society? (2) How does analysing migrants' survival strategy on high-risk migration routes help us better understand states' moves towards increasingly securitised and extended enforcement regimes?

The intention was to avoid inappropriately leading participants in any particular direction and to find out as much about their journey as they were willing to share (Mosely 2013). For the humanitarian sector participants, there was additional interest in finding out how much migrants' experiences and perspectives aligned with those working in the field to support them. Therefore, the questions aimed to elicit as much data as possible about how humanitarian workers respond to the needs of vulnerable migrants in these high-risk migration settings. The complete set of questions prepared for the high-risk migration participant is available in Appendix A. The complete set of questions for the humanitarian sector participants is available in Appendix B.

Throughout these two data collection phases, I gave much thought and reflection to my role as a researcher, as others have done before me (Walford 2002; 2007; see also Easterday 1977; Corbett 1984; Boeckman 2019). It takes time to foster relationships of trust. It takes time to understand the location and terrain in which I operate. In this field research, given the risk factors for migrants noted above, there was a time compression. Something that might take weeks to establish needs to happen in days.

In line with a do-no-harm approach, I was concerned about how migrants would receive a tall white stranger approaching them in the streets. Most I surmised were of questionable formal 'legal' status and would be less than eager to engage with anyone appearing authoritative. I anticipated a general air of mistrust and suspicion to overcome. I tried not to add any undue stress to an already stressful environment. I gave thought to my attire and let individuals approach me. Which most did in the busy areas as many were selling items. I took time to admire displays that inevitably attracted the seller to me, in which a conversation more easily ensued. It was important that the conversations flow naturally and that I came across as amiable, authentic and non-aggressive. At the same time, I balanced this with an acute awareness that my time with any individual was brief. I needed to be mindful of my purpose and extend the conversation as long as possible.

In phase two, it was a little different experience. Here I needed to provide my research assistant with the best support possible remotely, ensuring we got enough participants to create a robust data set and that he also did not put himself in harm's way (Gruber 2020). During this phase, there was a certain frustration of not being 'on the ground'. At the same time, there was an even stronger sense of team accomplishment and personal satisfaction with adapting research approaches to the unfolding real-time

situations. After experiencing phases one and two of the data collection exercises, I fully appreciate and take the role of the researcher even more seriously.

4.3 Data Analysis Methods

This section discusses the methods of analysis used. Multiple strategies were adopted, consistent with best practices for qualitative research (Creswell and Miller 2000; see also Creswell 2016). First was the primary practice, open and axial coding (Weston et al. 2001). The second was triangulating data to reinforce the discussion and implications that are forthcoming in Chapter Six.

The analysis focused on the interviews at the locations visited during data collection phase one and the interviewers' impressions of those conducted remotely during data collection phase two. In addition, coding was conducted on data from the completed interviews. Transcripts were subjected first to open coding to highlight keywords and recurring themes across interviews (Holloway 1997; Neuman 2006; Saldaña 2013; Williams and Moser 2019). Then axial coding was conducted, focused on highlighting connections between themes (Neuman 2006, p. 462). In the axial coding phase, high-risk migration factors and types of network-derived social capital became more apparent and crystallised as high-risk migration patterns. From these patterns emerged the six broad ways in which migrants seek to derive social capital through networks on high-risk routes.

The overarching aim was to provide critical insights into participants' protection strategies developed during their high-risk migration experience—the satisfaction of the aim is with the bulk of testimony from data collection phase two. Comprehensive, fully ethnographic studies involving several weeks or months of observation and engagement

at these three locations were not feasible, given resource and time constraints. At the same time, the investigator's previous experience with the 2017 pilot study at the Niamey location and extensive contract and full-time work on migration issues with the International Organization for Migration (IOM) provided a fundamental background for understanding the context of participant responses.

As noted, the approach to analysis adopted included triangulation of the data. Triangulation is a reliability procedure where researchers search for convergence among multiple sources of information to form themes or categories of information (Creswell and Miller 2000; see also Neuman 2006). Denzin (1978) identifies four triangulation types: across data sources, such as participants— theories, methods, interviews, observations—documents and different investigations. The data triangulation included multiple field entries and speaking with migrants and humanitarian civil servants. It also included cross-checking the findings against other field-based work, inter and non-governmental organisation data, and related accounts of high-risk migration routes.

The analysis here also is informed by IOM's Displacement Tracking Matrix (DTM) survey data. Displacement Tracking Matrix is a four-pillar data collection system focused on the 'mobility, vulnerabilities, and needs of displaced and mobile populations,' used by IOM and other UN entities. It involves migrant mobility tracking, surveys, flow monitoring and registration. Displacement occurs in several events, such as civil conflict, climate-induced and other natural disasters. The design of DTM is critical to responses by a wide range of humanitarian actors, and the data that DTM generates is highly sought after by most government bodies interested in funding emergency responses to displacement. Displacement Tracking Matrix survey datasets were consulted on mixed migration populations flows through West Africa, the Sahara

Desert and Europe (Displacement Tracking Matrix 2019; 2022a; International Organization for Migration 2019c). Relevant publications from IOM and other UN entities, news accounts, policy papers and reports from EU and African Union agencies interested in the high-risk migration routes through the Sahara Desert and the Mediterranean Sea were also consulted.

In terms of data protection, each participant interview is contained within a numbered file and confidentiality is protected. Interviews were recorded with a digital recorder and transcribed verbatim. The interview transcripts and the interview recordings in digital format stored on a password-protected computer. The storage of master copies of the digital research data is on Griffith University systems, specifically the Research Storage and the Research Vault services. Storage of the raw data files is for up to one year after the publication of this thesis, after which the destruction of the raw data files will take place.

4.4 Six Factors in Deriving Social Capital Through Networks During High-Risk Migration

As discussed, the challenges migrants face on high-risk migration routes are enormous. Challenges on the Sahara and North American routes include physical hardships from negotiating harsh desert terrain and conditions to abuse at the hands of authorities and human smugglers (Szabo 2017; see also Cabrera 2010; International Organization for Migration 2020a). The following sub-sections discuss additional factors intensifying risks, including some distinctive Saharan migration dynamics. These six factors include (1) having limited resources, (2) having no contacts at the intended destination, (3) lacking knowledge of migration routes, (4) travelling alone, (5) vulnerability to

authorities and (5) vulnerability to human smugglers and other actors (see figure 4.5). These factors during high-risk migration are often interlinked, as will be evident from statements below. The following subsections discuss each in turn. Each of these factors focuses on migrants' experiences and interpretations of them. It helps to highlight why migrants strive to develop social capital through networks while in transit and at their destination.

4.4.1 Having Limited Resources

Having limited resources to travel these routes is a factor during high-risk migration that motivates migrants to seek to develop social capital. The data shows that all participants travelled with limited resources and had few opportunities to access or generate additional funding in transit. When asked to describe any help received, responses revealed interesting ways migrants received support. Some responded that no one had helped them. Others said their family had given a little money to start. For example, Participant 80, from the Gambia, when asked who had helped said, 'My family, with great difficulty and sacrifice, helped pay for some of my journey' (2 November 2020). And everyone who used smugglers acknowledges that any funds they received primarily were used to gain by sometimes paying an intermediary for the introduction and then to pay the smugglers to help them get to each stage of their journey (here again, showing how interlinked these threats are).

The entire set of participants reported leaving their homes due to the economic hardship of their country and with the belief that if they could only reach Europe, their fortunes would change. The prospect of a better life and a better economic standing

helps incentivise those travelling these routes to find a way to make it. However, most do so with limited funds, increasing their vulnerability.

In many cases, fees for the entire journey are entirely arbitrary, set at the whims of the human smugglers. Migrants along these routes do not pay one price at the start of their journey. Rather migration costs escalate throughout the high-risk migration experience, and debts can accumulate. Having limited resources is thus a particular risk factor. As the journey progresses, it becomes apparent to travellers that more funds are needed to finance the remaining stages of the journey. Human smuggling can quickly turn into human trafficking. According to one humanitarian organisation staff member:

Migrants are at risk of extortion, crime, and abuse. Migrant women and girls are at particular risk of sexual exploitation along the way and once at the destination. Deals are made to repay debt incurred along the route and servitude and slavery is of great concern (Humanitarian sector participant, 7 December 2020).

Exploitation can come in the form of forced prostitution, forced labour and other forms of coercion, fraud, and being paid only subsistence wages. There are reports of people harassing migrants along the way and seeking to take advantage of them in sometimes horrific ways. For example, as one humanitarian sector interviewee noted, 'Along the route a high percentage of travellers are asked for body parts in exchange for money' (13 November 2020). Similarly, in one survey on the prevalence of human trafficking and other exploitive practices along the Central Mediterranean Route, respondents reported instances where traffickers force migrants to give either blood or body parts against their will (International Organization for Migration 2017; 2019d).

By way of context for such risk factors, the International Criminal Police Organization (2021) released a report assessing trafficking in human beings for organ

removal (THBOR). The trade is becoming more lucrative due to a global shortage of organs used in ethical transplants, which creates opportunities for organized crime groups. These groups are involved with medical sector personnel worldwide, including the North and West Africa regions. Those involved connect through transplant tourism, where a buyer, sometimes the patient, travels abroad to buy body parts like kidneys or livers from other countries for an illegal transplant procedure. During high-risk migration, migrants' risk of THBOR is significant (see also Pascalev et al. 2016; United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime 2023).

For this high-risk migration factor, the risks are similar and as significant in the Latin America context. Migration from Central America and Mexico to the United States is particularly violent. An example is the killing of 72 migrants from Brazil, Ecuador and Guatemala in San Fernando, Tamaulipas, in 2010 for resisting to work for a criminal enterprise (Correa-Cabrera 2017).

Overall, then, having limited resources is a critical issue for migrants travelling high-risk migration routes. This threat motivates migrants to try to develop networks and derive social capital from them. Their strategies in this context primarily focus on utilising informal labour networks, as detailed in section 4.5.

4.4.2 Having No Contacts at the Intended Destination

Having no contacts at the intended destination is another factor that motivates the construction of network-derived social capital. One dynamic distinctive to the Saharan routes, or at least one that contrasts with findings reported elsewhere, is that the migrants interviewed had few or typically no friends, relatives or other contacts waiting for them at their intended destination cities in Europe. That is a stark contrast to

findings reported, for example, from the experience of migrants travelling high-risk migration routes from Central America and Mexico to the United States. Migrants travelling in that context seem to have more robust network-derived social capital before leaving their country of origin, during the journey itself and at their destination country (Massey 1986; Massey et al. 1994; Massey et al. 1994; Silva and Massey 2014). For example, family connections between migrants travelling high-risk migration routes from Mexico and those already in the United States provide the most sustaining links to information and resources. According to Massey (1986, p. 104),

To a brother arriving in the United States [from Mexico] without money, job, or documents, there is a series of obligations. A place to stay, help in finding work, a loan of money, and the payment of trip expenses are common ways that fraternal ties are strengthened in the migrant context.

For those travelling high-risk migration routes through the Sahara Desert, not having these established links is a significant liability and a threat to survival. None of the 18 migrants interviewed in Niamey reported having any contacts at their destination before leaving, nor did the 55 participants in Italy. As for the 28 participants from The Gambia, one said he knew someone in Europe, though he did not know where they lived. A second participant said he did have some family in Europe, and they helped him by sending money:

My three brothers, they are already in Europe, in Italy. My plan was to join them. They are not here in the country at that time [before I left]. They help me with some small money (Participant 79, from The Gambia, 31 October 2020).

It could be that the responses in Niger and Italy stemmed from an overall sense of distrust and the personal intrusion by a stranger asking about people they know. Similar responses, though, were garnered through my research assistant in The Gambia,

who had built some level of trust over a more extended period. In searching for an explanation of how most migrants do not have established contacts at their destination, two answers emerge. Most did not know which country they would end up in before they left. A similar dynamic is highlighted by Collyer, who notes of migrants he engaged:

A small number of migrants had family in Europe. They were also the minority of individuals with a clear destination in mind, even from the outset. They reported receiving money from relatives more or less regularly. They were keen to emphasise that they did not receive very much (Collyer 2007, p. 682-683).

There is value in the notion that many migrants travelling these high-risk migration routes through the Sahara Desert mostly do not know anyone in Europe. Having no contacts at the intended destination was reinforced by a few humanitarian experts interviewed, who provided a unique aspect. The idea that those who survive together stay together says one expert:

We get consistent feedback from the interviews we conduct on disembarkation [after rescue at sea] that most do not know anybody along the way or here [Italy]. They didn't know each other until they get into the boat. If they survive the boat, they stay together. Survive together, stay together (Humanitarian sector participant, 21 November 2020).

Having no contacts at the intended destination can increase vulnerabilities and add to threats to basic survival for migrants travelling high-risk migration routes. Migrants attempt to survive often unwelcoming transit destinations such as Algeria or Libya, get into precarious boats, navigate the treacherous Mediterranean Sea and attempt to integrate into their destination country. They lack vital sources of information about routes and modes of travel that those who have gone before could provide. They

lack the ability to gain information about enforcement contexts and developments, and they may make riskier or less informed choices about transit country destinations and possible entry or crossing points. The field work shows that a threat like this motivates migrants on high-risk migration routes to seek to derive social capital through networks. They do so by seeking to form groups, by sticking together when groups are formed, and by pooling their information as they make their way across the desert.

4.4.3 Lacking Knowledge of Migration Routes

Lacking knowledge of migration routes is a further factor motivating social capital development through networks. Some of these factors have similar characteristics depending on the region of the migration routing systems. Most high-risk migration participants lacked knowledge of the routes they would take before starting their journey. Responses ranged from the first attempted journey, ‘No, I never knew the journey before’ (Participant 83, The Gambia, 4 November 2020), to a second or multiple attempts, ‘No and yes. Not before, and yes, I went two times before. I regretted my last journey. The backways change all the time’ (Participant 78, The Gambia, 30 October 2020). Here the participant is referencing the changing aspects of these routes.

To note, names of routes, such as the Central Mediterranean Route, West Africa Route or Western Mediterranean Route, are not one clearly demarcated path. Instead, they are a series of routes that are highly variable, depending on factors such as the existence of enforcement measures or the risk of abuse by authorities, other actors, and border controls. To the question, did you know the route before you left The Gambia? All responded no. When asked how they received information, responses indicated they asked people at each new stop along the way, ‘I stopped in Tripoli, my information is about asking people along the route’ (Participant 92, The Gambia, 15 November 2020).

Another recalls, ‘Our information we used to ask people they will tell you here is good, there is a bad way’ (Participant 93, The Gambia, 16 November 2020). Not knowing the route translates in part to being flexible. As Collyer notes:

For many migrants on these routes their destination is not determined when they leave home, it may change many times during the course of the journey and, whatever it is, they may never get there (Collyer 2007, p. 668; See also Schapendonk 2011).

In the context of Latin America, migration from Central America and Mexico to the United States had historically been more circular. There was a higher rate of crossing and greater knowledge of routes, such that human smugglers, known as *coyotes*, were often by-passed:

Migration is highly circular, and migrants often make regular trips back and forth, often in their own vehicles...Experienced migrants may even guide friends across the border themselves, eliminating border-crossing fees entirely (Massey & España 1987, p. 734).

More recently however, with the hardening securitisation approaches the need for guides or coyotes has increased exponentially (Holmes 2013; Triandafyllidou 2018a; Campos and Cantalapiedra 2022; Timple 2022). Human smuggling is big business and bigger than ever. Globally there are two broad leading categorised routing systems in which human smuggling operations have the highest activity concentration: East, North and West Africa to Europe and Central America and Mexico to the United States. Conservative estimates put revenues over US\$ 6.75 billion and climbing (United Nations Office of Drugs and Crime 2022; see also Greenfield et al. 2019; Raineri 2021).

Routes through the Sahara Desert are ever-changing. It is unlikely that a migrant will know the entire way beforehand, even if they are making a second or third attempt. As a result, information on routes quickly needs to be updated. In many instances, the

direction and destination that someone will attempt depend on the path that is available and accessible. Invariably, these decisions are with the assistance of human smugglers.

Lacking knowledge of migration routes threatens the basic survival of migrants travelling high-risk migration routes. The vast majority found information about their high-risk migration journey from people they met on the journey. Moreover, these sources connected them to smugglers who facilitated different stages of their high-risk migration journey.

4.4.4 Travelling Alone

Travelling alone along these routes is another threat that motivates the construction of network-derived social capital. My research shows that the nationalities interviewed the majority travelled alone, at least initially. Responses were similar: ‘I left home alone, and later I found some other people’s going and we went together’ (Participant 84, The Gambia, 29 September 2020); ‘I travel alone. Soon I meet a group of people in Senegal, I buy a ticket to join them in a car to Mauritania’ (Participant 77, The Gambia, 30 October 2020). One participant describes his experience in more detail:

I left my village alone. Later, I meet a group of peoples at the border between The Gambia and Senegal. I ask them, “Where are you going my friends?” They replay [reply] me that we are going the backway [clandestine] journey (Participant 78, from The Gambia 30 October 2020).

In these responses, it is evident that migrants are travelling alone. The further they move from home, the more likely they need an understanding of the direction. This threat links to the previous lack of knowledge of migration routes in some instances. The further they travel alone, the more vulnerable the situation is for the solo traveller.

From battling the elements to bearing the psychological burden alone is tremendous stress over time. Recounts one participant:

I travel alone for so long. The journey is difficult, and I lose my way. Later, I was in the Sea, leaving from Mauritania for three days with no water and no food. I don't recommend this journey to anyone. These ways destroy my money (Participant 77, The Gambia, 30 October 2020).

The further travelled, the higher the risk. This aspect of travelling alone confirms by data from other scholars in the field, 'Of the 142 migrants interviewed, the huge majority were travelling alone when I interviewed them' (Collyer 2007, p. 668; see also Schapendonk 2011).

Here again, this experience of travelling alone contrasts with the Latin American context, where migration from Central America and Mexico to the United States is an exercise in collective mobility. Migrants travelling those routes do so in large groups, in the form of caravans. As they move through countries along the way, travellers join them. A caravan may start with a handful of fifty migrants from Central America, already a number that far exceeds travellers' experience along the Sahara. Wirt weeks later, it will quickly grow tenfold (Wurtz 2020).

The risks of travelling alone are more significant than travelling with others. The vulnerability to human trafficking is tremendous. The increasing securitisation along these routes and policies designed to impede migration make it necessary to construct alternative travelling methods. The motivation to develop better strategies to protect oneself along these routes is compelling. When travelling alone, a migrant's voice may die in the desert sands. Finding ways to join a group strengthens a migrant's sense of connection, belonging and safety.

4.4.5 Vulnerability to Authorities

Encountering authorities and enforcement measures along these routes is another factor in high-risk migration. Numerous respondents reported facing threats from authorities on the Sahara Desert routes and requiring them to pay them to continue. Said one participant:

I paid the journey through someone who was taking me on the journey. I do not know him. Later I put the rest in my pocket for the police and the armies. They are asking for 15.000 Niger money at each check point. Then I called my father to send me money again. When I reach in Agadez then he sends me 16.000 to pay for the trip to Libya across the Sahara Desert. I paid to the man again in the second capital of Niger where I found numbers of people gathering and waiting for car pick-up from traffickers. I joined in Libya (Participant 78, The Gambia, 30 October 2020).

A (2020) report by the UN Refugee Agency and the Mixed Migration Centre (UNHCR/MMC) at the Danish Refugee Council found that thousands of migrants are abused by authorities and other actors each month on routes between West Africa and the Mediterranean Sea. These include police forces, the military and various security forces, alongside abuses by human smugglers and traffickers. In addition, many of those intercepted in the Mediterranean by Libyan forces face arbitrary detention and abuses while in custody. Furthermore, the data shows that the risk of apprehension by authorities through stringent securitisation mechanisms is high along all routes leading to the EU. Another participant recounts:

I travel from Sierra Leone to Guinea, to Mali, to Niamey and then to Libya. I go through much suffering. In Libya, I spend a month in prison. After, I go to Zawiyah by the seaside. My aim is to reach Europe. I load in the boats. We are caught by Libya Maritime. They take us all to prison. I spend three months. There is so much suffering there. Someone helps me with money to get out. They put me in a truck and send me back to Niamey, (Participant 9, from Sierra Leone, 26 June 2019).

These deterrent enforcement approaches add a layer of vulnerability for migrants in an already high-risk migration scenario. As a result, states increasingly face the dilemma, and tension exists between national self-determination and territorial sovereignty on the one hand and the inherent right of individual self-determination and the right to seek asylum. These individual rights are enshrined in documents such as Article 14 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and Article 1 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and (United Nations 1948; 1966; see also Freeman 1996; Griffiths 2011). Add to these the states' obligations of *non-refoulement* in multiple international human rights instruments,¹⁰ and the pressure for reform of migration processes increases.

There are multiple reasons migrants decide to take high-risk migration routes—conditions in their home country, conflict, economics, or the environment. Underlying the use of these high-risk migration routes are partnerships between states to provide security to prevent people from travelling along them. On the Central Mediterranean Route, for example, there are several enforcement actions by the Coast Guard of Libya to strengthen the integrity of their borders.

On the Atlantic, West Africa and Western Mediterranean Routes to Spain, stringent border enforcement arrangements exist between Algeria and Spain to patrol and prevent crossings. Some examples include the double fence construction along the borders of Ceuta and Melilla and increasing maritime patrols along the Mediterranean Coast and in the Atlantic regarding the Canary Islands (Collyer 2007). In the context of

¹⁰ State obligations of *non-refoulement* are in such instruments as the Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees, Convention Against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment, Convention on the Rights of the Child, the European Convention on Human Rights, amongst others (United Nations 1951; 1984; 1989; Council of Europe 1950).

the COVID-19 pandemic, many people who used to be working in Ceuta found the borders shut.

4.4.6 Vulnerability to Human Smugglers and Other Actors

Closely related risks arise from the necessity to rely on human smugglers, since such reliance often involves extortion or at least depletion of limited resources for migrants. All respondents indicated they had to engage smugglers at some stage of their journey, partly because of the limited knowledge and fluid nature of the routes noted. It was only possible to navigate the way by doing so. Through the interviews, there is a glimpse of how these clandestine human smuggling operations work. By design, facilitators or agents will help a migrant get from point A to point B and not know more beyond that point. At point B, the migrant meets another agent who does not know the previous one and facilitates the journey's next stage. This loose syndicate is a fragmented and compartmentalised web. On the one hand, such a structure intensifies migrant vulnerability partly because families back home have more difficulty monitoring their progress. Recounts one participant:

I pay my journey through someone (smuggler agent) here in The Gambia before I left. Then my parents always come to him and ask where I am now? He said, let's me call my people in Niger. And he called me I will communicate with them. Then I reach Libya and I don't communicate with my family. I used to communicate with them through someone who was responsible for me always (Participant 84, The Gambia, 5 November 2020).

On the other hand, the fragmented nature provides more significant space for a migrant to negotiate terms or even get out of a particularly precarious situation than if this human smuggling enterprise was an organised structure (Mainwaring 2019). In many cases, fees for making the entire journey are entirely arbitrary and at the behest of

the smugglers. Migrants along these routes do not pay one price at the start of their journey. Rather migration costs escalate throughout the high-risk migration experience. Having limited resources is a particular factor that creates indebtedness to smugglers. As the journey progresses, it becomes apparent to travellers that more funds are needed to finance the remaining stages of the journey. Migrants are then at risk of exploitation and abuse. Human smuggling can quickly turn into human trafficking, including through the lure of social networking applications (Calderwood 2018). According to one humanitarian worker:

Migrants are at risk of extortion, crime, and abuse. Migrant women and girls are at particular risk of sexual exploitation along the way and once at the destination. Deals are made to repay debt incurred along the route. Servitude and slavery is of great concern (Humanitarian sector participant, 7 December 2020).

A participant from The Gambia noted the extreme risks to migrants at all stages of the journey, especially from the human smugglers he paid to deliver them across some of the world's harshest terrain:

The most difficult thing is hunger, thieves, hand robbers and difficultly crossing the desert. In one pick up almost 36 people. Some people their legs will break down when walking. They [smugglers] will throw you out of the truck and leave you in the desert. All of this happened on my journey (Participant 90, The Gambia, 11 November 2020).

Closely linked to the limited resources factor, the vulnerability to human smugglers and other actors shows how quickly human smuggling turns into human trafficking. Experiencing any of the factors listed in this section is strong motivation to develop strategies to compensate. The following section will present how migrants strive to do just that.

Figure 4.5 Six Factors in and Six Ways Migrants Are Deriving Social Capital Through Networks During High-Risk Migration

4.5 Six Ways Migrants Derive Social Capital Through Networks During High-Risk Migration

Migrants travelling high-risk migration routes experience factors along the way. As discussed in the previous section, the most common factors include (1) having limited resources, (2) having no contacts at the intended destination, (3) lacking knowledge of the migration routes, (4) travelling alone, (5) vulnerability to authorities and (6) vulnerability to human smugglers. These high-risk migration factors motivate migrants

to develop social capital through networks as a survival strategy. The following sub-sections present how migrants derive this social capital through these networks. These six ways include (1) forming groups, (2) humanitarian organisations, (3) human smugglers, (4) informal labour networks, (5) social networking applications and (7) support of kinship connections.

The data collected and analysed shows that most participants had no well-established network-derived social capital before they started their journey. Instead, most participants constructed their network-derived social capital in stages throughout the journey. Out of the testimony, compelling strategies emerged, such as family members sending money, meeting someone along the way who had connections using their mobile phone, and linking up with someone else who knew how to get through areas certain to be blocked by authorities. The following sub-sections discuss each in turn.

4.5.1 Forming Groups

Forming groups is a crucial and critical self-protection strategy used by migrants travelling on high-risk migration routes. The purpose is twofold. First, it is intended to yield better information on the way ahead. As discussed, few if any know the whole route when they start, or typically which will be their final destination country. The second is as a form of defence against abuse from bandits, law enforcement and even the human smugglers they seek out.

There is a greater sense of belonging and security in groups than in attempting to go it alone. Many started the journey alone and then connected with others they found on the route, 'I left here alone, later I meet many people along the route' (Participant 89,

from The Gambia 11 November 2020). Said another, ‘My information is I meet people along the way, asking for them about the journey’ (Participant 91, The Gambia 13 November 2020). Connecting with others is a way to discover which areas to avoid and where potential trouble may be waiting ahead in its various forms. In this way, developing this network-derived social capital as a protection strategy. Recounts one participant:

I stopped in Libya, in Tripoli. My information is along the route. Some people will explain to you if you go this way, they will shoot you. They will also explain to you this way if you go there, they will sell you. Another way again they will explain to you they will lock you up. (Participant 94, The Gambia, 17 November 2020).

Sometimes there is a free-flowing aspect to these group formations. For example, people meet at one stage, then move off in one direction, and the participant meets up with other groups at the next stage. Sometimes it is groups of two or three travellers until they link up with others at hubs like Agadez, where migrants merge with smugglers, get on trucks, and cross the Sahara Desert to Libya. In all cases, this type of network-derived social capital is an essential survival strategy:

We think many migrants attempt to travel in groups. These networks can be used as a support mechanism throughout the journey, whether it is finding the most appropriate route, needed financial support, and finding out ways to connect with human smugglers (Humanitarian sector participant, 7 December 2020).

4.5.2 Humanitarian Organisations

A second way migrants derive social capital through networks is through their intersecting with humanitarian organisations. Humanitarian organisations are sometimes active in the region, be it with limited resources and capacity. Such groups typically

work hard to do the best possible to reach the migrants they can under increasingly complicated environments. In the end, all participants from The Gambia decided to return home, and a significant number sought and received help from humanitarian organisations. Some interviewees noted the role these organisations played for them:

I feel sad on the journey, because I was in jail in the prison for six months. We were locked up in a town called Zabrata in Libya. They beat us seriously. When we were released, we went to where peoples are always waiting to cross the sea. I was there for a long period. IOM meet me there with a group of people helping people to get back home, then I joined with them. They took us to IOM Libya. They are the ones who helped me reach at home (Participant 78, The Gambia 30 October 2020).

After making it to Algeria with smugglers' help, one group from Liberia spent some time working as labourers to pay for the next leg of their journey. All were arrested and deported by the authorities. They attempted to find their way back through the desert and try another route to Libya. They did not have the help of smugglers this time and did not find their way. In the end, they decided to return home with the service of humanitarian organisations. Said one participant:

I spent seven months in Algeria and then got kicked out. We tried to find another way to Libya. The desert is very difficult though. We get lost. We then find our way back to Agadez. In Agadez we find UN to help us go to Niamey. Now I want to go home (Participant 1, Niamey, Niger, 25 June 2019).

Migrants access humanitarian organisations as a source to help with returning home, a resource discovered along the way, or the critical stage of rescue from the desert with government authorities' assistance. However, most participants contacted at the field sites were unaware that there were any humanitarian organisations around. Some participants confused the names of organisations or referred to all of them as UN.

Some mistook the humanitarian organisation's role in their journey, for example, thinking that the humanitarian organisation had jurisdiction over detention: 'We were locked down. Later UN meet us in the prison and unlock us. Later they sent us back to Niger' (Participant 100, The Gambia 23, November 2020). While they may have confused these organisations' roles, the impression was that migrants were thankful to have found some access to such a form of network-derived social capital.

Organisation staff detailed sometimes intensive efforts to find and aid migrants on the high-risk routes. Said one:

Volunteers and humanitarian workers often follow some of the migrants they encounter. It is better this way than staying stationary and missing so many. If we travel with migrants, we can better provide support and, we can report any incidents encountered along the route. We can provide advocacy. We do our best to protect (Humanitarian sector participant, 18 November 2020).

Overall, humanitarian organisations can be seen to constitute a network inclusive of migrants, from which they seek to derive social capital. Given the relatively hierarchical nature of the networks, they might best be described as ones providing access to linking social capital.

4.5.3. Human Smugglers

The third type of network-derived social capital from the interviews involved the use of human smugglers – offering a more rigidly hierarchical form of linking social capital. This type of network-derived social capital is the one that migrants most construct on these high-risk migration routes. Migrants typically utilise smugglers hoping to reduce costs and risk. Yet, the use of human smuggling networks can represent the type of network-derived social capital that costs the most and is often the riskiest for the

traveller, 'My most difficult thing is all about money. The money is now my problem. The money I paid to smugglers' (Participant 99, The Gambia, 22 November 2020). Recounts another participant:

I paid the journey through someone who was taking me on the journey. When I reach Agadez I paid to the man again for the trip to Libya to cross the Sahara Desert. (Participant 78, The Gambia 30 October 2020).

Human smugglers constitute a significant source of information. These operations' fragmented and hidden nature means that migrants travel in stages. Information and payments are made only to get to the next stage. These are independent operators until crossing the Sahara Desert or the Mediterranean Sea, where it is more of an organised effort (Hamood 2006; see also Collyer et al. 2012; Campana and Gelsthrope 2020; Mixed Migration Centre 2021). The cost to the migrant can be extreme, and the danger they have placed themselves at this phase of the crossing is acute.

Along the route, when the money runs out as it often does, migrants seek another type of network-derived social capital to help. Some seek employment in the form of labouring. When asked who helped you? All 18 responded smugglers. When asked how you found help? A typical response was, 'Someone knows someone' and 'During travel', as in along the way. When asked how they found their way, the majority responded that they would talk to people in the area at each stage of their journey and find out information about the next step. In data collection phase two, the discovery was that information knowledge, and sharing fragmentation is mainly human smugglers' design.

4.5.4 Informal Labour Networks

Many of the respondents in phase two indicated that they paid for their journey to find employment through labour at various stages along the way. Some were spending a significant amount of time in locations attempting to move to the following location on their journey. A participant recounts in-depth his experience:

When I am going, I was having 15.000 CFA [West African CFA Franc]. When that money finished, I worked in Bamako [Mali] then I got that money to pass to Agadez [Niger]. I work again to get some money to pass into Algeria from a small village called Assamakka [Niger] then from there we join in a pickup going to Tamanrasset [Algeria]. Then from there to Ghardaia [Algeria]. Then from there we went to Oran [Algeria]. Then from there we went to Maghnia [Algeria] between Algeria and Morocco border. I work there for one year five months. I send money to my family in The Gambia. After all that I pass to Morocco, a town called Oujda [Morocco] then from there I pass to Fez [Morocco], then from there to Rabat [Morocco]. I spend almost one year there working. After that I went with a group of people's going to Nador [Morocco], that is the last town in Morocco where people are crossing the [Mediterranean] Sea [to Spain]. I stop there (Participant 87, The Gambia, 9 November 2020).

Regarding the types of labour migrants engaged in, some spoke of finding odd jobs and the shady nature of the employment. One participant describes it thus:

Nobody didn't help me. I work and I pass [to the next location]. In Libya I worked cement and building construction I get money. Sometimes they didn't pay me (Participant 89, The Gambia, 11 November 2020).

In terms of the type of work found, when asked what he did for work, one participant recounts how he went about it:

Yes, I work as a labour for construction. I find this work outside buildings [under construction]. Sometimes they [foremen] will come out and ask who wants to work. Many of us do work this way. Sometimes I do work by cleaning some compound in Tripoli [Libya]. I also worked in Ouagadougou [Burkina Faso] again for construction. Yes, they pay

me at the time. I never got trouble getting paid (Participant 94, The Gambia, 17 November 2020).

While another participant highlights the grave risk of exploitation associated with and how quickly these relationships can turn to human trafficking:

They can find people for work. Sometimes I will go outside and search for work by sitting near the route. Yes, sometimes they will pay you and sometimes I have trouble getting paid because sometimes they will not pay you and you cannot do them nothing. If you talk too much, they will shoot you or they will sell you to another person (Participant 96, The Gambia, 20 November 2020).

Migrants found employment in labour which links to other types of network-derived social capital on these high-risk migration routes. Finding information on labour through forming groups and working to further establish access to human smugglers. A participant's testimony:

I travel to Mauritania. I then find work there. I find out from people on the bus. Later I paid for Algeria again. I worked there for a long time and find someone who takes me away to the Sahara Desert (Participant 75, The Gambia, 20 October 2020).

These interviews show how vital this network-derived social capital is for migrants travelling on high-risk migration routes and how it links to other types discussed in this section.

4.5.5 Social Networking Applications

All participants indicated having received assistance from smugglers. When asked, how did you find your help? A typical response was, 'At each place along the way', or no answer. Moreover, 'I use my phone and WhatsApp or Facebook'. Many of the participants I spoke to carried two mobile phones. One of the questions is explicit, do

you have a mobile phone? Which was followed by how many? In case they lose one, they will still have another to help find their way and in case of needing rescue.

Something human smugglers and traffickers are aware of, one participant divulges:

Yes, I have [a mobile phone] at this time. When going in the desert, they [smugglers] will not allow you to have a phone. I hide one. (Participant 83, The Gambia, 4 November 2020).

A second type of network-derived social capital to come out of the interviews was participants' use of social networking applications, such as WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter and other communication platforms. These applications help to communicate with others, 'I communicate with my family through my phone and my friends in Europe and Libya, also here in The Gambia' (Participant 89, The Gambia 11, November 2020). In addition, social networking applications help migrants connect with human smugglers known to advertise on various platforms, find information on migration routes, provide GPS location assistance, and receive money from friends or family (Schapendonk and van Moppes 2007; see also Dekker and Engbersen 2014; Regional Mixed Migration Secretariat 2016; Dekker and Engbersen 2018; Campana 2020). Verifies one participant, 'I used my phone for communication with my father to send money to me' (Participant 90, The Gambia, 11 November 2020). This type of network-derived social capital is a crucial element for many in helping navigates the journey. When I asked how they found their way, in one particularly revealing testimony from a participant, 'I have information through social media. I use Facebook and WhatsApp. Facebook showed me places, WhatsApp I was given [contact] numbers' (Participant 97, The Gambia 20 November 2020).

Social networking applications are critical in a migrant's survival strategy while in transit on these high-risk migration routes. This can help to overcome problems

related to fragmented information, including about contacting smuggling syndicates. As one humanitarian sector participant noted:

Social media as a network is used much when the journey is being conceived. Facebook, Twitter where offers are being posted by smugglers including prices for packages for crossing into one or multiple countries. Those social networking applications are extensively used. Using these apps, like WhatsApp too, migrants send their location if they are distressed at sea in hopes of being rescued. Also used in transit to seek out others of similar nationalities to link up with for support and information (Humanitarian sector participant, 18 November 2020).

Another observed of interactions with smugglers:

In the Sahara, migrants use a lot of social networking [apps] when they are on the move. The human smuggling environment is more like a loose syndicate. Migrants must pay. These routes are then only exposed once you pay. Therefore, the routes are not easily available in the beginning. As the routes continue to change, they also can remain hidden. Once you pay a section is revealed (Humanitarian sector participant, 13 November 2020).

4.5.6 Support of Kinship Connections

Another type of network-derived social capital from the interviews was the notion of kinships that some participants draw on to support their efforts when possible. At the same time, the support from kinship connections is not as strong as the kinship connections for migrants on the Central America and Mexico routes to the United States. Nevertheless, it is still a type of network-derived social capital on these routes. Responses to those who helped included family in the form of funds, ‘They give me money for some of my journey’ (Participant 76, The Gambia 30 October 2020). Family members also give moral support. Said one participant:

My father helps me. I told him I want to leave the country for more than three times. He doesn’t allow me. Later he said yes. This is your final

journey my Son. Have a safe journey (Participant 78, The Gambia, 30 October 2020).

When it comes to family sending money along the way, the most common and fastest way was through Western Union. Most times, it transfers were given when participants ran out of money and were in trouble, typically when they owed money to smugglers or needed more money to finance more of the journey. An example demonstrates how two types of network-derived social capital, in this case, support from kinship connections using human smugglers, sometimes intersect and become linked on these high-risk journeys. The response of one participant:

I stop for a time because my money got finished. I got one person who was responsible for me until I called my family again to sell one cow for me. I called them through that smuggler there because I don't have a phone number at that time. My family send me almost 20,000 Niger money to pay the car. I don't receive the money myself. It's the man [smuggler] who received the money. Later he called my name, "Tomorrow you are going to Libya because your family send me the money". I tell him ok them for me. Then he called them for me. They explain to me everything that they paid the money to him (Participant 80, The Gambia, 2 November 2020).

Migrants thus seek to make use of existing kinship networks while in-transit, seeking to derive forms of bonding social capital from them.

4.6 Conclusion

This chapter presented the results of the data collection exercise in regard to transit on high-risk routes. Phase one occurred in three locations: Niamey, Niger, Rome and Milan, Italy. At these locations, interventions with migrants were in public spaces, including train stations, on the streets and in high foot traffic areas. During phase two, interviews were remote with the help of a research assistant on the ground in The

Gambia. In addition, interviews were conducted remotely with members of the humanitarian sector representing interests from NGOs and international organisations within the UN system. As a result, the data set includes interviews with 101 high-risk migration participants and 16 humanitarian sector participants.

The chapter then discussed the methods of analysis employed: a multi-pronged strategy including open and axial coding and data triangulation to reinforce learning. From this analysis, themes emerged that were divided into two categories—the first category factors in deriving social capital through networks during high-risk migration. There were six, including (1) having limited resources, (2) having no contacts at the intended destination, (3) lacking knowledge of migration routes, (4) travelling alone, (5) vulnerability to authorities and (6) vulnerability to human smugglers and other actors.

The second category included the types of network-derived social capital that participants developed. These six types included (1) forming groups, (2) humanitarian organisations, (3) human smugglers, (4) informal labour networks, (5) social networking applications and (6) support of kinship connections. Again, the data reinforces how dangerous and vulnerable the experiences are. Migrants use this network-derived social capital as part of their survival strategy. What is happening is that migrants often find themselves in even more precarious circumstances, especially when engaging human smugglers.

One thing that ties together the factors and the types of network-derived social capital is information: migrants start with an information deficit. Nevertheless, knowledge is the key to survival -- knowledge about the routes, the smugglers, the authorities, the humanitarian organisations, and about needing two mobile phones. The results, as presented here, go a long way toward answering the first research question:

How do migrants seek to develop and utilise network social capital as a survival strategy on high-risk migration routes? Chapter Five adds to the discussion by examining how migrants seek to use network-derived social capital from their in-transit experience on high-risk migration routes to aid integration in destination countries.

Chapter Five

Network-Derived Social Capital and Migrant Integration in the European Union

5.1 Introduction

5.2 Migrant Integration in the European Union

5.2.1 Common European Asylum System

5.2.2 Europeanisation of Migrant Integration

5.3 Member State Enforcement and Migrant Integration (Italy)

5.3.1 Asylum Procedures

5.3.2 Reception and Detention Systems

5.4 Anti-Migrant Rhetoric: A Barrier to Migrant Integration

5.5 Network-Derived Social Capital: An Integration Survival Strategy

5.6 Conclusion

5.1 Introduction

This chapter focuses on how migrants seek to extend their network-derived social capital from their high-risk migration experience and create new threads to facilitate their integration and survival in their destination country and host community. Woven within the six ways migrants derive network social capital, first introduced in Chapter Four, are the elements of bonding, bridging and linking. This chapter aims to give insight into processes of migrant integration within a context of securitised migration by examining three groupings of migrants: those who apply for asylum, those who are not eligible for asylum and those awaiting a decision on their claim or appeals against a rejection. There is a fourth grouping of migrants, those not in the asylum system at all, who are in the most precarious position within the EU, as they lack access to support services and state protections. As in Chapter Four, the discussion here will highlight some factors driving migrants to maintain and further develop social capital networks as a security strategy in receiving locales. The forthcoming sections focus on three factors that increase risks during integration processes: having no contacts at the intended destination, having limited resources and vulnerability to authorities and human smugglers. The discussion will highlight how these factors lead migrants to exercise various significant forms of agency, including seeking to derive network social capital – bonding and bridging -- through developing and maintaining tightly knit groups, some of which are an extension of the groups formed on their Sahara journey. They also seek to use information and services provided by humanitarian organisations, representing linking social capital.

The chapter thus offers an analysis of the Milan and Rome portion of the phase one fieldwork, using the data from interviews with migrants in these cities and the

humanitarian sector participants. In addition, it draws on scholarship on migrant integration and other studies on migrant experiences in EU destination countries to contextualise the findings. Finally, significant attention is devoted in the chapter to EU migration and asylum regimes, and ways in which they have become increasingly stringent and exclusionary. These systems are influenced by the ongoing securitisation of migration, or an anti-migrant rhetoric cycle foregrounded within Member States. Analysis of such cycles in the chapter highlights how migrants who have navigated the dangers of the high-risk Sahara routes may still be at risk in receiving countries and cities. In response, migrants adopt specific protective strategies.

The chapter is structured as follows. First, some background is offered on the Common European Asylum System, which does much to determine formal structures. Second, it examines attempts at the supranational level to ‘Europeanise’ migrant integration, or develop common principles and processes, and how Member States generally resist such efforts. Third, using Italy as a case study, a review is offered of asylum procedures. That is followed by details on reception and detention systems features that highlight increasingly restrictive migration policies reflecting the securitised aspects of migrant integration. Fourth, it is highlighted how political elites’ anti-migrant rhetoric contributes to an overall hostile context, may increase risks, and generally exacerbates the multi-faceted challenges migrants face in their attempts to integrate into their destination country. Fifth, political elites are shown to leverage media influence as part of a political strategy to shape public opinion and implement policies that create barriers to integration for migrants. The strands of the analysis are tied together in the sixth section, which explores how, in the face of such pressures against migrant integration, migrants exercise sophisticated and varied forms agency by

extending, forming, or reinforcing existing groups, deriving bonding and bridging capital from them, and accessing humanitarian organisations' services as linking capital.

In summary, Chapter Four discussed how the EU's increasingly hardened external borders and extraterritorial enforcement efforts motivate migrants on high-risk migration through Sahara to adopt specific strategies to derive network-social capital. This chapter focuses on migrant integration in a context of more stringent internal enforcement and extensive efforts by political elites to frame migration as a pressing security threat. It examines specific pressures this poses on migrants, which, along with the factors highlighted that are specific to many migrants -- having no contacts, limited resources, and being vulnerable to authorities and human smugglers -- drive social capital strategies at receiving sites.

5.2 Migrant Integration in the European Union

This section introduces the European asylum system and briefly discusses attempts at *Europeanisation* of migrant integration. A definition of *Europeanisation*: the process of influence stemming from European decisions and impacting Member States' policies and political administrative structures (Héritier et al. 2001, p. 3; see also Ladrech 1994; Risse et al. 2001; Radaelli 2003; Lenschow 2006; Graziano and Vink 2007; Ladrech 2010; Exadaktylos et al. 2020).

When it comes to migration, Europeanisation efforts face continuous obfuscation and rejection by Member States. Member States generally opt instead for a nationalised migration regime, with some adopting largely restrictive policies on migrant integration. These restrictive measures reflect the increasing securitisation of migration and the exclusionary nature of the integration experience. They contribute

significantly instead to migrants' adoption of the network social capital development strategies examined.

Chapter Three introduced how political elites within EU Member States have increasingly framed migration as a security issue, and how migration enforcement has been extraterritorialised. The EU and Member States extend enforcement borders through cooperative security agreements and providing funding to countries in North and West Africa. The aim is to curb migration flows and prevent migrants from reaching EU external borders. Extraterritorial as it relates to processes of transferring or delegating tasks related to migration control to third countries and the externalisation of migration governance or policies (Lemberg-Pedersen 2018; Crisp 2022; International Migration Research Network 2022).

Externalisation of migration control to third countries occurs at multi- and bi-lateral levels (Haastrup et al. 2020; Ambrosini and Hajer 2023). The framing of migration as a security issue is understood here as securitisation: a process of social construction that pushes an area of regular politics into a place of security by resorting to a rhetoric of threat and danger aimed at justifying the adoption of exceptional measures (Wæver 1993; Wæver 1996). Chapter Three looked at such processes in the context of EU external borders. This chapter develops the conceptualisation further and looks within the EU borders.

Numerous migration events have profoundly influenced European debates about migration recently, with the most dramatic being the increase in arrivals in 2015, discussed earlier. During that year, DTM recorded 1,046,599 migrants arriving in the EU, compared to 283,532 arrivals in 2014 (Displacement Tracking Matrix 2015; Council of the European Union 2022a). The sheer number and compressed time frame

of the increase drove an increased atmosphere of security. An example of the types of securitised response was on 14 September 2015, Hungary completed the construction of a fence on its border with Serbia to stop migration flows along the Balkan routes (Displacement Tracking Matrix 2015; Bello 2022a).

In addition, there were other effects and a general rejection in many Member States of EU policies, from burden sharing in the form of relocating asylum seekers to relieve pressure from frontline receiving countries like Greece, Italy and Spain, to rejection of policies fostering multiculturalism (Mulcahy 2009; Geddes and Scholten 2015; Geddes et al. 2020). To some, there has been a reframing of national policies aimed at further alienating newly arrived migrants through such tools as citizenship and language tests (Vertovec and Wessendorf 2010; Wodak 2015; Boulila, 2019).

Details on principles and policies related to the movement of persons more generally in the EU should be useful here. For example, the 1986 Single Europe Act outlined commitments to principles of freedom of movement within EU territory and removing borders between the Member States. It is the fundamental idea of the EU experiment (European Union 1986; Huysmans 2000). EU citizenship was formalised and free movement rights were extended in the Treaty of Maastricht, which took effect in 1993 and fully visa-free travel has emerged within the 26-country Schengen Area. Each such development arguably is in tension with the management of significant migration events in recent years when some Member States have taken steps to re-impose some border controls. That is, there are provisions in the application of Schengen *Acquis* to trigger the resumption of internal border checks should it be deemed in the interest of national security to do so (European Union 1986; Hanke et al. 2019; European Commission 2020d). This occurred in 2015 when Austria, Germany,

Hungary, and others reintroduced internal border checks in another effort to stop migration flows or at least significantly slow onward mobility (Szakacs and Zuvela 2015; Geddes et al. 2020).

These actions reinforce how migration and migrant integration within the EU are increasingly viewed predominantly through a security lens. I also note here the Schengen Information System, a database designed to verify a third-country national's 'right' to be in the Schengen area (European Commission 2015c; 2018c). These moves by the EU help show the securitised environment migrants are navigating and begin laying the groundwork to explore how migrants respond.

As a further example, by the EU's estimates, only 10 per cent of those who receive refugee status in the EU arrived by non-clandestine means (European Union Agency for Asylum 2021). This is potentially a crucial insight that, taken alone, presupposes a link between securitisation and high-risk migration. The premise is that clandestine entry would reduce if there were safer migration pathways. The lack of data highlights the need for further investigation to demonstrate whether a decrease or increase in asylum applications links to securitised EU migration policy.

The European Parliament (2016a) has made safer migration proposals by wanting to issue humanitarian visas in origin and transit countries to third-country nationals seeking international protection in a Member State. The other EU institutions of, the European Commission and the European Council, have soundly blocked these types of reforms. Regarding EU jurisprudence and court challenges in 2017, the EU judicial arm, the Court of Justice of the European Union, ruled in *X and X v État belge* that Member States have no obligation to do so under EU law (Court of Justice of the European Union 2017a; Cheung and Delfabbro; European Parliament 2018).

Providing a microcosm of the adversarial nature and competing agendas in EU governance (Silvestre 2022; see also Panke 2012; Warntjen 2017). In summary, the migration events, such as those of 2015 and subsequent responses by the EU at the supranational and Member State level, provide some context to understanding why migrants strive to develop networks in the ways that subsequent sections in this chapter describe.

5.2.1 Common European Asylum System

Some basic details on the EU asylum system will help to put its migration and asylum regimes in context, highlight how they have developed and the challenges they can pose to forms of integration. At the supranational level, several key institutions make up the governance structure of the EU. The first is the European Parliament which has evolved to exercise some significant powers to co-decide legislation with the Council of the European Union (Council of Ministers), composed of Member State cabinet members jointly addressing issues in their assigned portfolios. The 705 Members of the European Parliament serve a five-year term. They are elected directly by the citizenry of the 27 Member States, with seats allocated by population size (European Parliament 2021a).

Another key institution is the European Commission, composed of permanent delegates sent by each Member State who similarly serve for a five-year term. The European Commission draws up legislative proposals, implements its decisions and enforces EU law. The Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) is the judicial arm of the EU, which interprets EU law through its two courts, the European Court of Justice and General Court (Court of Justice of the European Union 2021a; see also

Innes 2015; International Association of Refugee Law Judges 2016). Finally, the European Council (EU CO) is comprised of the heads of government of each Member State. It typically sets the political agenda for the EU (see figure 5.1).

The Common European Asylum System is situated within this governance structure. The CEAS provides common standards and designs to the EU asylum framework and seeks to foster cooperation between each Member State. The Asylum Procedure Directive establishes the conditions for asylum decisions within the CEAS. The Reception Conditions Directive specifies common standards for reception conditions, and the Qualification Directive supports access to integration measures for asylum seekers who receive international protection. In addition, the Dublin Regulation (Dublin), covering EU Member States and four other European countries¹¹, determines where asylum claims will be processed. Dublin came into force with a series of regulations created in the form of Dublin through the Convention of 1990, the Dublin II Regulation of 2003 and the Dublin III Regulation of 2013 (European Parliament 2011). In addition, the European Asylum Dactyloscopy Database (EURODAC), mentioned in Chapter Three, allows law enforcement to access the EU's fingerprint database as part of the security screening of applicants (see table 5.1).

¹¹ The Dublin regulation covers EU Member States and four other European countries, Iceland, the Principality of Liechtenstein, Norway and Switzerland.

Figure 5.1 Where Migration Fits in the EU Governance Structure

Sources: Adapted from Humanitarian Designers 2021; see also European Commission 2018d; European Parliament 2021a; Council of the European Union 2022b; Court of Justice of the European Union 2022b.

Finally, the European Union Agency for Asylum (EUAA), which is under the jurisdiction of Justice and Home Affairs (JHA), is composed of the Justice and Home Affairs ministers of all EU Member States.¹² The EUAA provides operational support to each Member State and is responsible for the overall implementation of the CEAS

Table 5.1 Common European Asylum System Instruments

Temporary Protection Directive, 2001
This directive establishes minimum standards for giving temporary protection in the event of a mass influx of displaced persons and on measures promoting a balance of efforts between Member States in receiving such persons and bearing the consequences thereof.
Commission Regulation, 2003
This regulation establishes detailed rules for the implementation of ‘Dublin’.
Qualification Directive, 2011
This directive establishes standards for the qualification of third-country nationals or stateless persons as beneficiaries of international protection (recast).
Asylum Procedures Directive, 2013
This directive establishes common procedures for granting and withdrawing international protection (recast).
Dublin III Regulation, 2013
This regulation establishes the criteria and mechanisms for determining the Member State responsible for examining an application for international protection (recast).
Eurodac Regulation, 2013
This regulation establishes ‘Eurodac’ to compare biometric data for the practical application of asylum and migration and the resettlement regulation (recast).
Reception Conditions Directive, 2013
This directive establishes standards for the reception of applicants for international protection (recast).

Sources: Council of the European Union 2001; European Commission 2003; 2020c; European Parliament 2011; 2013a; 2013b; 2013c; 2013d.

¹² There are nine agencies included in the JHA network, European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Training (CEPOL), European Union Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE), European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction (EMCDDA), EUAA, European Agency for the Operational Management of Large-Scale IT Systems in the Area of Freedom, Security and Justice (eu-LISA), European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation (EUROPOL), European Union Agency for Criminal Justice Cooperation (Eurojust), European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA) and FRONTEX. All have rotating hosting of the network. The hosting agency reports to the Council’s Standing Committee on Operational Cooperation on Internal Security (COSI) (European Union Justice and Home Affairs 2019).

(European Parliament 2018). According to the EUAA, in 2021, there were 617,800 asylum applications made in the EU+ countries¹³. Also, in 2021 of the decisions made on 523,000 applications, 35 per cent were granted two forms of protection: refugee status (117,500 persons), and subsidiary protection (63,000 persons) (European Union Agency for Asylum 2021). The major countries of origin of applicants were Afghanistan, Iraq, Pakistan, Syria and Turkey¹⁴.

Before authorities process an asylum application, they decide through Dublin which Member State is responsible. This determination has four criteria, from most important to least important. The first is if a family member has already been granted protection in a particular Member State or already has an asylum application under consideration. Both the family member and the new applicant must agree to reunification. In this case, the Member State where the family member resides becomes the responsible country. Second is the Member State, which may have granted the applicant a visa, which holds weight regarding location. Third is the Member State which first recorded an applicant's fingerprints. Fourth is the Member State of their first arrival or where an applicant may have transferred to even if fingerprints are recorded in a different Member State (see table 5.2).

The CEAS has attracted criticism. Much of it centres around contentions that the Dublin process is unfair and at odds with common standards of reciprocity among Member States that the system purports to champion. Also, the Dublin criteria have family reunification as its top indicator, yet migrants' transfers based on family

¹³ EU+ includes the 27 EU Member States, plus Norway and Switzerland. Norway is part of the European Economic Area (EEA), which also consists of the 27 EU Member States plus Iceland and Liechtenstein. Switzerland is part of the European Single Market through a bilateral treaty. The European Single Market includes the EU Member States and the EEA (European Union Agency for Asylum 2021).

¹⁴ Applications made by nationals of the same country of origin as my dataset participants are combined in the 'other' category.

reunification are rare in practice. Instead, many migrants seek to create network-derived social capital independent of Dublin. Rather than apply for asylum in the Member State of their first arrival, which is often Greece, Italy, or Spain, many prefer to move on to other areas of the EU (European Parliament 2015a; Loschi & Slominski 2021; European Asylum Support Office 2021). So long as asylum processes vary widely by Member State, attempts at Europeanisation will continue to falter. The following section looks closer at the Europeanisation of migrant integration.

Table 5.2 Hierarchy of Criteria for Determining the Member State Responsible (Dublin III)

Minors (Article 8)

Where the applicant is an unaccompanied minor, the Member State responsible shall be that where a family member or a sibling of the unaccompanied minor is legally present, provided that it is in the best interests of the minor.

Family members who are beneficiaries of international protection (Article 9)

Where the applicant has a family member, regardless of whether the family member was previously formed in the country of origin, who has been allowed to reside as a beneficiary of international protection in a Member State, that Member State shall be responsible for examining the application for international protection, provided that the persons concerned expressed their desire in writing.

Family members who are applicants for international protection (Article 10)

If the applicant has a family member in a Member State whose application for international protection in that Member State has not yet been the subject of a first decision regarding the substance, that Member State shall be responsible for examining the application for international protection, provided that the persons concerned expressed their desire in writing.

Family procedure (Article 11)

Where several family members and/or minor unmarried siblings submit applications for international protection in the same Member State simultaneously, or on dates close enough for the procedures for determining the Member State responsible to be conducted together, and where the application of the criteria set out in this Regulation would lead to their being separated, the Member State responsible shall be the one taking charge of the largest number of them and failing this, responsibility shall lie with the Member State responsible for examining the application of the oldest of them.

Issue of residence documents or visa (Article 12)

Where the applicant is in possession of a valid residence document, the Member State which issued the document shall be responsible for examining the application for international protection.

Entry and/or stay (Article 13)

Where it is established, on the basis of proof or circumstantial evidence that an applicant has irregularly crossed the border into a Member State by land, sea or air having come from a third country, the Member State thus entered shall be responsible for examining the application for international protection. That responsibility shall cease 12 months after the date on which the irregular border crossing took place.

Visa waived entry (Article 14)

If a third-country national or a stateless person enters into the territory of a Member State in which the need for him or her to have a visa is waived, that Member State shall be responsible for examining his or her application for international protection.

Application in an international transit area of an airport (Article 15)

Where the application for international protection is made in the international transit area of an airport of a Member State by a third-country national or a stateless person, that Member State shall be responsible for examining the application.

Source: European Parliament 2013c.

5.2.2 Europeanisation of Migrant Integration

Proponents of strengthening migrant integration policies at the supernational level point to mismanagement of state borders, deaths of migrants at sea and bureaucratic limbo of the asylum procedures in CEAS. In many Member States, however, there is a rejection of migrant integration policies, based in part on a rejection of multiculturalism seen as directed by Brussels, the epicentre of EU power. While resistance to Brussels extends beyond migration issues, migration is undoubtedly one of the flashpoints. The Treaty on European Union (1992), Article 6, sec 3 states, ‘The Union shall respect the national identities of its Member States’ – a principle many interpret as an explicit acknowledgement of the importance of Member State authority, including in relation to migration and migrant integration (Mulcahy 2009; Vertovec and Wessendorf 2009; Geddes and Scholten 2015; Geddes et al. 2020).

From the perspective of the Justice and Home Affairs Council (JHAC), a body or configuration of the Council of the European Union featuring Member State ministers of justice, a Europeanised migrant integration policy will benefit Member States and European society overall. The JHAC issued a non-binding set of 11 Common Basic Principles for Immigrant Integration Policy in the European Union (Council of the European Union 2004). Principle One, for example, states that:

Integration is a dynamic, long-term, and continuous two-way process of mutual accommodation, not a static outcome. It demands the participation [of migrants] and their descendants [and] of every resident. The integration process involves adaptation by immigrants, both men and women, who all have rights and responsibilities in relation to their new country of residence. It also involves the receiving society, which should create the opportunities for the immigrants’ full economic, social, cultural, and political participation. Accordingly, Member States are encouraged to consider and involve both immigrants and national citizens in integration policy, and to communicate clearly their mutual rights and responsibilities.

With cultural diversity framed as an asset, Member States and their citizens are encouraged to accommodate and incorporate migrants as full members of society. The principles also encourage Member States to embrace a more expansive view of migration as a benefit and make available resources and urban life fully accessible. Principle seven, for example, supports a greater frequency of interaction between citizens and migrants, while principle eight promotes enhanced dialogue in line with the guarantee of cultural diversity under the Charter of Fundamental Rights (European Union 2000a; Council of the European Union 2004). The impetus, therefore, is for a comprehensive policy where migrant integration is a mutual responsibility of migrants and residents. Migrant integration is respect for EU fundamental values. Employment is an essential component of integration, and the participation of migrants in the labour market is a visible contribution. A rudimentary knowledge of host countries' history, structures and language is essential. Education is a formidable way to prepare better migrants and their children for a more successful integration experience (Vertovec and Wessendorf 2009).

Accordingly, these principles promote equal access to private and public economic consumption as a citizen's right, an essential pillar of migrant integration. Inter-cultural dialogue and frequent interaction between migrants and Member States' citizens are crucial indicators for the integration experience. The Charter's protection of cultural and religious diversity is framed as inviolate (European Union 2000a). Member States are responsible for safeguarding this right in concert with other European rights and national law. Participatory democracy in developing integration policies for migrants at the local level enhances integration. Embedding migrant integration policies in ministerial portfolios and multi-level governance is essential when forming public

policy. Developing healthy, transparent evaluation and monitoring processes supports the necessary evolution of integration policies (Council of the European Union 2004).

Because the principles are non-binding, Member States have tended to adopt looser interpretations of them or, in many cases, ignore them entirely. Numerous Member States have introduced more restrictive controls on migrant integration, meaning that asylum seekers face restricted access to labour markets, issues with recognition of qualifications, language barriers and lengthy procedures. Further, national models requiring language and citizenship tests for migrants make integration much more complicated. While Member States are burdened or responsible for providing basic needs regarding accommodation, health, education and jobs, observers have identified significant gaps in provision. Thus, many asylum seekers opt for employment in the informal sector, where they often face exploitation and discrimination (Şahin-Mencütek et al. 2021; see also Kaczmarczyk et al. 2015). Additionally, there are multiple and confusing procedures for the integration of refugees. The governance system is fragmented, again leading many migrants to opt-out and go alone instead (Geddes and Scholten 2015; Fontana 2021).

Multinational NGOs have lobbied for more significant supranational influence on migrant integration. They emphasise links between successful integration policies and economic and social cohesion (Rosenow 2009). The emergence of even a fractured migrant integration policy agenda may contribute to these efforts in the face of national hesitations. NGOs and other civil society actors play a significant role in attempting to provide services and strengthen the belonging of migrants in host cities where the CEAS is a more cohesive set of instruments. Member States, however, have been reluctant to cede power, especially regarding the governance of entrance and staying in

their territory. Certainly, populist parties on the right use this relationship as part of their anti-migrant rhetoric and to promote national sovereignty over being ruled by Brussels. The cost to these NGOs by national legislatures is described further in the next section as part of the most significant barrier to migrant integration, anti-migrant rhetoric, and Member State enforcement of migrant integration (Geddes 2008; Urso 2018; Kirchick 2019).

In sum, rather than Member States coalescing in their response to the Europeanisation of migrant integration policy proposals, they continue to entrench into their national models. EU rhetoric on convergence around supranational strategies on migrant integration into civil society is thus far ineffective (Mulcahy 2009; Kirchick 2019). One result is that many migrants fall outside the asylum system or exist on the periphery of societies awaiting protection decisions. As a result, their outlook is precarious and uncertain.

5.3 Member State Enforcement and Migrant Integration (Italy)

Using Italy as a case study, this section gives more fine-grained detail on asylum procedures and works to show the scope of securitisation in reception and detention systems. It highlights the internal migration enforcement measures migrants face from arrival to accommodation or rejections in the country and the pressures this creates for them. It draws here on data collected from phase one of the field research conducted in Milan and Rome. A total of 55 interviews was conducted with migrants on the streets of these cities, as detailed in the previous chapter. Supplementing these interviews are ones conducted with humanitarian sector participants, focused on insights into the reception on arrival experience and integration strategies by migrants in the two cities.

5.3.1 Asylum Procedures

The EU asylum procedures are challenged both in design and function. Amongst these challenges is the uneven process of making distinctions between asylum seekers and economic migrants. This section briefly outlines what migrants rescued at sea and brought to the island of Lampedusa, Italy, go through in terms of procedure. This section covers three types of individuals: those who apply for asylum, those who are not eligible for asylum and those awaiting a decision on their claim and appeals against a rejection. The fate of these individuals is a complex and sensitive topic. Non-eligible applicants can only hope and wait. Those who have exhausted all available options may find themselves stuck with unclear prospects for years after their appeals run out.

According to IOM data, between 1 January and 11 November 2022, 135,889 migrants arrived at sea in the EU. Between 1 January and 11 November 2022, 88,100 arrived in Italy (International Organization for Migration 2022a). Authorities and humanitarian staff meet those brought to Lampedusa, where they undergo various asylum procedures (see figure 5.2). The design of these procedures again attempts to distinguish between asylum seekers and economic migrants. However, this distinction is often complicated and overdrawn. If an individual is ineligible for asylum, they may be returned to their country of origin or detained pending deportation.

Migrants determined to be ‘economic’ in nature, those who migrate to improve their economic prospects or are from safe countries, do not meet the criteria for asylum. Those deemed ineligible may be repatriated or detained pending deportation. In some cases, they access temporary permission to remain in the country if the assessment is that they pose no threat to public safety or national security. The Asylum Procedures Directive establishes common standards for determining who qualifies for asylum.

However, implementation of the Directive has been uneven across the Member States, leading to inconsistencies in the treatment of asylum seekers.

There are three pathways through which an asylum seeker may apply for protection: at a designated hotspot on arrival at an external border, at another external border point, and within a Member State. The hotspot approach is where authorities use fast-track operational assets to process asylum applications and act immediately on return decisions. As of this writing, Greece and Italy are the only two Member States implementing or *surging* hotspot assets. However, other Member States may request the deployment of this approach (Mentzelopoulou and Luyten 2018; Papoutsi et al. 2019). In Italy, three recent hotspots centre around areas where most migrants arrive Taranto, Apulia, a city on the coast of Southern Italy—Lampedusa, an island in the Mediterranean Sea off the coast of Southern Italy—and Pozzallo, a town in the province of Ragusa, Sicily (Asylum Information Database 2020; Loschi and Slominski 2022).

It is at such sites where organisations such as the Praesidium Project work to assist migrants. Established in 2006 by the Italian Ministry of the Interior, the project relies on cooperation between the Italian government, the Italian Red Cross (CRI), IOM, Save the Children Italy and UNHCR (Italy 2006). The purpose of Praesidium is to better aid migrants immediately on arrival, especially survivors of trafficking, minors and unaccompanied minors. It transfers the most vulnerable from Lampedusa to other centres in the city (Italian Red Cross 2010). As one legal counter-trafficking field specialist describes what happens when humanitarian staff get the call about arrivals on Lampedusa and what migrants go through in their first moments on European territory, procedurally:

We would receive calls at any time of the day by the Italian Coast Guard, saying “There is a boat approaching Lampedusa. It will be disembarking in 10 minutes.” We go to the port and assess the situation. Migrants are taken to the reception centre and the first thing they start with the police and immigration officers for identification procedures. We then start to give out leaflets in different languages. After identification, we do our work which is in the first place to talk to individuals and tell them what happens next and provide important legal information before they are transferred to any accommodation settings (Humanitarian sector participant, 21 November 2020).

It is also at the point of initial registration on arrival where Dublin is triggered.

An embedded unit with the Ministry of Interior sends representatives to the arrival points whose job is ascertaining Member State responsibility. Authorities ask questions related to the Dublin Regulation to determine through a hierarchy of criteria which Member State holds jurisdiction (see table 5.2). If Dublin applies, alternate arrangements for transfer to the Member State responsible ensue (Italy 2007; Asylum Information Database 2020).

Technically, within 30 days of lodging the application for asylum, a representative from the Territorial Commissions for International Protection located in the national territory interviews the applicant. A decision is made in the following three working days with permissible extensions within specific criteria on whether to grant protection. (Asylum Information Database 2021; Italy 2008). However, the government considers arrivals by sea to be clandestine migration and attempts to evade border procedures. Therefore, the whole process unfolds at the arrival point or transit zone (Italy 2008).

A successful asylum application yields one of three protection results: refugee status; subsidiary protection, which is an EU-level designation for those needing protection and not qualifying as a refugee under UN convention; and humanitarian protection, which is an identification afforded under Italian law (National Commission

for the Right to Asylum 2022). With a rejected application, the applicant may appeal the decision through civil justice within an immediate 30-day window. That window is reduced to fifteen days if the application is in detention pending an expedited procedure. The final appeal of the civil court's decision may be challenged through the higher Court of Cassation again within an immediate 30-day window. Once all appeals are exhausted, this triggers the removal mechanisms for the migrant's expulsion from EU territory (Asylum Information Database 2022).

While an asylum seeker's application is awaiting a decision or under appeal, the applicant may not seek employment. At the same time, until the State responds to the application, it is responsible for providing accommodation, education, professional training and social welfare. Moreover, all three forms of protection granted to the individual translate to full access to health care, housing and the labour market. However, there appears to be stress on the system with fewer services and difficulty accessing support for refugees (Bolzoni et al. 2015; Asylum Information Database 2019; System of Accommodation and Integration (*Sistema Accoglienza Integrazione*) 2020; National Commission for the Right to Asylum 2022).

The above relates to those migrants formally seeking asylum. The situation is even more precarious for undocumented people who either do not apply for asylum or have had their claims rejected. Between 500,000 to 700,000 undocumented migrants have been estimated to be living in Italy in recent years (Connor and Passel 2019),¹⁵ most with no support from the State. More than two-thirds of such migrants living in Europe were estimated to be in France, Germany, Italy and the United Kingdom. Migrants who lack documentation find it more difficult to access services, obtain

¹⁵ Estimates include asylum seekers awaiting a decision on their application (Connor and Passell 2019).

residence permits, or return to their country of origin. Statelessness becomes an absolute liability with no proof of nationality (International Organization for Migration 2019d; Pontiggia 2020).

In the field research described in this chapter, the 55 migrant respondents contacted in Milan and Rome were evasive when asked whether they had applied for asylum, were awaiting a decision, or were rejected. The presumption is that most thus did not have formal leave to remain in the host country and were in the more precarious state described. I strengthened this view when tracked with results of others who substantiated the fear of deportation amongst migrants such that the better of the worse options is not to seek refugee status (Schuster 2011; Crawley and Kaytaz 2022; Badalič 2023).

5.3.2 Reception and Detention Systems

As noted in Chapter Three, the New Pact on Migration and Asylum seeks to encourage EU Member States to share responsibility more equally for addressing acute migration pressures felt by some states (European Commission 2020a; 2020b). However, in practical terms, such pressure release mechanisms and fair distribution are less robust. Nor is this solidarity forthcoming regarding migrant relocation to other Member States. Solidarity is evident, however, around migration as a security issue and expediting returns of migrants to countries of origin. Between February and September 2021, for example, 411,710 persons had asylum applications pending in Italy (averaging over

Sources: Adapted from the Association for Juridical Studies on Immigration 2021; see also Asylum Information Database 2022.

50,000 a month). In contrast, Portugal had only 475 persons with pending asylum applications in this same period, averaging between 30 and 80 a month (Statistical Office of the European Union 2021b).

Arriving migrants who decide to apply for asylum, most of whom have few resources, are afforded stays in the reception system. Authorities disperse migrants to maximise a shared responsibility of placements at reception sites throughout the country. The challenge is that the efforts made compared to the size of the number's strains personnel, political will and resources (Italy 2015; Lumley-Sapanski 2022; National Commission for the Right to Asylum 2022). For example, Italy has the greatest concentration of stranded migrants of any Member State at 78,421 (Displacement Tracking Matrix 2022a). A humanitarian worker made this observation on the length of time migrants may spend in the reception system:

Arrivals will be held on Lampedusa for between a few days to maximum a month. My experience is that most are transferred within a week or two. We have some time with them during this time to work with people, hear their stories and provide as much emotional support as possible during this incredibly stressful period of their experience (Humanitarian sector participant, 21 November 2020).

The Italian reception system is multifaceted and encompasses state agencies, humanitarian IGOs and NGOs. The national system of Accommodation and Integration (SAI) includes hosting and reception facilities coordinated at the national level and managed by the Italian Association of Local Authorities (ANCI). More specifically, there are three basic elements to the reception centre system. The first element is in the first arrival areas and hotspots and is called the First Aid and Reception Centres (CPSA) (Italy 2020; Asylum Information Database 2020). A second element operates in tandem and involve reception centres run by the Ministry of the Interior. These reception

centres host most asylum seekers through this element of the reception system (D'Angelo 2019; Bello 2022b). Finally, the Emergency Reception Centres (CAS) make up the third element of the system. These centres perform pre-reception activities and are short-term as first reception centres before transfers to secondary sites (Asylum Information Database 2020).

The ministry of the Interior lists psycho-social assistance as a migrant's right while in reception centres (National Commission for the Right to Asylum 2022). One of the challenges is providing appropriate psycho-social support, whether in the reception system or outside of these facilities. Migrants have experienced extreme trauma throughout their high-risk journey, many of whom are women. As one survivor recounts:

One of the most pressing things was that lots of women were coming from the Ivory Coast, Guinea, and other parts of West Africa. Many, many women reported escaping from forced marriage, enduring female genital mutilation, and other forms of abuse. These are survivors of gender-based violence either in their country of origin, while transiting or in Libya, or both (Humanitarian sector participant, 21 November 2020).

Then there are the Centres for Identification and Expulsion (CIE), now known as pre-removal detention centres (CPRs), which accommodate migrants categorised as those requiring repatriation back to their home country (D'Angelo 2019). The Italian Detention System has also developed from a place of migration securitisation, responding, as Campesi (2014) notes, 'to the dual logic of risk and emergency' (p. 160). The securitisation of migrant integration in Italy is a process of increasing threat framing supporting increasing state power over the freedoms of migrants. They combine with anti-migrant rhetoric leading to a criminalisation of migrant movements.

Closely related to this is the legal process developed to detain and expel migrants. On the one hand, the so-called Reception Decree, which is an Italian law that provides a unified approach to supporting asylum seekers and those granted international protection, with proceedings divided into distinct stages, does not allow placing asylum seekers in the detention system to scrutinise applications for protection. On the other hand, modifications and amendments to this bill create a space for detention in facilities hotspots and other areas of the first arrival to establish identity (Italy 2008; Asylum Information Database 2020).

According to a report on the detention conditions in the country by the Association for Juridical Studies on Immigration (ASGI), based in Torino, Italy, substantial migrant protection issues are in serious need of oversight regarding the detention system. There are three issues emphasised. The first is the need for a mechanism to notify family members of migrants in cases of emergency. Notably, a family notification system is absent when a migrant dies in detention. The second is the need to better monitor detention conditions. The third issue is the role of protecting the health of migrants while in detention and the need for a mechanism to address care (Association for Juridical Studies on Immigration 2021). The absence of monitoring and accountability for the health and well-being of migrants reinforces the image of a securitised internal migration context where enforcement, not migrant integration, is foregrounded.

Twelve months of detention for asylum issues is the maximum allowed. Then those assigned for removal have a maximum of 120 days in detention and 150 days for identification. However, officials have yet to release data on how this law works in practice and how long the average detention time length for asylum seekers in either

CPRs or hotspots. In 2019, there were 6,172 migrants detained in CPRs. In addition, judicial decrees released one thousand seven hundred fifty-five migrants, stating that their detention was unwarranted. Another 2,992 were sent back to their country of origin (Asylum Information Database 2020). Reception and detention conditions also vary widely by Member State. And, as noted, many migrants avoid being held in reception, opting to remain out of the system and have increased freedom of movement (European Parliament 2015a; see also Ceccorulli and Lablanca 2014; Ceccorulli 2021).

It is important to note that the data-driven exercises to track migrant deaths and missing during high-risk migration do not account for migrants who die in detention. This category of a migrant regulates one of the most significant holes in accounting for missing migrants in data collection of this nature. The combined efforts of news organisations, inter-governmental and NGOs have not resulted in a comprehensive understanding of detention deaths. The secretive nature and lack of transparency add to the urgent nature of protecting the rights of migrants (Wong 2015).

5.4 Anti-Migrant Rhetoric: A Barrier to Migrant Integration

This section offers more comprehensive detail on ways in which the securitisation of migration has posed significant barriers to migrant integration within EU Member States. The disjointed, varying and often overwhelmed migrant integration regimes in EU Member States such as Italy provide one set of challenges to migrants. However, anti-migrant rhetoric is a more contextual and general challenge to migrants and their successful integration. Anti-migrant rhetoric in this environment of precarity may in fact be the most significant barrier to the integration of migrants in host cities within the EU. This section presents scholarship and survey data on general attitudes towards

integrating migrants by the broad EU and Italy-specific populations. Moreover, how media and political parties have engaged in anti-migrant rhetoric, creating an environment of increased vulnerability for migrants.

While this section primarily highlights how far-right political parties engage in anti-migrant rhetoric resulting in increased securitised *mise en scène* (*setting the stage*) it also posits that by no means is this the exclusive domain of the right. Opposition to migrants from the political left exists as well. While some on the left support migrants' rights, others believe that migrants are a threat to economic security. Left-wing critics often argue that migrants take jobs away from local workers and depress wages, as do trade unions resisting displacement of factory workers. Critique from the left also highlights migrants' ostensible strain on social services, such as education and healthcare. Additionally, some on the left believe that migrants increase competition for scarce resources, leading to environmental degradation. Critics on the left also argue that many migrants are fleeing conflict and poverty caused by neoliberal policies. Thus, they view migration as a symptom of broader problems with the global economy. For these reasons, some on the left advocate for stricter migration control and engage in anti-migrant rhetoric (March and Mudde 2005; March 2007; Alonso and da Fonseca 2012; Mudde and Kaltwasser 2013; Kriesi 2014; Stavrakakis and Katsambekis 2014; Natter and de Haas 2018; Dennison and Geddes 2019; Alcoy 2020; Kopyciok and Silver 2021).

When looking for a theoretical explanation, one note is that anti-migrant rhetoric stems from threat perception based on fear. Group threat theory, for example, seeks to explain these perceptions of migrants that do not have the data to support most claims. Group threat theory seeks the reasoning behind overreaction to events with more

securitised migration rather than the more beneficial to society development response to migration. It stems from the contribution of Blalock (1967), the belief that resources are scarce and that competition already exists among the local population translates to an increased perception that groups attempting to integrate into the populace will mean even fewer possibilities, more competition and therefore a cause for concern (Natter and de Haas 2018). The minority group is perceived to threaten the benefits accrued by the majority group. Then, responses to this threat include prejudiced attitudes and exclusion policies (see also Dixon and Rosenbaum 2004; Schlueter and Scheepers 2010; García-Faroldi 2017; Demirkol and Nalla 2021). Many threat perceptions are feeding anti-migrant rhetoric that leads to increased security and barriers to migrant integration. These include economic and financial threats of migrants competing for jobs and taking advantage of social safety nets. In addition, the physical risk of terrorism and worsening crime is a perceived threat to national culture, identity and religion (Dinas and van Spanje 2011).

Many political elites also work to tilt the political agenda against migrant integration by the media to promote their messaging and gain support (Bohman 2011; Urso 2018). Anti-migrant rhetoric significantly intensified in 2015, coalescing around significant numbers of migrants entering Europe as introduced previously. Extensive flows of people fled war-ravaged Syria into Europe through the Eastern Mediterranean Route to Greece and then onward in attempts to reach other countries thought to be migrant welcoming, such as Germany. The media and political party actors amplify rhetoric to escalate and dramatise the emotional contexts surrounding migration, which has an impact or at least some influence on public opinion (Kosho 2016; Mauro and Memoli 2021). The development of anti-migrant rhetoric and other rhetoric follows a

cycle that begins with the migration event. And then interchangeable are the influences and interplay of the following elements: media coverage, public opinion, political agenda and policy implementation (see figure 5.3).

Figure 5.3 Anti-Migrant Rhetoric Cycle

Visual evidence stokes emotions and factors into how individuals approach migration events (Bleiker 2018). Examples include videos of the Libyan Coast Guard shooting at a boat full of migrants, as reported by *The Telegraph* (21 July 2021), or migrants jumping into the sea as their dinghy deflates between Libya and Sicily, as reported by the *Wall Street Journal* and *The Guardian* (6 May 2015). There are images of European beaches covered in life jackets left by thousands of migrants or the incident captured on camera of the body of little Alan Kurdi lying face down and washed up on

the shore in Turkey after attempting to reach Europe (Pop 2013; Rygiel 2016).¹⁶ These scenes, and others depicting long lines of migrants walking toward Europe, slipping under fences or crowded onto boats, can inform and influence judgements about such processes as migrant integration. They are used to ignite passions on both sides of the politics surrounding migration, from compassion to fear (Sohlberg et al. 2019; Kjeldsen and Andersen 2018). They are further dramatising migration as either one of accommodation or security and framing a migration event in a particular way assists in placing the matter higher on a party's political agenda or platform, both conservative and liberal, including populist segments and the extreme factions of both sides of the political spectrum.

Comments made earlier in this section regarding the political leanings of parties also hold for media coverage. A comparative analysis of how the European media covers migration across 17 countries reveals the following: When outlets considered liberal/left-wing cover migration, 38 per cent of that coverage is negative. Among conservative/right-wing outlets, coverage is 45 per cent negative (Fengler and Kreutler 2020). Media coverage of events increases supports extreme politics against migrant integration (Huysmans 2006; Esses et al. 2013).

Media coverage can also serve to reframe how people perceive an event, with framings of migration as an economic or security threat. A report examining how the media covers migration in 17 countries found that in Italy, the media coverage of migration trended towards sensationalism instead of objectivity. It points to data in 2016 showing how this extensive coverage links to an increase in fear using one of the

¹⁶ Alan Kurdi was a three-year-old boy from Syria, one of at least 12 who drowned trying to reach the island of Kos, Greece. He wore a bright red t-shirt and shorts when his body washed up near a resort in Bodrum, Turkey. Within hours a photo of this scene went viral (Smith 2015).

examples of connecting migration to Islamic terrorism (Ethical Journalism Network 2017; Kreutler and Fengler 2020; see also Gallantino 2022).

For example, many view migrants entering the EU territory from a war-torn country alternately as an imperative for humanitarian response or a security threat (Huysmans 2006; Pietsch 2015; Eberl et al. 2018). For others, migration threatens European health, increasing structural violence and discrimination (Freedman 2021). All such framings can impact how or whether citizens welcome migrants into communities and their access to services and support. Derrida (2005) notes that the principle of hospitality is often set aside in contexts of racism and xenophobia. Instead, migrants are framed as burdening a country's already stretched social support resources (Kaczmarczyk et al. 2015; Pietsch 2015). For example, in Italy, the term 'clandestini' is a frequent term used by media to describe migrants attempting to reach their shores. It is another example where 'Clandestine migrants' have no legal merit yet fuel passions (D'Angelo 2019). Instead of developing integration policies based on a host country's hospitality, migration is framed as dangerous to society, and terrorist infiltrators sustain security policies (Bandeira 2021; see also Asylum Information Database 2020). The media focuses attention on this aspect of migration.

At the same time, the EU hosts relatively few refugees in percentage terms. Specifically, the percentage of refugees compared to the 447.5 million population of the EU is 0.6%. According to UNHCR data, there were 2.5 million refugees in the EU as of mid-2021, meaning asylum seekers who have been granted refugee status by Member States (Statistical Office of the European Union 2020; United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees 2021). If I compare this result to other refugees-receiving countries such as Canada, whose percentage of refugees compared to its 38.7 million

population in 2021 stands at 14.74% (Statistics Canada 2022), it becomes evident that rhetoric may not match the reality in the EU context.

Survey data shows that public opinion in migrant receiving states such as Italy has been negative toward migration in recent years. In a survey on public perceptions of migrants, 74 per cent of Italians think that migration is more of a problem than an opportunity. This figure is 31 per cent across the EU. Some 75 per cent of Italians believe migrants worsen crime problems, compared to 55 per cent across the EU. Around 75 think migrants are a burden to the country's welfare system, versus 55 per cent in the EU, and the split is 58-39 per cent on the question of whether migrants take jobs away in the country (see figure 5.4) (European Commission 2017b). Other data support the notion that many view migration as a security issue and that some migrant groups are 'difficult to integrate' (Caneva 2014). However, at odds with this is data on terrorist attacks, which show something different. Between 2011 and 2019, Global Terrorism Database (GTD) (2019) recorded 78 terrorist attacks in Italy. Of these terrorist attacks, GTD designated five as refugee incidents, defined as including camps and involving migrants. Of these five incidents, one was active instigation by migrants, and the Italian population perpetrated the rest toward migrants. Homegrown Italian extremist groups accounted for the vast majority of the 78 incidents committed, including anarchists, antifascists, antisemitic, left-wing, neo-fascist and right-wing activists and extremists (Global Terrorism Database 2019; 2021; see also European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation 2022). It is another example of where fact and perception are at odds.

More broadly, regarding the views of Europeans and Italy country-level opinions on the obstacles to migrant integration, respondents in a Special

Eurobarometer survey consider ten. These include (1) difficulties in finding a job, (2) discrimination against migrants, (3) limited effort by migrants to integrate, (4) high concentration of migrants in certain areas, (5) difficulties in accessing long-term residence permits, (6) negative portrayal of migrants in the media (7) difficulties in finding adequate accommodation, (8) limited interactions between migrants and host country citizens, (9) limited access to education, healthcare and social protection and (10) difficulty in bringing in family members (see figure 5.5) (European Commission 2022; see also Dražanová et al. 2020).

Figure 5.4 Public Perception of Migrants (EU and Italy)

Sources: European Commission 2017a; 2022a.

Figure 5.5 Ten Obstacles to Migrant Integration (EU and Italy)

Source: European Commission 2022a.

The following striking paradox is an example of political agenda and the influence of public opinion driving responses toward migrants. In 2013, following the sinking of a boat in the Central Mediterranean, Italy bestowed the estimated three hundred and sixty-six migrants who lost their lives with honorary Italian citizenship, while the survivors were criminally charged and held in detention (Danewid 2017; Rainey 2018; Missing Migrants Project 2022a). In the immediate week following the disaster, then Prime Minister Enrico Letta declared there was to be a state funeral on Lampedusa for those migrants who drowned. However, following a public backlash, the downgraded policy was a discrete memorial service in Sicily (Kingston 2013; Davies 2013).

Policies towards migrants, typically slow to change, will gain speed by politicians during significant upticks in migration flows, especially when there is a media spotlight on the issue and public opinion erupts alongside. As an example, in attempts to advance a hardline political agenda Umberto Bossi, former head of Italy's right-wing political party Lega Nord (Northern League), called for military action against migrants arriving by sea. Bossi was quoted as saying this:

After the second or third warning, boom... the cannon roar. Without any beating about the bush. The cannon that blows everyone out of the water. Otherwise, this business will never end (*BBC News* 2003)

Matteo Salvini, leader of the Lega Nord and Deputy Prime Minister of Italy has sought to leverage Facebook and Twitter to push public opinion on migration to the far right (McGinnis 2021). Salvini has five million followers on Facebook and another 1.5 million on Twitter (Salvini 2022a; 2022b). One of his strategies on these platforms is consistent postings to push his political agenda, part of which opposes migration. One

of the results is a high percentage of Likes and Retweets (Salvini 2022c; 2022d). Leaving aside the question of whether Salvini's use of Facebook and Twitter effectively swayed public opinion, his anti-migrant rhetoric certainly intends to impact how people think about migrants and migration. I posit that by constantly reinforcing harmful stereotypes and presenting migrants as a threat to society, he helped create an environment where discrimination and prejudice are more likely to flourish (Berti and Loner 2021; see also Noritio et al. 2021). Therefore, raising the risk level for migrants themselves is particularly dangerous in a country like Italy, where anti-migrant sentiment is already high. Several violent incidents have targeted migrants in recent years (European Network Against Racism 2016).

Anti-migrant rhetoric in Italy has contributed to harsh migration policies such as Law 189 of 30 July, known as the Bossi-Fini law (Italy 2002). The architects of the legislation were hard-right politicians known for anti-immigration rhetoric, including Bossi and Gianfranco Fini, leader of the Alleanza Nazionale Party (Northern Alliance). Under Article 11 of the law, specifying provisions against clandestine migration, the Italian Navy and ships on police duty may board vessels in and outside of Italian waters if suspected of unlawfully transporting migrants. This legislation made rescuing migrants at sea a legally challenging prospect for Italian vessel owners. Citizens who might otherwise be involved in informal rescue attempts would now face imprisonment (Colombo et al. 2002; Geddes 2008; Bull 2010; Akkerman 2012).

Another area where the effects of anti-migrant rhetoric are evident is the criminalization of NGOs engaged in sea rescues. As NGOs stepped into the breach left behind by Italian forces to conduct search and rescue efforts in the Mediterranean, there were accusations of colluding with smugglers and claims of smugglers profiting from

NGO rescuers. Such charges were made by an Italian prosecutor and at least one Interior under-secretary of Italy as reported by multiple media outlets such as La Stampa and the Euro Observer (Cusumano and Bell 2021; see also European Border and Coast Guard Agency 2017; Molinari and Albanese 2017; Nielsen 2017; Öner and Cirino 2021; Court of Justice of the European Union 2021b; 2021c). As a result, the media amplified their charges of violating border security.

In addition to coverage of sea rescues, there are documented crackdowns on humanitarians assisting migrants in the cities of Italy. It provides further evidence of the securitized context in which migrants seek to integrate. Specifically, one charge levelled against many Member States is denying access to humanitarian organisations that provide essential care and assess potential human rights abuses in reception centres. For example, some have cited reduced access to Lampedusa cites as part of a Council of Europe (2017) report (Vosyliūtė and Conte 2018). Humanitarian workers related experiencing this type of obstruction, as one describes:

Providing assistance to migrants was more supported by the government and there were more services in place. In the past few years things have changed drastically — of course the political climate has changed. Some of those services have been taken down. In many cases our access to migrants is more restricted. It has become very, very hard for us as service providers and for migrant communities who rely on our help (Humanitarian sector participant, 21 November 2020).

The anti-migrant rhetoric cycle is not exclusive to Italy. It manifests itself in other countries in Europe and around the world. The following example is from the U.S. context. In this case, the reference is to migrants travelling the Central America and Mexico routes to the United States. There is a podcast called War Room Pandemic, hosted by populist of the right and political strategist Steven K. Bannon, former White House Chief Strategist and Senior Counsellor to President Donald Trump. In a recent

episode, the host describes migrants as ‘embedded into the U.S., a stampede of people. They are destroying our nation and doing it on purpose.’ Bannon also makes a direct link to his political agenda. He states that ‘this [migration event at the Southern Border] is what is going to give us the hundred seat pick-up [in Congress] in November’ (Bannon 2022a)—showing that anti-migrant rhetoric is ubiquitous. In another episode, Dr Peter Navarro describes ‘a flood of illegal aliens putting downward pressure on workers’ wages and creating economic dislocation and making recession worse’ (Bannon 2022b).

The populism of this ilk has strong ties to conservative groups and right-leaning political parties globally. For example, Bannon and numerous other figures on the US populist right have expressed admiration for hard-right Hungarian Prime Minister Viktor Orbán, noted for his anti-immigration stances (Dallison 2018). It is an integral part of the growth of populism from the right across the U.S and Europe, including France, Hungary, Italy and the United Kingdom. However, Bannon also claims solidarity with factions of populism from the left, such as those aligned with progressive Senator Bernie Sanders. It highlights the interconnected nature of global populism (Eatwell and Goodwin 2019; Agwu 2021; Day and Uetrict 2021; Feffer 2021; de la Torre and Srisa-nga 2022).

The use of victim rhetoric to frame migrants is also highly prevalent. There is extensive data on the effective treatment and recovery benefits to the individual who experiences trauma when using survivor rhetoric and framing the individual as resilient when the person holds this belief (Park et al. 2009). Another factor makes life more precarious for migrants in the host state. Certainly, humanitarian programming is moving rapidly in this direction both in rhetoric and substantive practice by

strengthening this type of migrant agency and using terms such as a survivor of gender-based violence and a survivor of trafficking. These labels mean a great deal (Kapur 2002; Wirtz et al. 2013; Murray et al. 2018; Hayward 2019; Haefner 2021). Having set the scene of what arriving migrants are up against, the following section presents how migrants navigate this securitised migrant integration environment and use network-derived social capital.

5.5 Network-Derived Social Capital: An Integration Survival Strategy

Migrants face an increasingly securitised integration context in European Union destination cities. This increases risks to them, as do the factors noted earlier: having no contacts at the destination, limited resources and being vulnerable to authorities. In response, they exercise agency and seek to derive network social capital in crucial ways as part of their resilient survivor strategy. They respond by seeking to maintain ties developed in transit or to form new groups, and thus to derive horizontally oriented forms of bonding and bridging social capital. They also often seek to gain accessing humanitarian organisations' services, and so derive more vertically oriented forms of linking social capital. In addition, many migrants continued to rely on the linking capital of their vertical ties with smugglers. They were using these connections to navigate the complexities of their new cities.

To note, the risk of death is high for migrants traveling high-risk routes, and it is also higher for migrants traveling within their chosen destination states or regions. Data from Missing Migrant Project shows that between January 2014 and October 2022, an estimated 7,701 migrants died during migration through Europe. Causes of death include accidents, drowning, sickness due to lack of access to adequate healthcare,

exposure to inadequate food, shelter, or water, hazardous transport and mixed or unknown circumstances (Missing Migrants Project 2022b). In host cities, migrants often face threats related to racism and xenophobia and violence stemming from both, from labour exploitation and unsafe working conditions, and from structural discrimination. Relatedly, one of the most pressing issues facing migrant communities is access to medical care (Legido-Quigley et al. 2019). Several organisations are working to address this problem, and structural weaknesses remain (Chiarenza et al. 2019).

Fieldwork found that migrants from West Africa stayed in Italy or intended to reach the country as a first entry point. Analysis of the complete phase one fieldwork dataset show 89 per cent of the 73 migrants interviewed had Europe as their intended destination. This finding is consistent with other studies and interviews with humanitarian sector participants (Schapendonk 2011; 2018; 2020). Those migrants who claim asylum when they arrive are issued a stay permit while their claim is adjudicated. In the meantime, they make things work the best they can, in ways very similar to those who do not apply for asylum and have clandestinely made their way to the cities. For example, many respondents were street vendors selling trinkets or fake Prada and Gucci wallets to tourists in high-traffic areas in Milan and Rome. There was a high degree of fear and trepidation of authorities observed in these areas since, as earlier noted, migrants do not have permits to sell in many cases. For example, in Milan, migrants approach tourists to buy colourful handmade wristbands for five EURO, and then many would flee if there were police close — a frequent occurrence throughout the day. In addition, the Italian authorities continue to crack down on and remove migrants from informal makeshift camps throughout cities, such as those at Via Cupa and Via Curtatone in Rome (Busby and Dotto 2018; Weima and Minca 2022).

The asylum question was again a tricky one to pose to participants. When asked if they had applied for asylum, all respondents in Milan and Rome said no or did not reply. Moreover, many would not tell if they planned to apply. There was thus a challenge in building trust with migrants on the streets in an environment of fear and suspicion. However, there was also much to glean from the interactions. For example, when it comes to forming groups, 84 per cent of the phase one participants reported that they did not have family or friends waiting for them in Europe, which means the groups they formed on the route or in the cities became more critical for survival. Another potentially significant insight was that many continued to attempt to seek the assistance of the smuggler groups who brought them to Europe.

They did so primarily by maintaining connections through social networking applications or connections made in the migrant community. Responses from participants included: ‘Smugglers helped me in the city’, ‘They [smugglers] I again on my Facebook for helping find work’ (Participants 20 and 22, Rome, 28 June 2019). ‘I found my way around through the internet’, ‘People I met here introduce me to help from knowing people’ (Participants 54 and 59, Milan, 5 July 2019).

Field work highlighted how network-derived social capital — in this case, groups formed during the journey — can support migrants during the integration process as they attempt to find ways to settle in their destination country. Migrants develop networks with those connected within departure, transit and then destination countries. These connections support each other during integration and settling into a new country. They find support with language and learn from each other how best to navigate the complexities of a new community and a different political system. As one

humanitarian worker noted:

When we speak with migrants it's at the initial stage of their arrival. They have just crossed the Mediterranean Sea. They've spent time in a vessel with others. Some surviving together the sinking of the vessel and this experience forms a close knit especially with migrants from the same country meeting on these vessels. Even if they didn't know each other before getting on the boats. They tend to stay together as much as possible in the next phases including into integration (Humanitarian sector participant, 26 November 2020).

Furthermore, there can be long-term benefits of migrants participating in the citizenry, as in a recent example of migrants from the migration events of 2015 fleeing the war in Syria and welcomed by some countries such as Germany, who recently participated in their first elections since becoming citizens (Solomon 2021). However, there is only sometimes a direct line to positive outcomes, as it may lead to a parallel system detached from the formal processes. One humanitarian worker describes this:

Migrants might have multiple social networks that help them to establish themselves. If those stream towards an official process within the country's legal framework, networks help migrants find jobs and navigate the paperwork. In addition, they find support to overcome language barriers and understand better the requirements set by the system. Nevertheless, they can also be a potential threat to the sustainability of their stay in the destination country if they are side-tracked into spheres outside of the legal system (Humanitarian sector participant, 7 December 2020).

Field work also gave insights on how the positive impacts to migrants of forming groups can be long lasting:

Some people that arrived in Italy many years ago, didn't know each other until they got on the boat, today they are still living together and supporting each other, working in the same factory, and living in the

same apartment. Sharing costs and managing challenges together (Humanitarian sector participant, 21 November 2020).

Yet, for some migrants, there are dangers experienced on the routes that manifest similarly even in the host city. Here a humanitarian worker highlights where sometimes staying within a group is not of the migrants' free will:

Sometimes they do so unwillingly, being forced to stay in these social circles because they owe the 'syndicate' something. Some stay together as the 'syndicate' are still the ones that they hope are going to help them in their destination city (Humanitarian sector participant, 18 November 2020).

Similarly, many migrants are exploited by those whom they encountered in transit, including in some cases where they formed or joined groups:

If you are beautiful you can end up working in a brothel. Even though you didn't start out planning to do that. On the way you meet these people and now human smuggling turns to human trafficking and you are a captive. For men forced labour is a concern. In Europe there is more opportunities to break away, whereas if they stay in Libya, it is even harder to integrate unless you stay with the very people who smuggled you (Humanitarian sector participant, 13 November 2020).

Numerous humanitarian organisations operate in Member States to support migrants from NGOs, local volunteers, faith-based groups, and other informal groups. However, this network-derived social capital is accessed slightly differently than on the high-risk migration journey. On the high-risk migration routes, if migrants use humanitarian organisations, it is generally for assistance to return home or rescue from a crisis in the desert. In the city, migrants seek out humanitarian organisations through the groups they connect with to find ways to support integration. Furthermore, data from

the phase one fieldwork shows that only 5 per cent of the migrants successfully engaged with the humanitarian groups operating in the cities.

After the migration events of 2015, Jai Mexis, a national of Greece, founded the NGO Odyssea to support migrants, primarily youth, to access employment opportunities. Based in Greece, Odyssea started operations by collecting the thousands of lifejackets left on the beaches of Lesbos by the hundreds of thousands of migrants arriving by Sea. Initially running workshops with refugees, the organisation created products from these lifejackets, selling them commercially, creating employment opportunities and supporting local economies. In another example from the same year, the NGO Lesvos Solidary started Safe Passage, a project converting life jackets into bags, pencil cases and wallets, while employing migrants from Afghanistan, Iran and Pakistan (Wilding 2016; Petridou 2020). In Italy, through organisations such as Juma Map Services for Refugees (2021), migrants can more easily seek out services available to them in their local areas of the country. The services are available in 15 languages, helping migrants find accommodation, legal counsel, access to health services and psycho-social support.

Another aspect of the importance of the linking social capital of humanitarian organisations is the vertical ties developed between migrants and the humanitarians themselves:

I've witnessed many cases of migrants building long term relationships of trust with humanitarian workers, particularly NGOs. These relationships often go beyond the direct assistance and support provided to migrants in one of the transit countries. There could be an international network of referrals, connections at destination countries (Humanitarian sector participant, 7 December 2020).

The intensity and scope of powerful voices generating anti-migrant rhetoric compels migrants to develop an alternative to state-migrant integration policies when none is available. The most straightforward pathway to do this is through the development of two fundamental types of network-derived social capital forming groups and humanitarian organisations. Again, during integration in a similar fashion to the high-risk migration experience, there is a notable absence of strong ties in the individual development of social capital and a move to strengthen weak ties.

5.6 Conclusion

This chapter has showed that as migration increasingly has been securitised within and by the Member States of the European Union, so too have approaches taken to migrant integration. In addition, the most significant overarching barrier to migrant integration is anti-migrant rhetoric. The central takeaway is that in the face of these forces, migrants use their agency and seek to derive two critical types of network social capital: forming groups, from which they seek to derive both bonding and bridging social capital; and using services provided by humanitarian organisations, which provide forms of linking social capital. Moreover, many migrants continue to derive network social capital from groups formed in transit – although continued affiliation with smugglers and some other groups can have negative impacts on them.

This chapter also gave context on the highly securitised environment of the migrant integration system. It highlighted tensions within the European Union and its Member States. On the one hand, the EU – like the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) and the African Union — champions internal freedom of movement. It also affirms responsibility to accept asylum seekers in whichever manner

they arrive on EU territory. On the other hand, built-in mechanisms reimpose internal border controls when Member States deem it appropriate to curb migration flows. Often these decisions are exploited by political parties who utilise the anti-migrant rhetoric cycle as leverage. And treatment of asylum seekers and the adjudication of their cases is uneven across Member States and increasingly restrictive.

The second section presented a view of migrant integration in the context of securitisation at the supranational level. First, it introduced the Common European Asylum System's structure. Second, it showed how, while there is a stated aim for common standards and shared responsibility for refugees and asylum seekers between Member States, the practical reality is starkly different, with some states being called to bear much more of the burden of arrivals. Migrants often opt out of the system rather than apply for asylum in the Member States upon arrival. Instead, they preferred to make their way to other areas within the EU. Also discussed were attempts to harmonise, or 'Europeanise' migrant integration policies, and resistance to and rejection of such attempts by Member States. Instead, national models and a lack of cohesive policies make integration for migrants that much more confusing and complicated. Moreover, as migrants opt out of formal processes, the result is an even bigger dilemma for Member States, where large populations of migrants require even greater assistance and protection.

The third section focused on migrant integration at the EU Member State level, using Italy as a case study. It highlighted the process migrants might anticipate on arrival at disembarkation points such as Lampedusa, how the hotspot approach fast-tracks arrival procedures and asylum applications, and the critical issue of giving authorities assets to act on return decisions immediately. Highlighted was the struggle

asylum seekers face awaiting a decision or an appeal on their application when they may not look for work. This condition stresses the migrant and the state's capacity to respond with services. Further, of those who opted out of the asylum process entirely, 500,000 to 700,000 were in Italy in 2019. These migrants are considered undocumented, and their situation is even more precarious.

Meanwhile, Italy's multifaceted reception and detention system has its deficiencies, from limited capacity to provide appropriate psycho-social support, the need for mechanisms to protect the health of migrants and ensure that there is adequate oversight of conditions in reception and detention facilities. In addition, there are reporting deficiencies on migrant fatalities that occur in detention settings and expressed needs to pursue greater transparency in protecting migrant rights.

The fourth section presented anti-migrant rhetoric as a primary barrier to migrant integration. Throughout the left and right spectrum, political elites and many media outlets offer rhetoric to elevate the emotional views around migration and integration. In the case of anti-migrant rhetoric, a cycle begins with a migration event. Next, there is negative and inflammatory media coverage of the event. Another cycle layer is the political rhetoric attached to a migration event. A further piece of the cycle is the policies implemented in response. An additional layer is the political agenda of the party elites, and the last piece of the anti-migrant rhetoric cycle is the public's opinion of the migration event. These layers, on their own or cumulatively, translate into more challenges for migrants seeking to be part of their new environment.

The fifth section explored how migrants exercise and seek to develop some critical types of network-derived social capital in the face of this securitised migrant integration context. One centres on groups formed during the journey, and migrants

supporting each other during the integration process. As a result, they learn how to navigate processes best and find support within the group than attempt to go it alone – though field work highlighted how continuing affiliations with smugglers and others can lead to ongoing exploitation and abuse. Migrants also seek to form various social networks once in the host cities. Finally, they use services provided by humanitarian organisations, which become a crucial survival link especially for those outside the formal asylum system. As on the high-risk routes through the Sahara and the Mediterranean, migrants seeking to overcome personal risk factors – limited information, vulnerability to authorities – strive to form networks and derive specific forms of bridging, bonding and linking social capital from them.

Chapter Six ties together the strands of the analysis thus far and examines some broader theoretical implications of the securitised migration, related extraterritorial enforcement of migration by the EU, and barriers to migrant integration in a securitised internal context.

Chapter Six

A Discussion of Contribution and Significance

6.1 Introduction

6.2 Advancing Understandings of High-Risk Sahara Routes

6.3 Advancing Understandings of Migrant Agency

6.4 Advancing Understandings of Migration and Social Capital

6.5 Securitisation and Neo-Colonial Power

6.5.1 Migration and Competing Regionalisms

6.5.2 Extraterritorial Enforcement and Neo-Colonial Power

6.5.3 Securitisation and Ethnicity: Internal Power

6.1 Introduction

This chapter highlights several contributions made by this thesis toward advancing understandings of migrant agency and network social-capital development and use on high-risk migration routes. Five discrete contributions are identified, corresponding broadly to the two overarching research questions. Those questions again are:

- 1) How do migrants seek to develop and utilise network social capital
 - a) as a survival strategy on high-risk migration routes?
 - b) to facilitate integration into their host society?
- 2) How does analysing migrants' survival strategy on high-risk migration routes help us better understand states' moves toward increasingly securitised and extended enforcement regimes?

In relation to the first research question, this chapter highlights three practically oriented contributions, each of which has theoretical resonance. It also offers an analysis of a closely related set of theoretical and practical contributions relating to the second research question, and the treatment here of securitised migration and extraterritorial enforcement. The chapter is structured as follows. It first notes the contributions made to advancing understandings of the high-risk Sahara Routes themselves: the specific risks migrants have faced on them, the shifting nature of both migration routes and risks, and migrants' perspectives on the hardships they have faced in transit. Second, it offers discussion on practical-theoretical contributions to understanding migrant agency. That is, the thesis has highlighted how migrants seek to exercise agency on high-risk routes while offering an alternate framing of migrants as agents drawn from migrants' understandings. They are not victims, villains, or heroic agents pursuing their goals against all odds. Instead, they are resilient survivors. They meet hardship and suffering typically with persistence and resilience and seek to avoid

both with the exercise of creative forms of agency, including network formation and use.

The chapter then discusses the third practical-theoretical contribution: understanding social capital formation's role on high-risk routes. The existing literature features numerous investigations of how migrants seek to develop and use social capital in destination states and how existing forms of social capital, such as networks of relatives already living in those states, can shape choices to migrate and provide resources for doing so. However, the literature has remained underdeveloped in treating the role social capital formation and use plays for migrants in transit on high-risk routes. Highlighted are how this thesis has built on relevant work by Schapendonk (2011; see also Schapendonk 2012; 2013; 2015; 2018; 2020; Schapendonk and Steel 2014; Schapendonk et al. 2015) and other scholars (Collyer 2007; Liu 2013; Schaub 2012; Maher 2018) to offer a fine-grained, nuanced account of how migrants strive to develop networks on dangerous routes—or use existing ones in the case of human smuggling syndicates—the social capital they seek to derive from those networks and the challenges they face in using it to survive. Each set of insights stands to make significant contributions to theories of social capital formation concerning migration.

The chapter then discusses two more fundamentally theoretical advances offered by the thesis to understanding the implications of securitised migration and the closely related extraterritorial enforcement of migration. Highlighted first are some critical tensions around theorisations of free movement in regional organisations. Numerous researchers have sought to explain why organisations such as the EU, among others, have developed internal free movement regimes (Heinikoski 2022). There has been relatively little discussion, however, about how the extraterritorial enforcement of

migration by the EU has posed challenges to ECOWAS' principles of free movement among its Member States and the progress toward free movement by the African Union.

The chapter then turns to related questions the thesis highlights around extraterritorial enforcement of migration and neo-colonial power. It asks, for example, whether migration agreements between EU Member States and African Union Member States formerly colonised by Europeans represent forms of neo-colonial power more than shared attempts to manage shared challenges. Then follows a discussion on how the analysis of migrants' attempts to derive network social capital within destination countries calls attention to a possible reinforcement of neo-colonial power internally related to securitised migration.

6.2 Advancing Understandings of High-Risk Sahara Routes

This thesis has provided a detailed account of high-risk migration through the Sahara Desert. Information presented has included data on migrant routes, fatalities and international political agreements that often shape these routes. Even more importantly, the fieldwork conducted for this thesis gives us a close-up view of migrants' insights and perspectives on their journeys. The study thus contributes to our knowledge of how high-risk routes are experienced by those who travel them. Finally, it also shows how external factors, such as political decisions, impact their journey.

Details will be given on each of the contributions. First, I note the advances in understanding the specific risks migrants have faced and continue to. Researchers such as Schapendonk (2011; 2013; 2015; 2018; 2020; see also Schapendonk and van Moppes 2007) and organisations such as IOM and its affiliated authors (Singleton et al. 2017; Cusumano and Villa 2020; Black 2020; 2021) have done significant work in

documenting features of the high-risk Sahara migration context. This thesis has built on that foundation to provide details, especially in Chapter Four, on migrants' perceptions of the chief risks they have faced. These risks stemmed from such factors as having limited resources, which typically led to indebtedness towards smugglers. These factors may create a situation where migrants cannot pay for services rendered, leaving them in a precarious position and vulnerable to exploitation by human smugglers. Furthermore, when relying on human smugglers, migrants are subject to potentially life-threatening situations as these smuggling operations often do not prioritise the safety of those who use their services. These smugglers may transport migrants in dangerous or substandard conditions or coerce them into exploitative labour or even human trafficking.

Migrants also are vulnerable to authorities encountered along their journey, leading to various cases of abuse. Interviewees reported physical and sexual abuse, extortion and extended detainment without due process. These issues stem from the vulnerability migrants face when attempting to traverse borders without proper documentation or protection. This vulnerability is acute when individuals lack representation or legal protections against arbitrary detention and mistreatment by state authorities.

Furthermore, this vulnerability often leads to extortion from other actors, as criminals take advantage of migrants along these routes. Also discussed were ways in which solo travel by migrants along these routes can add risk. For example, respondents discussed getting lost while travelling alone and spending days without food or water, only to happen across other travellers, without which they surely would have perished.

Such details, drawing on migrants' perspectives, help to advance understanding of the risks implied by the 'high-risk route' and reinforce ways in which specific risks

link to broader political contexts, including extraterritorial enforcement. In addition, the fieldwork has helped to highlight and reinforce the prevalence of South-South migration on the high-risk Sahara routes (Adepoju 2008a; 2008b; Awumbila and Manuh 2008; Schapendonk 2010). As discussed, many from West and Central Africa and the wider sub-Saharan are travelling to other countries within North Africa as their primary destination. This framing challenges securitised rhetorical claims and perceptions that South-North migration is the dominant mode. That has potential implications for the justification of extraterritorial enforcement regimes that hamper movement across numerous states in the region.

6.3 Advancing Understandings of Migrant Agency

The thesis' fieldwork is also valuable for providing details on how migrants seek to exercise agency on high-risk routes – and for the alternate framing of migrants as agents. As discussed in detail in the previous chapter, many political elites have sought to villainise migrants, portraying them as complicit in criminal smuggling activities and as posing various urgent threats to domestic populations. Other narratives frame migrants primarily as victims, passively suffering hardships. This thesis has emphasised the creative agency exercised by migrants, especially as they have sought to develop networks in transit and derive crucial social capital from them. It has not, however, offered a portrayal of migrants as 'heroes' simply meeting and overcoming challenges out of duty to those at home. Such a characterisation, while commonly offered by some sending states' political elites (Picos III 2019), would be as one-dimensional and inaccurate as the others. Instead, migrants are framed here as *resilient survivors*.

In medicine and psychology, the concept of resilience and self-identity of a survivor is well developed. Working definitions of resilience include ‘an adaptive and active coping style’ (Rashidi et al. 2021, p. 350) and ‘the dynamic capacity of individuals to successfully maintain or regain their mental health in the face of significant life adversities or risks (Min et al. 2013, p. 2470; see also Horn and Feder 2018). Resilience is an essential concept for survivors of traumas to cultivate to maintain a healthy sense of self-identity. A resilience mindset helps individuals develop coping skills and strategies as they navigate life after experiencing trauma, supporting them to move more effectively forward with their lives. Trauma survivors work towards resilience by redefining the narrative constructed around their experience, embracing their strengths and developing skills such as problem-solving, emotional regulation and cognitive reappraisal, and creating new identities rooted in resilience. By doing so, survivors gain greater control over how they interpret their experiences while at the same time learning how to be better prepared should they encounter similar situations in the future. Such resilience-oriented practices are essential for survivors to construct, maintain and strengthen their self-identity. Ultimately, resilience provides survivors with greater endurance and an enhanced capacity to face adversity with determination, creating a positive outlook in life. Resilience is vital in treating post-traumatic stress disorder and other traumatic events (Tummala-Narra 2007; Thompson et al. 2011; Southwick and Charney 2012; Goodman et al. 2017; Horn and Feder 2018).

Self-identification as a survivor of cancer or other critical illnesses is associated with improved psychological well-being and reduced emotional stress. Research suggests that survivor identity can be an essential source of strength, motivation and resilience for individuals struggling with chronic illness. By embracing survivor

identity, individuals can often find the courage to confront their cancer experience more positively and gain greater control over their lives. In addition to helping individuals cope better with their illness's physical and psychological challenges, survivor identity may also confer social benefits such as increased access to support networks and resources. Furthermore, survivor identity benefits mental health and quality of life, so healthcare providers create an environment where survivors feel more empowered to identify (Park et al. 2009; Min et al. 2013; Morris et al. 2014; Cheung and Delfabbro 2016; Maley et al. 2016; Ben-David 2020). The experience of resilience has been significant for female survivors of domestic violence (Crann and Barata 2016), studied among survivors of genocide rape in Rwanda (Zraly and Nyirazinyoye 2010) and sexual violence in Congo (Murray et al. 2018).

This idea of the resilient survivor is defined here as an individual's capacity to adapt — through an interaction of risk and protective factors — in the face of adversity and experience, amidst high-risk migration and migrant integration. In the context of migration, the experience of resilience is of utmost importance, for example, among survivors of trafficking. Knight et al. (2022) notes that in the context of human trafficking there are critical characteristics associated with resilience are networks of support, relationships formed through groups and a sense of community between members:

The most frequently mentioned resilience factor was positive interpersonal relationships. A variety of such relationships were discussed in the studies, including familial ties, community-level ties, or knowing other survivors of the same adversity. The resilience factors described in these studies do not differentiate trafficking from other types of adversity (Knight et al. 2022, p. 1054-55).

There are several salient parallels then to this thesis. Chapter Four discusses ways that migrants seek to derive social capital through networks, including the forming of groups, the support of kinship connections and their interactions with humanitarian organisations. All are evidence of resilience in the sense of representing a capacity to adapt in the face of adversity. This thesis shows us that migrants exercise agency as part of a resilient survivor strategy during their experiences of high-risk migration and migrant integration in destination countries. It highlights ways in which migrants display resilience when confronted by anti-migrant rhetoric and disingenuous framings of migrants by some media and certain political parties, and it reinforces findings by authors such as Striel (2018), who discusses ways in which anti-migrant and security crisis rhetoric has spurred the EU to fortify its layers of deterrence for some categories of migrants and not others.

This thesis also reinforces scholars like Mainwaring, whose work on migration in the Mediterranean provided essential ground for an expanding look further into other parts of the migration journey, in this case, through the Sahara Desert. Mainwaring supported a widening of the lens to see more clearly the agency of migrants when faced with incredible forces aligned against them, positing here:

That framing migrants as victims or villains misconceives the agency, however limited, demonstrated by migrants and refugees and evidenced in their own accounts of border crossings and experiences within host states. Ignoring this agency reifies the power of the state to ‘secure’ and control migrations and conceals the contested politics of mobility and security evident in negotiations between migrants, border guards, smugglers, fisherman, and other actors (Mainwaring 2016, p. 291).

This thesis also contributes to understandings of the exercise of such agency, in particular in the Sahara context, and in extremely challenging integration contexts in

European cities. Mainwaring has highlighted that while migrants hover on the cusp of communities and encounter marginalisation, there is a characteristic of resistance and a desire to find places of accommodation and negotiation, whether it's with authorities, smugglers, or other travellers along the routes of those within cities. Migrants are creatively looking for ways to propel their onward mobility.

It is my view that a resilient survivor framing adds nuance to prominent approaches to migrant agency. Triandafyllidou (2017) shares this perspective and views migrants' use of agency as tackling the obstacles set forth by deterrence policies. Migrants in such vulnerable contexts look for ways to assert some semblance of leadership, control their lives and exercise their agency through negotiation. Indeed, the testimony of participants in this study supports this notion and adds some layers to it. Migrants seek to exercise control and leadership. They also display endurance and resilience in the face of repeated hardship. That resilient survivorship may be related to some form of leadership by example, and it deserves a better capture within the concept of leadership.

Nor is the resilient survivor completely aligned with Benli's (2018) depiction of migrant agency as a form of civil resistance, challenging domination amid dire circumstances, or Beattie's interpretation of agency as expressed through storytelling. For Beattie (2017), telling their stories is a way for migrants to process their traumatic experience of high-risk migration, with emphasis on a dialogue between researcher and participant to encourage the retelling of their own story of migration. The proposition here is that migrants are *fundamentally* resilient survivors in their exercise of agency during the entire high-risk migration and migrant integration experience.

Such a framing could have more rhetorical power to counter problematic ‘villains or victims’ rhetoric than other approaches, for it presents migrants as persons who experience trauma and have also sought and found ways through it. Stierl highlights costs associated with framing migrants as victims:

Migrant travellers, as the paradigmatic figures of vulnerability – the displaced, the ones without a home, the victims in need of others’ aid and generosity – are only rarely understood as agents of political transformation (Stierl 2018, p. 1; see also Nyers 2010; Stierl 2012).

Framing migrants as victims may be problematic in limiting opportunities for migrants to participate more fully in their new communities – speaking rather than being spoken for. In Chapter Five, I noted that migrants attempt to link with humanitarian organisations through the groups they connect with as an act of agency to foster a better community integration experience. A resilient survivor framing highlights the potential for both agency and such community integration transformations.

6.4 Advancing Understandings of Migration and Social Capital

That brings us to the third and last practical-theoretical contribution: advancing understandings of how social capital can be generated through networks, and its possible roles on high-risk routes. Building on the groundwork laid especially in works by Schapendonk (2011; see also Schapendonk 2012; 2013; 2015; 2018; 2020; Schapendonk and Steel 2015; Schapendonk et al. 2015), this thesis has endeavoured to contribute to much-needed interventions along the Sahara routes and offer some substantial advances to the existing literature, in particular along these high-risk routes where more data is needed to understand the experiences of migrants fully. The thesis builds on the theoretical insights Schapendonk offers to help us understand how

migrants seek to network-derived social capital while in transit from sub-Saharan Africa to the EU. Specifically, Schapendonk (2015) examined migrant networks on high-risk Sahara routes and how these networks are highly malleable and changeable and provided a general understanding of social capital in this migration context.

It is here where my research diverges and offers a deeper systematic analysis of why and how migrants seek to develop networks while in transit on high-risk routes, how they use existing networks and how both may extend into their efforts to integrate into their destination country in Europe. This thesis highlights six specific factors motivating migrants on these routes to seek to form networks and six ways in which migrants seek to derive social capital as part of their survival strategy on these routes. It also highlights an important distinction from other high-risk routes, particularly in the Americas. That is, in the Sahara, migrants typically do not have contacts at their intended destination country before starting their journey.

Furthermore, the thesis highlights how these efforts are carried forward in the destination country as part of a migrant integration effort. Here, this thesis advances the existing literature in linking the experiences in transit and destination. This research also is detailed in its results from participants' experiences confirming distinct factors and identifying critical ways migrants derive social capital through networks. Finally, it draws on the insights of humanitarian organisations to illuminate areas of further investigation.

This research again identified at least six factors in network-derived social capital as a survival strategy during high-risk migration in the Sahara context. This research shows and is supported by others that most respondents travelled alone initially (see also Schapendonk 2011). Travelling alone is a significant risk the further one

travels from home along these routes, and the more vulnerable the situation for the solo traveller. From lack of knowledge of routes, battling the elements to bearing the psychological burden alone is tremendous stress over time. The risks of travelling alone are more significant than travelling with others. The vulnerability to human trafficking is enormous. The increasing securitised nature of these routes and policies designed to impede migration make it necessary to construct alternative travelling methods. Finding ways to join a group strengthens a migrant's sense of connection, belonging and safety.

Much of the migration literature has turned more and more towards network effects and social capital. The focus of migration literature is on cases from the Central America and Mexico Routes to the United States, and there are some similarities. For example, using human smugglers is an integral part of the network social capital approach pursued by migrants along those routes, especially as border policies restrict or border sections undergo greater scrutiny (Campos and Cantalopiedra 2022). More questions need to be pursued, such as how smugglers are convincing migrants to take on these services. It is not the strong social ties that support migrants. Here it is these weak ties of bridging social capital in their relationships with smugglers where rumour intelligence in this region prevails.

This research has helped to understand better how migrants use social capital while in transit and is strengthening the social capital scholarship with this contribution. Migrants exercise agency as resilient survivors by attempting to derive social capital through networks during their high-risk migration and their integration experience. Consistent with the literature on social capital, there are three types of network-derived social capital identified in this study, bonding, bridging and linking social capital. Furthermore, my research presents six ways that migrants derive network social capital:

1. Using kinship connections (bonding)
2. Forming groups in transit (bonding)
3. Making use of informal labour networks (bridging)
4. Using human smugglers (bridging)
5. Using social networking applications (bonding and bridging)
6. Using humanitarian organisations (linking)

The emphasis also is that migrants are leaning on weak ties in the absence of strong ties during this experience.

The notion of collective migrant agency has been explored to some extent on other high-risk migration routes, most notably Central America and Mexico Routes to the United States, by authors such as Wheatley and Gomberg-Munoz (2016). This thesis deepens, extends and reinforces that work in the Sahara Desert context. In these environments filled with violence, a lack of regard by authorities and the lived experience of exploitation by many, including smugglers, migrants seek where possible to band together. However, there is a substantive difference highlighted by the thesis. Migrants travelling through the Sahara Desert typically started out travelling alone, in contrast to groups forming from the start along the Central American-Mexico-US routes. Participants in this study express the critical importance of finding others along the routes, upon hearing other nationals of their country of origin, linking up with them and carrying these relationship connections onward – through the Mediterranean and in their destination country to support their integration efforts.

6.5 Securitisation and Neo-Colonial Power

6.5.1 Migration and Competing Regionalisms

The EU and the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) both have freedom of movement regimes within their organisations and territories. However, the enforcement of migration by the EU outside its borders poses a challenge to ECOWAS'

freedom of movement principles, and to an emerging free movement regime within the African Union. This issue raises significant questions regarding the full implications of extraterritorial enforcement of migration, in particular the relationship between forms of population mobility and their encounters with the conceptual, organisation and territorial borders of states (Geddes 2005; see also Flahaux and De Haas 2016; Zanker 2019). Such concerns connect, for example, with Torpeys' well-known analysis of limitations on mobility, where:

Modern states, and the international state system of which they are a part, have expropriated from individuals and private entities the legitimate 'means of movement', particularly though by no means exclusively across international boundaries (Torpey 2000, p. 4).

Researchers have long examined and sought to explain the emergence of free movement mechanisms in a regional organisation, particularly the EU (Guild 1999; Scholten and van Ostaijen 2018; Geddes 2022). The EU's free movement regime has developed over decades. Since Article 20 of the TFEU and Article 9 of the TEU citizens of EU Member States have held formal EU citizen status (Treaty of the Functioning of the European Union 1958; Treaty of the European Union 1992; European Union 2008). As earlier discussed, in the Schengen region, comprised of 26 EU and affiliated states, all internal border controls have been abolished. Thus, the Schengen Area offers free movement to its citizens, allowing them to cross internal borders without undergoing immigration checks. However, Schengen poses a challenge regarding humanitarian assistance, as the Agreement obliges the Member States to protect external borders and maintain a standard visa policy to avoid migratory risk. As such, Schengen countries must carefully consider how they can best balance these obligations while still providing the necessary humanitarian aid (European Union 1985; Hanke et al. 2019).

In chapter three, I highlighted the tensions between the EU's embrace of free movement for itself and its moves to effectively deny free movement through these agreements within regions of Africa that are trying to establish it. ECOWAS and the African Union are working toward a free movement regime for people in the area, with ECOWAS' focus on intra-regional cooperation and the African Union's emphasis on pan-African integration (Arhin-Sam et al. 2022). An irony exists in understanding why organisations such as the EU have developed this internal freedom of movement regime yet, through extraterritorial enforcement mechanisms, restrict it for others. A nuanced understanding of the issue develops by analysing the legal implications and precedents with extraterritorial enforcement of migration (Trauner and Deimel 2013; Trauner and Servant 2016). Further challenging these developing free movement regimes is the external pressure from the EU, which leads us to the final theoretical contribution of extraterritorial enforcement and post-colonial power.

6.5.2 Extraterritorial Enforcement and Neo-Colonial Power

The thesis also makes some contributions to advancing understandings of neo-colonial power dynamics in Africa (Huggan 1997; Parashar and Schulz 2021). I work here from the conceptual framework of this thesis the analysis of extraterritorial enforcement from Chapter Three, which highlighted the implications of partnerships to deter migration. The oppressive history of colonial power from European countries such as France, Italy and Spain, in the leading African countries discussed in this thesis, Algeria, Libya, Morocco, Niger and Tunisia, still reverberates today (Rock 2017; Zanker 2019; Parashar and Schulz 2021).

The neo-colonial legacy may also be seen as manifest in agreements between the EU and several African countries, including Algeria, Libya, Morocco, Niger and Tunisia. These arrangements often continue the former colonial powers' influence over their once colonies rather than granting mutual benefit between equals—this neo-colonial power dynamic results in oppressive regimes limiting opportunities for legal and safe migration even further (Ronzitti 2009; Onar and Nicolaïdis 2013; Bøås 2021). As discussed in depth in Chapter Three, such dynamics are evident in instruments such as the Treaty of Friendship, Partnership and Cooperation between Italy and Libya, the Euro-Mediterranean Association Agreements with Algeria and Morocco and Tunisia and other funded arrangements by the EU with Morocco, Niger and Tunisia. (Libya 2009; Ronzitti 2009; European Parliament 2016b, European Commission 2017a; 2019; 2021c; European Union 1998; 2000b; 2005). This thesis has helped demonstrate that these are more than interstate agreements. They arguably are extensions of European dominance and power in Africa (Oğurlu 2018; Opi 2021).

Such a claim is similar to ones offered in the context of the International Criminal Court. The court for some critics is a tool for former colonising states to continue to exercise control over the formerly colonised, given its early emphasis on cases emerging from Africa (Schneider 2020). In other analyses, this neo-colonial power takes the form of economic exploitation in which neo-colonial powers deprive African countries of their natural resources or other partitions or the benefit of their former colonial masters (Miles 2015). Similarly, as the thesis has highlighted, the extraterritorial enforcement of migration may be framed as a direct extension of control by former colonising states. Such agreements and initiatives seek to deter migrant onward mobility to the European continent. The Euro-Mediterranean Association

Agreements are exemplars, in promoting freer trade and economic development in African states while seeking to suppress the freer movement of persons to Europe (European Union 1998; 2000b; 2005).

The neo-colonial power also manifests through the EU Courts and has been increasingly present in African geopolitical landscapes. Rulings from the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) impact neo-colonial justice systems, evidenced here in the following two case examples. In the first case, *Achbita v. G4S Secure Solutions*, the CJEU ruled that private employers could restrict religious symbols in their workplace. This ruling had significant neo-colonial implications for African countries, especially in Muslim countries where these private companies operated (Court of Justice of the European Union 2017b). It effectively meant that European companies run by primarily white owners operating in an African country had dominion over their Muslim employees, with the power to restrict religious practices in the workplace.

In the second case, *Council v. Front Polisario*, the CJEU ruled in favour of Front Polisario and annulled some Council of the European Union (CotEU) embedded decisions inside a more considerable negotiation between the EU through the CotEU and Morocco's contextualised association on fisheries. Specifically, in part of the case brought before it, these involved decisions on arrangements made regarding products originating in Western Sahara and destined for the EU. For context, Western Sahara is a disputed territory, formerly a colony of Spain which Morocco says belongs to them and is also claimed by the Front Polisario on behalf of the Sahrawi people of the area (Damis 1983; Maghraoui 2003). The Front Polisario brought the case before the European court. They argued that these arrangements provided for exploiting its natural

resources and encouraged Morocco's annexation of that territory (Court of Justice of the European Union 2016; 2021d; Council of the European Union 2018; European Union 2019).

One point of view of the CJEU's judgements in this matter act as a delegitimising function of Morocco's authority on the Western Sahara and brings up questions as to occupation (Wrangé 2019). Both examples suggest the influence on neo-colonial legal systems by decisions made at the supranational EU level.

6.5.3 Securitisation and Ethnicity: Internal Power

The EU, as neo-colonial power, has been increasingly displaying anti-migrant rhetoric and racism within its internal discourse. More than likely this has been a response to shifting demographics in Europe, with numerous and sustained migration events over land and sea from neo-colonial countries domestically in many EU Member States. Many EU countries either decreased their accommodation for migrants or outright reversed acceptance rates leading to a sharp rise in xenophobia. The result is an atmosphere of pervasive anxiety about national identity and culture.

The discussion of Chapter Five on anti-migrant rhetoric and its by-product of racism can help advance understandings of the exercise or emergence of neo-colonial power dynamics within the European Union (Huggan 2008; De Genova 2018; Beaman 2021). The chapter highlighted ways in which the securitised migration posed complications to migrants seeking to integrate into host countries. There was a presentation of an anti-migrant rhetoric cycle to spotlight the many forces at play in generating racism and xenophobia, from media coverage to migration events and the agenda of political parties. For example, some populist parties spur anti-migrant rhetoric

in framing migrants as ‘others’ (McDonnell and Bobba 2016; McDonnell 2017), and those others often are racialised and associated closely with formerly colonised states. There is a cautionary tale here for those holding extreme views, as it does seem that data is emerging that those members of populist political parties themselves run the risk of feeling stigmatised based on their ideological positioning (Ammassari 2022).

Hate crimes and racially targeted attacks against migrants have been trending upward within the EU (European Network Against Racism 2018). Institutional racism is another form of internal neo-colonial power over migrants and other minority groups. In addition, there is an internal power over migrants that is creating a racial imbalance against them, from barriers to accessing the formal labour market and the criminal justice system to segregation due to migration status. These imbalances invariably increase mistrust and suspicion between migrants and their host country (European Network Against Racism 2021; 2022). Even with EU instruments designed to counter racism and xenophobia, such as the Joint Action Plan and the Council Framework Decision to criminalise forms of expression, such as hate speech or other discriminatory incitements, the same challenges remain with implementation and enforcement (Council of the European Union 1996; 2008; European Network Against Racism 2018).

All this is against the backdrop of measures to combat human smuggling and clandestine migration. Nations in North and West Africa are the frontline border patrol for the EU, incentivised to act with pre-emptive enforcement. However, when it comes to Libya, the effects are chilling. A recent flash update report details over five thousand migrants detained in detention centres after authorities conducted a security operation in Hai Alandalus (Displacement Tracking Matrix 2021a). While the international community continues to denounce the arbitrary detention of migrants, the EU estimates

that 90% granted international protection have reached their border through clandestine means (European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation 2016). While shared responsibility between Member States inches forward with ways to embrace migration reform of Dublin III, calls continue for structural transformation of the migration governance system and expansion of legal avenues for those seeking asylum and those who want to come to the EU to work. They also agree that migrants are stigmatised before they even arrive at the external borders of Member States (European Commission 2022b).

Rather than the ever-increasing reduction of ways for people to migrate to the European continent and barring a complete deconstruction of the administrative state, perhaps areas for compromise are available. A shift to arenas where change is progressive and where concepts of hospitality and representation link migrant integration to the strength of political participation and trust (Fine and Ypi 2016; Fennema and Tillie 2001; Jacobs and Tillie 2004; Farahani 2021 see also Eckersley 2007). Moreover, promoting migrant participation and representation could provide a necessary antidote to the unchecked internal power of the political elites and racialisation over migrants, for example, a counterbalance from the agenda of nativists and the neoconservative faction of populist nationalists. It could help to create a bulwark against collective discrimination, which, left unchecked, risks industrialised racism.

Chapter Seven

Conclusions

7.1 Summary Review

7.2 Directions for Future Scholarship

7.1 Summary Review

I began this thesis by presenting two primary research questions it would investigate:

- 1) How do migrants seek to develop and utilise network social capital
 - c) as a survival strategy on high-risk migration routes?
 - d) to facilitate integration into their host society?
- 2) How does analysing migrants' survival strategy on high-risk migration routes help us better understand states' moves toward increasingly securitised and extended enforcement regimes?

I have worked throughout to advance understandings of what is happening on high-risk migration routes, and what the implications may be. I have also wished to present it as much as possible through the migrant's own experience. I'll now take the time I have left in these remaining pages to review the central arguments of the main core chapters. To that end, I have structured this chapter into two sections. The first offers a summary review by chapter, where I will reinforce the findings and areas of contribution. The second offers a presentation of some directions for future scholarship.

Chapter Two examined the existing research salient to this thesis. I first provided background on high-risk migration, including data on fatalities at sea and in the desert and physical hardships many experience on these routes. I then discussed the literature on migrant agency and how it intersects with existing treatments of social capital and migration, where much of the research focuses on the routes from Central America and Mexico to the United States. I emphasised where my research branches off from the work of Schapendonk (2011; 2015), who has similarly studied migration patterns and survival strategies on high-risk Sahara routes. In that regard, I highlighted his contributions and the space left where my research has contributed in several ways,

primarily related to how migrants seek to develop social networks and derive forms of social capital from them *in transit* on high-risk routes.

Second, I discussed how this thesis focuses on how migrants who have formed such networks continue to develop them in various ways once they reach their destination countries. Ultimately, this investigation sought to further the knowledge deficit of migrant agency along the Sahara routes and contribute practically and theoretically to the literature surrounding high-risk migration. I then worked to show how existing treatments of such network formation by migrants are underdeveloped when it comes to understanding why and how migrants seek to develop these networks and derive crucial social capital from them while in transit on high-risk routes. That is, while researchers have extensively studied roles networks play in decisions to migrate, choice of destination city or country and related questions, there has been relatively little attention given to their roles in transit, in particular on high-risk routes. Nor has there been extensive exploration of how migrants who have formed such networks draw on them in various ways once they reach destination countries. Through this thesis I have sought to address both areas of underdevelopment in the literature.

In Chapter Three, I introduced the thesis's conceptual framework, which involves two pillars of migration governance: securitised migration and extraterritorial enforcement. The securitisation of migration, where political elites and others frame migration as a security threat rather than primarily a set of economic and processes, was introduced and discussed in the EU context. Such securitisation has centrally informed the EU's migration strategy, a twofold approach that extends enforcement through incentivised partnerships with North and West African states on the one hand and increases enforcement at EU borders and between the Member States on the other hand.

Such measures seek to deter clandestine migration flows and disrupt the human smuggling apparatus. I highlighted how, when it comes to the enforcement of migration, as routes become more scrutinised and governments simultaneously limit safe and legal pathways for migration, human smugglers become more sophisticated, and routes change to adapt.

More narrowly, the chapter focused on the evolution of a security-based approach to migration governance in the EU. I noted specific EU migration control mechanisms, including technology-based ones and those focused on the voluntary return of migrants. I then examined specific agreements the EU or its Member States have struck with African states, with emphasis on measures that have served to increase enforcement – and to increase risks to migrants – on already high-risk routes. Those include the Central Mediterranean Route to Italy and agreements with Niger, Libya and Tunisia; Atlantic Routes to Spain (Canary Islands), with Morocco as the leading African player; and enforcement on the Western Mediterranean Route to Spain (Ceuta and Melilla), and specifically the relationship with Algeria.

In Chapter Four, I presented my fieldwork and its findings. The fieldwork involved interviews conducted in Italy, Niger and The Gambia with 101 persons who had the experience of high-risk migration through the Sahara Desert and 16 interviews with staff of humanitarian organisations. Interview findings were subjected to open and axial coding, to identify recurring themes and relationships between themes. Findings were triangulated with reports from non-governmental organisations and other researchers' salient field work. The ensuing analysis revealed two main findings. The first relate to why migrants on high-risk routes seek to form networks and derive specific forms of social capital from them. These factors were: (1) having limited

resources, (2) having no contacts at the intended destination, (3) lacking knowledge of migration routes, (4) travelling alone, (5) vulnerability to authorities and (6) vulnerability to human smugglers and other actors. These six factors motivate migrants to develop networks in one or more of six primary ways: (1) forming groups in transit, (2) connecting with humanitarian organisations, (3) connecting with human smugglers, (4) integrating into informal labour networks, (5) using social networking applications and (6) seeking support from kinship networks.

In Chapter Five, I discussed how network-derived social capital is essential for migrants settling into a new environment and working towards stability. The chapter first explored the intricate details of the Common European Asylum System, designed to guide and manage claims for asylum seekers in EU countries. This system creates a framework where nations may implement stringent measures such as border controls, visa requirements and processing centres across Europe to better control migration flows into the region. As well as orientating readers on how this aspect fits within broader structures of governance around migration policy at both national and supranational levels, I provided detail on instruments used under CEAS guidelines along with outlining “Dublin III”—a system that assigns Member State responsibility to address migrant applications for asylum.

Proponents of Europeanisation see such processes as an approach to safeguarding migrants and European societies. They argue that shifting from traditional state-level control towards one centred at the supranational level support policies on migration to be unified across Member States, providing safer conditions for those travelling and decreasing bureaucratic obstacles in navigating access rights. As discussed, however, the EU has increasingly come into conflict with Member States over its migrant integration

policies and proposals, as many resist relinquishing national sovereignty in place of embracing a perceived dictated multiculturalism. One example is Italy, which emphasises national rights and places heavy security measures upon those who enter and penalise those who attempt to assist migrants to the safety of Italian shores.

I then shifted the discussion to migrant integration in such a context of securitisation and increasing restrictions. I presented another novel contribution of the thesis: its emphasis on ways in which migrants who reach destination cities often continue to draw on social networks they formed while in transit on high-risk routes. These types of social capital open potential resources and access to services by humanitarian organisations, such as arranging housing solutions and distributions of food and non-food items. In addition, network-derived social capital supports migrants working together to ensure a better integration experience into a destination country or host community while laying the foundations for further interpersonal connectivity among newly arriving migrants. Specifically, the chapter examined how migrants, utilising a mixture of formal and informal networks, strive to create resilient identities to survive within host societies. By accessing social capital through these networks, they are better positioned to confront anti-migrant rhetoric as well as make their voices heard when dealing with employment or community building opportunities. Overall, the chapter provided insights on how migrants exercise agency in the face of securitisation and risk. By maintaining ties made during transit or forming new groups to gain both bonding and bridging forms of social capital, they better access resources to help them adjust to their destination while simultaneously developing meaningful community connections.

In Chapter Six I discussed the areas of contribution and significance of my thesis. The main contributions highlighted were: (1) an improved comprehension of Sahara

Routes, the risks migrants face on them, and how extended EU enforcement has intensified those risks; (2) a greater understanding of migrant agency, (3) how migration and social capital are related and (4) securitisation and post-colonial power which is divided into the three subsections of (4a) migration and competing regionalisms, (4b) extraterritorial enforcement and neo-colonial power and (4c) securitisation and ethnicity: internal power.

This research has sought to shed light on the profoundly challenging and often deadly dangers faced by migrants attempting trans-Saharan journeys. By analysing international political agreements, we understand how they shape migratory routes and glean insights into the motivations driving this harrowing journey from those who have made it. This fieldwork conducted offers us invaluable perspectives from migrants themselves about one of the world's most treacherous contexts for migration today.

This thesis offers an alternative perspective on migrant agency. It highlights ways in which migrants are more appropriately framed as agents rather than passive victims or perpetrators, and how the specific agency they exercise is best framed as that of the resilient survivor. Resilient survivors, it was shown, are individuals who, when faced with significant physical (medical), psychological or other trauma, develop adaptation and coping strategies that strengthen them to survive and ultimately aid recovery. Throughout, the thesis has highlighted ways in which migrants navigating perilous routes are misframed as victims, villains, or 'heroes' of sending states. These individuals have faced extreme hardships with adaptation, fortitude and resilience. The adaptations of primary interest throughout were efforts to develop and use networks and derive valuable social capital from them while in transit on high-risk routes. Overall, by examining the concept of social capital and its capacity to shape individual experiences, my aim has been to

provide deeper insight that informs practical and theoretical approaches towards understanding the dynamics of these high-risk journeys.

Chapter Six also highlighted some broader theoretical implications of the EU's securitised migration and more stringent enforcement regime. Implications were highlighted with respect to competing regional free movement regimes, extraterritorial enforcement and securitisation and ethnicity in the context of migrant integration. By comparing the EU and ECOWAS's respective regionalisms, this subsection interrogated how their freedom of movement regimes clash in response to extraterritorial migration enforcement. It highlighted the tensions between the EU enshrining of freedom of movement within its territory and the irony in its attempts to restrict the same in the ECOWAS region.

This thesis delved into the implications of extraterritorial enforcement and neo-colonial power dynamics. Drawing from historical perspectives and current agreements between the EU and Algeria, Libya, Morocco, Niger and Tunisia as examples, it analysed past and present trends to examine such effects. Through this analysis, the thesis has sought to advance understandings of how these agreements between African countries and the EU may be appropriately framed as a resurgence of neo-colonial power and dominion of the EU in Africa.

This chapter culminates in reaffirming the cyclical process behind anti-migrant rhetoric, highlighting how some political elites perpetuate racism and xenophobia in the context of migrant integration. Political leaders often utilise language designed to scare citizens into believing their jobs and security are at risk due to migrants entering the country. Unsurprisingly, media coverage often perpetuates these stereotypes — as well as negative stories associated with those seeking asylum or refuge — further inciting

fear among individuals and creating hostility towards migrants. Events such as border closures and deportations only deepen this atmosphere by emphasising an alleged threat posed by foreigners attempting entry into host countries.

7.2 Directions for Future Scholarship

This section focuses on possible directions for future research. A few discrete proposals are listed here. There are some practical, some theoretical and some hybrids of both.

The first is to continue and expand interventions in the Sahara-Sahel.¹⁷ The risks associated with migrants travelling routes through this region in attempts to reach Europe continue unabated. This research reveals that most migrants do not know anyone at their intended destination. As mentioned, this is a clear distinction from the experience of those travelling routes from Central America and Mexico to the United States — an interesting and unique aspect of a migrant's experience. It raises potentially essential questions about why this is and especially what its significance is for the risks they face in the Sahara.

Second, there is room for comparative work on other high-risk migration routes, such as those through Southeast Asia (see figure 7.1). The Bay of Bengal and the Andaman Sea are treacherous sea crossings that migrants attempt. In 2015 alone, records indicate over a thousand deaths at sea in those areas. Since then, estimates are that thousands more have perished. Further, the Bay of Bengal and the Andaman Sea have long been hubs for human smugglers and trafficking networks, with reports of hidden camps in the jungles along the Thai-Malaysia border. Those held captive in these camps are typically migrants who must pay a ransom before being granted onward

¹⁷ Eight countries comprise the Sahara-Sahel and include Algeria, Chad, Libya, Mali, Mauritania, Morocco, Niger and Tunisia (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development 2014).

passage. In many cases, those held hostages suffer from extreme forms of abuse, exploitation and violence at the hands of their captors (Pickering and Powell 2017; Missing Migrants Project 2022a). Such dynamics establish a significant basis for comparison with smuggling syndicates on the Sahara routes.

Figure 7.1 High-Risk Migration Routes: Southeast Asia

Source: Missing Migrants Project 2017.

Separately, I am interested to investigate migrant decision making, and specifically how prospect theory may give insight into decision making during high-risk migration. Prospect theory is an alternative to the traditional rational choice theory. According to prospect theory, people tend to focus on potential losses more than gains when making decisions, leading them to make decisions that are only sometimes in their best interest. Additionally, the theory suggests that people are more likely to take risks when avoiding losses than when attempting to maximise gains. Prospect theory offers essential insight into human decision-making processes and can provide alternative explanations for why individuals may act contrary to expectations (Kahneman and Tversky 1979; Levy 1997; Clark and Lisowski 2017).

For example, studies have focused on farmers in developing countries who are offered bioengineered seeds, with the promise of higher yields. However, farmers are unwilling to accept the risk. For the farmer, it is not just a question of yield (Herrera-Estrella and Alvarez-Morales 2001; Qaim and Kouser 2013; Azadi et al. 2022). For them, it is a question of yield variability. One year of non-producing yield is riskier than nine years of above-average crops. For migrants making decisions during high-risk migration, the hypothesis is that they also would be interested in the variability and not the average. They are motivated by fear of abuse and loss – ultimately the loss of life.

Prospect theory is a tool to evaluate individual decision-making (Vis 2011). Therefore, an open question is whether it applies to a group or collective decision-making. Investigating how prospect theory applies to migrant decision-making could provide insight into the motivations of migrants and how contextual factors impact their decisions, for example, decisions on whether and/or when to abandon their migration attempt and return to their homes. Studying prospect theory in a migrant context could

also inform policymaking and help guide interventions that support the needs of migrant populations. Prospective studies may reveal ways for states and other stakeholders to improve the experiences of migrants during their transition process. Thus, further research on prospect theory and its migration application is warranted. This research has broad implications for theoretical development and social welfare policies concerning migrants.

Afterword

My scholarship record reflects my passion for the work and the seriousness of the issues. Additionally, I intend to continue strengthening the links between academia and practice. In this thesis, I have re-exposed deep concerns about the treatment of migrants. Along with the responsibility to teach and pass on what we know, this platform comes with it an obligation, in my view, to act and influence outcomes. To spark debate and to give altitude to those ideals that help empower the individual and motivate change.

Though outside the scope of this research venture, I would be remiss unless I use this opportunity to advocate for innovation regarding how we collectively intervene with migrants. In this short piece, I draw from my ten years of experience in migration practice at the international level and this PhD process to highlight areas to invigorate our humanitarian and policy-driven approaches. In addition, I intend to reinforce the importance of looking for alternatives as we evolve solutions in the migration space. In line with this purpose are four recommendations for reform.

The first is to continue to frame migrants as resilient survivors instead of victims and mainstream this principle into both humanitarian programming and government policy initiatives. To do so promotes agency, recovery and strength for migrants. The second is to create opportunities for more direct face-to-face interviews with migrants on high-risk migration routes and in destination countries. Doing so promotes better data collection practices and a deeper understanding of migrant experiences to benefit responses.

The third is to foster more significant community connections with migrants to support a more inclusive integration experience. I propose that the more active

participation, the more room there is for migrant engagement and representation of the body politic as agents (Tazzioli 2015; Monforte and Morales 2018). One way to encourage migrant community connections is by implementing democratic tools such as ‘mini-publics’. Mini-publics comprise randomly selected citizens or another proxy to ensure robust representation to engage in a particular issue that affects everyone (Elstub 2014; Escobar and Elstub 2017; Guziana 2021). The more migrants pivot to political participation and representation—the more integration has excellent prospects of success. One area in this regard that is structurally weak are tools such as the census, which is generally disadvantageous to migrants (Koser 2010; Jandl 2011; Devkota 2022; Collyer 2023). Therefore, I suggest continuing to build migrants into EU population census data, like in housing (European Parliament 2008; Kraler and Reichel 2010; Statistical Office of the European Union 2022). Better representation also means potentially better access to services to support migrant integration. As Petter (2021; 2022) points out, there is an opportunity for stronger ties to the host community through constituency representation. Doing so promotes greater participation and better representation for migrants in host cities.

The fourth is to expand the definition of missing migrants. Missing Migrants Project (2022a) defines a missing migrant as a person who dies or is missing, presumed dead, in the migration process towards an international destination, regardless of legal status. I also recommend including data on deaths in detention and reception centres and those occurring in destination countries. Creating more reporting pathways encourages better and more data collection on migrant fatalities. More data supports greater rigour in incident investigations. Doing so potentially fosters greater openness and

transparency of governments to document and publish incidents of fatalities. It is critical data to include if we are collectively to generate and act on a global reference.

Four Areas to Explore Policy Alternatives

- 1. Frame migrants as resilient survivors instead of victims, promoting agency, recovery, and strength.
- 2. Create opportunities for direct interviews with migrants on high-risk migration routes and in destination countries—better data on migrant experiences.
- 3. Foster community connections to support more inclusive migrant integration—which leads to more participation and better representation.
- 4. Expand the definition of Missing Migrants to include deaths in detention and reception centres and in destination countries. Document and publish.

Source (icons): United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs 2020.

Combined, this is a four-pronged approach to championing real change. It heralds the potential for a better-lived experience for those embarking on the migration and integration journey, in which individuals exercise their fundamental human right to seek a better life. The odds continue to stack against them. The opportunity exists to shift from exclusion to support for productive contributors to economic and social growth. The time is now to be more engaged, not less. To speak up louder, not softer. Let us be steadfast and in common purpose for real achievements on safe migration and greater inclusion of migrants.

Appendices

Appendix A: High-Risk Migration Participant Questions

1. How old are you?
2. Where are you from?
3. What is your nationality?
4. Why did you decide to leave your home country?
5. Where did you plan to go?
6. Did you know anybody at your intended destination?
7. Who did you travel with, or did you travel alone? If with others how did you meet them and did they know the route beforehand, to the best of your knowledge?
8. How did you find your way? How did you find your information along the way?

Please describe.

9. Did you know the route before you left? How much did you know about the route (if travelling alone for the first time)?
10. Did you have help?
12. Who helped you? Who were they? Where were they from? How did you meet?
13. How did you find those who helped you?
14. In what ways did they help you? What did you share? (Food, money, supplies). Did you always travel together?
15. How did you pay for your journey?
16. How much did you pay for your journey?
17. Do you have a mobile phone? If so, how many?
18. What did you use your mobile phone for primarily? (GPS? Money transfers? Communication?)
19. How did you receive money on your journey? (Working? Family? Western Union?)
20. Did you work along the way? If you worked along the way, what did you do for work? How did you find work?
21. Did any humanitarian organisation help you along the way?
22. Which ones?
23. Did you know about these humanitarian organisations before you left for your journey?
24. How did these humanitarian organisations assist you?
25. Please describe your journey with as much detail as you would like.
26. What are some of the most difficult things that happened on your journey?

26. How is it for you now in your destination or return home country?
27. Have you, do you intend to apply for asylum in your destination country? If so, what was the outcome?
28. Are you receiving help now? If so from whom?
29. What advice would you like to give someone who is thinking about crossing the Sahara Desert or the Mediterranean Sea?
30. Is there anything else you would like to add?
31. Do you know anyone else I could talk to about their experience?

Appendix B: Humanitarian Sector Participant Questions

1. Please describe your area of focus in your organisation?
2. What is your experience working on high-risk migration routes? High-risk migration routes, including those through the Sahara Desert, West Africa, the Balkans, the Central, Eastern, Western Mediterranean Sea, or Central America and Mexico to the U.S. Border.
3. Please explain how your work supports migrants on high-risk migration routes, integration in a host, transit or return country? In what ways is your organisation supporting migrants on high-risk migration routes?
4. What factors do you think are currently influencing these high-risk migration routes and impacting a 'migrant's decision on which way to go?
5. How do you see migrants constructing and using network-derived social capital during their high-risk migration experience? How do you see migrants using these networks to support integration in either a host, transit or return country? Please provide as much detail as possible describing what you mean.

Examples of network-derived social capital include forming ties along the way to find information, resources, help, use of social media, access to humanitarian organisations, family, smugglers, etc.

6. Do you see migrants using the social ties they formed on the journey to help with their integration into a host city? Are these different networks in your view? How so?
7. What do you see as some of the vulnerability's migrants face on high-risk migration routes?
8. What do see as some of the biggest challenges in collecting data along these high-risk migration routes?
9. What more needs to happen to help support migrants in high-risk migration routes?
10. Is there anything else you would like to add?
11. Is there anyone else I might speak to about their own experience as a humanitarian working on high-risk migration routes?

Glossary

Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration
Asylum Seeker
Clandestine Migration
Common European Asylum System
Displacement
Displacement Tracking Matrix (DTM)
Enforced Disappearance
Europeanisation
Extraterritorial
Final Decision
First Instance Decision
Gender-Based Violence (GBV)
High-Risk Migration
Hotspot Approach
Human Smuggling
Human Trafficking
Migrant
Migrant Agency
Migrant Integration
Migration Governance
Migration Management
Missing Migrant
Mixed Migration
Neo-Colonialism
Network-Derived Social Capital
Non-Refoulement

Person Granted Subsidiary Protection Status

Racism

Recasting (of legislation)

Refugee (1951 Convention)

Refugee (EU context)

Refugee (Mandate)

Resilient Survivor

Securitised Migration

Shengen Aquis

Stranded Migrant

Survivor of Gender-Based Violence

Survivor of Trafficking

Terrorist Attack

Torture

Unauthorised Migrant

UN-Related Organisation

Xenophobia

Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration: Administrative, logistical, or financial support, including reintegration assistance, to migrants who are unwilling or determine it is impossible to remain in their host or transit country and return to their country of origin.¹⁸

Asylum Seeker: An individual who is seeking international protection. In countries with individualized procedures, an asylum seeker is someone whose claim has not yet been finally decided on by the country in which he or she has submitted it. Not every asylum seeker will ultimately be recognized as a refugee. Every recognised refugee is initially an asylum seeker.

Clandestine Migration: Persons who depart from, pass through, or arrive in a nation's territory contravening relevant international multilateral or bilateral instruments or agreements or national laws or regulations.¹⁹

Common European Asylum System: A framework of agreed rules which establish common procedures for international protection and a uniform status for those who are granted refugee status or subsidiary protection based on the full and inclusive application of the Geneva Refugee Convention and Protocol and which aims to ensure fair and humane treatment of applicants for international protection, to harmonise asylum systems in the EU and reduce the differences between Member States on the basis of binding legislation, as well as to strengthen practical cooperation between national asylum administrations and the external dimension of asylum.²⁰

Displacement: The movement of persons who have been forced or obliged to flee or to leave their homes or places of habitual residence, in particular because of or in order to

¹⁸ Unless otherwise indicated, definitions in this glossary are adapted and sourced from international migration law, glossary on migration (International Organization for Migration 2019a).

¹⁹ Adapted from Convention (No. 143) concerning migrations in abusive conditions and the promotion of equality of opportunity and treatment of migrant workers. Adopted by the General Conference of the International Labour Organisation at its sixtieth session, Geneva, 24 June 1975, Entry into force on 9 December 1978.

²⁰ Adapted from the European Migration Network (EMN) from Art. 78 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) (European Union 2008).

avoid the effects of armed conflict, situations of generalized violence, violations of human rights or natural or human-made disasters.²¹

Other classifications: cross-border displacement, disaster displacement, internally displaced persons, evacuation, forced migration, forcible transfer, protracted displacement.

Displacement Tracking Matrix (DTM): A system to track and monitor displacement and population mobility. DTM designs to capture, process and disseminate data to provide a better understanding of the movements and evolving needs of displaced populations, whether on-site or en route, regularly and systematically.²²

Enforced Disappearance: The arrest, detention, abduction, or any other form of deprivation of liberty by agents of the State or by persons or groups of persons acting with the authorization, support, or acquiescence of the State, followed by a refusal to acknowledge the deprivation of liberty or by concealment of the fate or whereabouts of the disappeared person, which place such a person outside the protection of the law.²³

Europeanisation: The process of influence deriving from European decisions and impacting Member States' policies and political administrative structures.²⁴

Extraterritorial: The processes of delegating or transferring tasks related to migration control to third countries. It is also referred to in the literature as the externalisation of migration governance or policies. The externalisation of migration control to third countries is at multi- and bi-lateral levels. Extraterritorial initiatives also include measures such as interdiction at sea and other *non-entrée (no entry)* policies like carrier liability and visa requirements.²⁵

²¹ Adapted from Guiding Principles on Internal Displacement, annexed to United Nations Commission on Human Rights, Report of the Secretary-General's Representative, Mr Francis M. Deng, Submitted under Commission Resolution 1997/39, Addendum (11 February 1998) UN Doc. E/CN.4/1998/53/Add.2, para. 2 of the introductions.

²² Adapted from Displacement Tracking Matrix <dtm.iom.int/about>.

²³ International Convention for the Protection of All Persons from Enforced Disappearance, Adopted 12 January 2007, General Assembly resolution 61/177, Entry into force 23 December 2010.

²⁴ Héritier et al., 2001, p. 3.

²⁵ Adapted from (Hathaway 1992; Hathaway 2005; Den Heijer 2012; Hirsch and Bell 2017; Crisp 2022; International Migration Research Network 2022).

Final Decision: A decision on whether the third-country national or stateless person be granted refugee or subsidiary protection status by virtue of Directive 2011/95/EU and which is no longer subject to a remedy within the framework of Chapter V of this Directive, irrespective of whether such remedy has the effect of allowing applicants to remain in the Member States concerned pending its outcome. The asylum procedures and the numbers/levels of decision-making bodies differ between Member States. The true ‘final instance’ may be, according to national legislation and administrative procedures, a decision of the highest national court. However, it is not intended that these statistics should cover rare or exceptional cases determined by the highest courts. Thus, the statistics related to the ‘final decisions’ should refer to decisions against which there is no further possibility to appeal on the substance of the decision and only on procedural grounds.²⁶

First Instance Decision: A decision (positive and negative) considering application for international protection as well as the grant of authorisation to stay for humanitarian reasons, including a decision under priority and accelerated procedures taken by administrative or judicial bodies in Member States. For instance, a decision includes a decision granted to persons who are subject of the Dublin Regulation (Council Regulation 604/2013/EC).²⁷

Gender-Based Violence (GBV): An umbrella term for any harmful act that is perpetrated against a person’s will and is based on socially ascribed, i.e., gender, differences between males and females. This includes acts that inflict physical, sexual, or mental harm or suffering, threats of such acts, coercion and denial of resources, opportunities, or services, forced marriage and other deprivations of liberty. These acts occur in public or in private.

High-Risk Migration: is defined here as the movement of persons on routes where significant numbers of fatalities have occurred, and where travel conditions are such

²⁶ Adapted from Glossary: Asylum decisions. Statistics explained (Statistical Office of the European Union 2021a).

²⁷ Adapted from European Commission, Decisions on application and resettlement.

that those on the move face a heightened likelihood of exploitation and mistreatment, injury or death. See also clandestine migration.

Hotspot Approach: Approach where the European Union Agency for Asylum (EUAA), the European Border and Coast Guard Agency (FRONTEX) and Eurojust work on the ground with authorities of frontline EU Member States which are facing disproportionate migration pressure at the EU's external borders to help fulfil their obligations under EU law and swiftly identify, register and fingerprint arriving migrants.²⁸

Human Smuggling: The procurement, to obtain, directly or indirectly, a financial or other material benefit, of the clandestine entry of a person into a state of which the person is not a national or a permanent resident.²⁹

Other classifications: people smuggling, smuggling of migrants.

Human Trafficking: The recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring or receipt of persons, by means of the threat or use of force or other forms of coercion, of abduction, of fraud, of deception, of the abuse of power or of a position of vulnerability or of the giving or receiving of payments or benefits to achieve the consent of a person having control over another person, for the purpose of exploitation. Exploitation shall include, at a minimum, the exploitation of the prostitution of others or other forms of sexual exploitation, forced labour or services, slavery, or practices like slavery, servitude, or the removal of organs.³⁰

Other classifications: child trafficking, trafficking in persons

²⁸ Adapted from European Commission, Migration and Home Affairs <ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/pages/glossary/hotspot-approach_en>.

²⁹ Adapted from Protocol against the Smuggling of Migrants by Land, Sea and Air, supplementing the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organised Crime ((adopted 15 November 2000, Entry into force 28 January 2004) 2241 UNTS 507) Art. 3(a).

³⁰ Protocol to Prevent, Suppress and Punish Trafficking in Persons, Especially Women and Children, Supplementing the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organised Crime, Adopted 15 November 2000, Entry into force 25 December 2003, 2237 UNTS 319, Art. 3(a).

Migrant: Migrant is an umbrella term undefined in international law. It reflects the understanding of a person who moves away from their usual residence, whether within a country or across an international border, permanently or temporarily and for various reasons. Such reasons may include environmental, economic and political instability or social mobility. The term is applied here, including several well-defined legal categories of people, such as asylum seekers, migrant workers and refugees. Other categories include smuggled migrants and those whose status or means of movement lacks definition under international law, such as international students and the internally displaced.³¹

Migrant Agency: Exploring how individuals exercise agency on high-risk migration routes and at destination communities. Expressions of migrant agency include specific adaptation and response strategies or instances of resistance to a securitised migration and migrant integration environment.³²

Migrant Integration: A range of actions and policies involving a wide variety of actors across levels of governance, national, supranational and international, that focus on forms of adaptation, cultural, economic, political and social by host societies and migrants.³³

Migration Governance: The combined frameworks of legal norms, laws and regulations, policies and traditions, and organisational structures, international, national, regional and subnational—and the relevant processes that shape and regulate States’ approaches concerning migration in all its forms, addressing rights and responsibilities, and promoting international cooperation.

Migration Management: The management and implementation of the whole set of activities primarily by States within national systems or through bilateral and multilateral cooperation, concerning all aspects of migration and the mainstreaming of migration considerations into public policies. The term refers to planned approaches to

³¹ Adapted from (Nail 2015; IOM 2019b).

³² Adapted from (Mainwaring 2016).

³³ Adapted from (Geddes and Scholten 2015).

the implementation and operationalisation of policy, administrative and legislative frameworks developed by the institutions in charge of migration.

Missing Migrant: A person who dies or is missing, presumed dead, in the process of migration towards an international destination, regardless of legal status.³⁴

Mixed Migration: A movement in which people are travelling together, using the same or similar routes and means of transport, and for different reasons. People travelling as part of mixed migration flows have varying needs and profiles.³⁵

Other classifications: mixed flows, mixed movements

Neo-Colonialism: The policy of the powerful developed countries use of cultural, economic, political and social influence to spread their hegemony to the previous colonies without demeaning their national status as colonies. Neo-colonialism deals with theories of capitalism, cultural and economic imperialism.³⁶

Network-Derived Social Capital: The connections, usually location-specific, an individual develops that provide value in pursuing one's objectives. Relationships that are influential and potentially more effective in supporting an individual's aspirations than operating alone.³⁷

Non-Refoulement: The prohibition for States to extradite, deport, expel, or otherwise return a person to a country where his or her life or freedom would be threatened, or where there are substantial grounds for believing that he or she would risk being subjected to torture or other cruel, inhuman and degrading treatment or punishment, or would be in danger of being subjected to enforced disappearance, or of suffering another irreparable harm.

³⁴ Adapted from (Missing Migrants Project 2022a).

³⁵ Adapted from United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, The 10-Point Action Plan, 2016 – Glossary, December 2016, p. 282.

³⁶ Adapted from <[differencebetween.com/difference-between-post-colonialism-and-vs-neo-colonialism](https://www.differencebetween.com/difference-between-post-colonialism-and-vs-neo-colonialism/)> (see also Huggan 1997).

³⁷ Authors definition.

Person Granted Subsidiary Protection Status: The protection given to a third-country national or a stateless person who does not qualify as a refugee yet in respect of whom substantial grounds have been shown for believing that the person concerned, if returned to their country of origin, or in the case of a stateless person to their country of former habitual residence, would face a real risk of suffering serious harm as defined in Art. 15 of Directive 2011/95/EU (Recast Qualification Directive), and to whom Art. 17 (1) and (2) of this Directive do not apply, and is unable or, owing to such risk, unwilling to avail themselves of the protection of that country.³⁸

Racism: The antagonism, discrimination or prejudice directed toward someone of a different race based on the belief that one's race is superior. Racism may manifest at the individual or institutional level. Consequently, the systemic nature and who holds power to perpetuate it is becoming more popular in the racism discourse. Institutional racism is how policies and practices create different outcomes for racial groups. The institutional policies may never mention any racial group, yet the effect is to create advantages for white people and disadvantages for other racial groups.³⁹

Recasting (of legislation): Recasting is like codification in that it brings together in a single new act a legislative act and all the amendments made to it. The new act passes through the entire legislative process and repeals all the acts under recast. However, unlike codification, recasting involves new substantive changes, as amendments are made to the original act during the preparation of the recast text.

There are two types of recasting: *vertical*: one original act and its amendments are incorporated into a single new act and *horizontal*: two or more original acts covering related subjects — and the amendments to them — are incorporated in a single new act.

Rules on the recasting technique are outlined in an interinstitutional agreement, signed on 28 November 2001, which provides special procedures for the legislative authority to concentrate its attention on those parts of the new legislative proposal.⁴⁰

³⁸ Adapted from Art. 2(f) of Directive 2011/95/EC (Recast Qualification Directive) of the European Parliament.

³⁹ Adapted from (European Network Against Racism 2022).

⁴⁰ Adapted from the European Commission Legal Services and (European Union 2001b).

Refugee (1951 Convention): A person who, owing to a well-founded fear of persecution for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group or political opinion, is outside the country of his nationality and owing to such risk and fear, is unwilling to avail themselves of the protection of that country, or who not having a nationality and being outside the country of their former habitual residence as a result of such events, and owing to such risk and fear, is unwilling to return to it.⁴¹

Refugee (EU context): Either a third-country national who, owing to a well-founded fear of persecution for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group or political opinion, is outside the country of his nationality and owing to such risk and fear, is unwilling to avail themselves of the protection of that country, or a stateless person who, being outside of the country of former habitual residence for the same reasons as mentioned above, is unable or, owing to such fear, unwilling to return to it, and to whom Art. 12 (Exclusion) of Directive 2011/95EU (Recast Qualification Directive) does not apply.⁴²

Refugee (Mandate): A person who qualifies for the protection of the United Nations provided by the High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), in accordance with UNHCR's Statute and, notably, subsequent General Assembly's resolutions clarifying the scope of UNHCR's competency, regardless of whether or not they are in a country that is a party to the 1951 Convention or the 1967 Protocol – or whether or not they are recognized by their host country as a refugee under either of these instruments.⁴³

Resilient Survivor: an individual's capacity to adapt — through an interaction of risk and protective factors — in the face of adversity and experience amidst high-risk migration and migrant integration.⁴⁴

⁴¹ Adapted from the Convention relating to the Status of Refugees, Adopted 28 July 1951, Entry into force 22 April 1954, 189 UNTS 137) Art. 1A(2).

⁴² Adapted from Art. 2(d) of Directive 2011/95/EC (Recast Qualification Directive) of the European Parliament.

⁴³ Adapted from United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, Handbook and Guidelines on Procedures and Criteria for Determining Refugee Status (2011) HCR/1P/4/enG/Rev. 3, 7, para. 16.

⁴⁴ Adapted from (Knight et al. 2022).

Securitized Migration: a process of social construction that pushes an area of regular politics into a place of security by resorting to a rhetoric of discursive emergence, threat and danger aimed at justifying the adoption of exceptional measures.⁴⁵

Schengen Acquis: Also known as the '*acquis communautaire*', it refers to the accumulated jurisprudence and legislation in the form of decisions, delegated acts, directives, implementing acts, regulations, treaties and case law of the Court of Justice of the European Union that makes possible the proper functioning of the Schengen Area.⁴⁶

Stranded Migrant: A person in a situation where it is not presently possible to return to their country of origin nor regularise their status in the country where they reside and do not have access to legal migration pathways which would allow them to move to another state. The term may also refer to migrants stranded due to humanitarian or security reasons in their country of destination, transit, or origin, preventing them from returning. At the same time, it is not presently possible to go elsewhere.

Survivor of Gender-Based Violence: A person who has the experience of gender-based violence.

Survivor of Trafficking: Any person subject to trafficking in human beings, regardless of whether the perpetrator is identified, apprehended, prosecuted, or convicted.

Terrorist Attack: The actual or threatened use of illegal force and violence by a non-state actor to attain an economic, political, religious, or social goal through coercion, fear, or intimidation.⁴⁷

Torture: Any act by which severe pain or suffering, whether physical or mental, is intentionally inflicted on a person for such purposes as obtaining from him or a third person information or a confession, punishing him for an act he or a third person has committed or is suspected of having committed, or intimidating or coercing him or a third person, or for any reason based on discrimination of any kind, when such pain or

⁴⁵ Adapted from (Wæver 1993).

⁴⁶ Adapted from Schengen Visa Info <schengenvisa.info/schengen-acquis>.

⁴⁷ Adapted from Global Terrorism Database (2021) Codebook.

suffering is inflicted by or at the instigation of or with the consent or acquiescence of a public official or other person acting in an official capacity.⁴⁸

Unauthorised Migrant: Are noncitizen living in their country of residence without a residency permit. Unauthorised migrants entered their country of residence without authorisation, overstayed a visa or did not leave after being ordered to do so. Children born to unauthorised migrant parents are also part of the unauthorised migrant population since most European countries do not have birthright citizenship, even though these children have never been part of the migration journey Unauthorised migrants include asylum seekers waiting for a decision on their case, as their future residential status is uncertain. Similarly, those waiting for deportation, even if suspended temporarily, are also considered part of this population. This definition does not include those with forged or false documents that allow migrants to enter and stay in Europe with authorisation from the viewpoint of authorities. Data systems do not permit researchers to capture this population.⁴⁹

UN-Related Organisation: An organisation whose cooperation agreement with the United Nations has many points in common with that of Specialised Agencies except that it does not refer to Article 57 and 63 of the United Nations Charter, relevant to Specialised Agencies. Nonetheless, these organisations are part and parcel of the work of the United Nations Systems Chief Executives Board for Coordination (UN Global Marketplace 2021).

Xenophobia: Attitudes, behaviours and prejudices that exclude, reject and often vilify persons based on the perception that they are foreigners or outsiders to the community, national or social identity. Often associated with anti-migrant rhetoric.

⁴⁸ Convention against torture and other cruel, inhuman, or degrading treatment or punishment, Adopted 10 December 1984, General Assembly resolution 39/46, Entry into force 26 June 1987, Article 27(1).

⁴⁹ Adapted from (Connor and Passel 2019).

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Anticipate More Extraordinary Decisions